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**Unschärfe Warnungen im Kraftfahrzeug
Eignet sich eine LED-Leiste als Anzeige für Fahrerassistenzsysteme?**

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Fuzzy warnings in motor vehicles

Is a LED bar suitable as a display for driver assistance systems?

From the Faculty of Life Sciences
of the Technical University Carolo-Wilhelmina

to Braunschweig

to obtain the degree

of doctor of natural sciences

(Dr. rer. nat.)

approved

D i s s e r t a t i o n

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Contents

List of Figures	7
List of abbreviations	9
Disclaimer	10
Acknowledgement	11
1 Introduction	12
1.1 The need for progress in road safety	12
1.2 Are autonomous vehicles the better drivers?	13
1.3 The Fuzzy Warning	16
1.4 Goal of this thesis	18
1.5 Structure of this thesis	18
2 Human visual processing	19
2.1 Human vision	19
2.2 Visual attention	20
2.2.1 How exactly does attention work?	21
2.2.2 Location and object-related attention	23
2.2.3 How to direct attention?	23
2.3 Peripheral perception	24
3 Previous findings on Fuzzy Warning	30
3.1 Peripheral Night Vision	30
3.2 Peripheral Collision Warning	31
3.3 Multimodal Warning Kit	32
3.4 Design of a peripheral display	33
3.5 Trials with a LED Matrix	35
3.6 Conclusion	37
3.7 Open questions	37
4 How well are peripheral light signals perceived under the windshield?	40
4.1 Introduction	40
4.2 Method	41
4.2.1 Study Design	41
4.2.2 Sample	41
4.2.3 Material	42
4.2.4 Procedure	43
4.3 Results	44
4.4 Discussion	47
5 Is a Fuzzy Warning intuitively understood?	49
5.1 Introduction	49

5.2	Method	49
5.2.1	Study Design	49
5.2.2	Sample	50
5.2.3	Material	50
5.2.4	Procedure	53
5.3	Results	53
5.3.1	Data preparation	53
5.3.2	Were the warnings intuitively understandable?	54
5.3.3	Was the driving behavior influenced by the warnings?	55
5.3.4	How were the three systems assessed?	57
5.4	Discussion	58
6	Is the Fuzzy Warning perceived peripherally?	60
6.1	Introduction	60
6.2	Method	61
6.2.1	Test Design	61
6.2.2	Sample	61
6.2.3	Material	61
6.2.4	Procedure	65
6.3	Results	65
6.3.1	With which warning did the drivers react better?	65
6.3.2	Which warning was being looked at more frequently?	66
6.3.3	Which warning was preferred by the test drivers?	67
6.4	Discussion	69
7	Does the driver react faster to a Fuzzy Warning than to a symbolic warning in the combined display?	71
7.1	Introduction	71
7.2	Method	72
7.2.1	Study Design	72
7.2.2	Sample	72
7.2.3	Material	73
7.2.4	Procedure	74
7.3	Results	75
7.3.1	Data preparation	75
7.3.2	Which of the warnings was responded to most quickly?	75
7.3.3	Was there a sign of an effect of the warning sound?	76
7.3.4	How were the systems evaluated?	76
7.4	Discussion	77
8	Can the gaze be guided with the Fuzzy Warning?	80
8.1	Introduction	80
8.2	Method	82
8.2.1	Test Design	82
8.2.2	Sample	82
8.2.3	Material	82
8.2.4	Procedure	84
8.3	Results	85
8.3.1	Did the LED warning direct the gaze towards the hazard?	85
8.3.2	Eye movements at potential hazard	85
8.3.3	Eye movements during the critical event	86

8.3.4	Was the direction hint understood?	87
8.3.5	Was the LED warning able to improve the drivers' reactions?	87
8.4	Discussion	87
9	How do drivers react to fuzzy fog information?	91
9.1	Introduction	91
9.2	Method	92
9.2.1	Test Design	92
9.2.2	Sample	92
9.2.3	Material	92
9.2.4	Procedure	93
9.3	Results	93
9.3.1	How did the drivers react to the fog information?	93
9.3.2	Speed reduction only of short duration	94
9.3.3	What message was conveyed by the fog information?	94
9.4	Discussion	96
10	Which warns better, a soft or hard warning transition?	97
10.1	Introduction	97
10.2	Method	98
10.2.1	Experimental design	98
10.2.2	Sample	98
10.2.3	Material	99
10.2.4	Procedure	102
10.3	Results	102
10.3.1	Data preparation	102
10.3.2	Do drivers react faster to a soft or hard warning transition?	103
10.3.3	Where did the drivers look during the warning?	103
10.4	Discussion	105
11	Final Discussion	108
	References	114

List of Figures

1.1	Crash Victims Germany 1950-2011	13
1.2	Fuzzy Warning Prototype	17
2.1	Blurred vision in periphery after Loschky et al. (2005)	20
2.2	Saliency model of attention according to Itti et al. (1998)	21
2.3	Signal Evaluation Environment after Werneke and Vollrath (2011)	27
3.1	Night vision via LED bar according to Mahlke et al. (2007)	31
3.2	Critical situations by Fricke (2009)	32
3.3	Chevrons and Light Emitting Diode (LED)s for speed reduction according to Laquai et al. (2010)	34
3.4	Two LED concepts for speed reduction according to Laquai et al. (2011)	35
3.5	LED matrix as pedestrian warning according to Kienast et al. (2008) and Henning et al. (2008)	35
3.6	Night vision by Head-Up Display and LED-Matrix according to Henning et al. (2008)	36
4.1	Test vehicles Opel Corsa and VW Passat	42
4.2	Light strip with lights	43
4.3	Occlusions in relation to ceiling distance	45
4.4	proportion of peripherally not visible signals	45
4.5	Visibility of light signals at windshield root	46
5.1	Test Track Braunschweig-Echte	51
5.2	Warning sequence	52
5.3	System function intuitively correctly recognized	54
5.4	Shorter speeding violations with LED warning	55
5.5	More speeding violations with LED warning	55
5.6	Driving speed schematic	56
5.7	Number of light and heavy speeding violations	56
5.8	Frequency of tailgating	56
5.9	Evaluations of the systems	57
6.1	Driving Simulator TU-Braunschweig	62
6.2	Dikablis Eye Tracking System	62
6.3	Schematic test track	63
6.4	Critical events	64
6.5	Collision warnings	64
6.6	Minimum distance to front vehicle	66
6.7	Reaction times to front vehicle	66
6.8	Cumulated gaze duration for warning	67
6.9	Number of views with warning	67
6.10	Views to inactive warnings	68
6.11	Evaluation of the warning	68
6.12	Acceptance of false alarms	68

7.1	SURT	73
7.2	Four warning systems	74
7.3	Response times to warnings	76
7.4	Response times under secondary task	76
7.5	Response times to warnings	76
7.6	Evaluation Systems	78
7.7	Acceptance of false alarms	78
8.1	Division of Field of View Dikablis	83
8.2	Pedestrian Events	83
8.3	Pre- and Main Warning	84
8.4	Number of glances pedestrians from the right	86
8.5	Gaze reaction time	86
8.6	Comprehensibility directional reference	87
8.7	Pedestrian Braking Progression	88
8.8	Reduced Speed	88
9.1	Fog information »Warn blinking« and »Bar«	93
9.2	Speed curve in fog	94
9.3	Brake pedal activity in fog	95
9.4	Fog speed curve (single)	95
10.1	Intersection schematic	99
10.2	Pre-Warning and Main Warning	100
10.3	Warning Activity Sequence	101
10.4	Average reaction time	103
10.5	Incorrect braking	104
10.6	Mistakenly stepped off the gas	104
10.7	Impact speed after warning transition	105
10.8	Gaze reaction time	105
10.9	Gaze Tracking Plot	106

List of abbreviations

ABS	Antilock Braking System
ACC	Adaptive Cruise Control
BAS	Brake Assistant
ESP	Electronic Stability Programm
FAS	Driving Assistance System
HUD	Head-Up Display
LED	Light Emitting Diode
MMI	Multimedia Interface
PKW	Passenger Car
RGB	Red, Green, Blue
SEE	Signal Evaluation Environment
SURT	Surrogate Reference Task
TH	Time Headway
TTC	Time To Collision
VP hours	Versuchspersonenstunden

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1 Introduction

In this thesis a new display for motor vehicles was investigated. In contrast to classical systems, this one was not designed to be perceived with the gaze focus, but via the visual periphery. It consisted of an one-dimensional bar of multicolored LEDs placed under the windshield. Due to the simplified representation, messages were not conveyed in the form of symbols and text, but via light bars. These bars could vary in size, color, position, brightness and animation. The concept promised to have various advantages over classical displays. In several studies the effect and the potential of the display to increase traffic safety were investigated. Based on the insights gained, an assessment is made as to whether the concept is suitable for use as a Driving Assistance System (FAS) in road traffic.

1.1 The need for progress in road safety

For many people, moving around in a vehicle is the epitome of mobility. Owning a car enables us to cover long distances in a short time and with little effort, thus granting us independence. Especially outside of cities, the possession of a car often goes hand in hand with reaching the age of maturity and is a sign of attaining the level of self-determined action. Not infrequently it is even a status symbol. The automobile has thus become an important part of many people's lives.

But cars are also an important support for the supply of food and goods for society. Industrialized countries are characterized by having extensive road networks that connect all important places of a civilization. They thus enable a smooth exchange of goods. The comfortable lifestyle in industrial countries like Germany would not be possible at all without road traffic.

However, these advantages of mobility and supply go hand in hand with the risk of being involved in a crash. The consequences of traffic crashes can be devastating due to high travel speeds. In 2011, 392 365 people were injured in German road traffic crashes and 4 009 people died in crashes (Statistisches Bundesamt, 2012b) (Figure 1.1). This means that in that year about 11 people per day died due to a car crash.

The situation is aggravated by the fact that traffic density on the roads is increasing year by year, because mobility in Germany has changed a great deal since its beginnings and more people than ever before own a car. Statistically speaking, in 2011, one in two inhabitants of Germany already had a Passenger Car (PKW) at their disposal (Statistisches Bundesamt, 2012b), whereas in 1953 there was only one vehicle for every 14th inhabitant (Statistisches Bundesamt, 2011a, 2012a). To reach one's destination unharmed is not only an understandable need of every road user, but according to surveys among German motorists it also influences buying behavior. The "vehicle safety/safety equipment" is given as a reason to buy in a survey by the General German Automobile Club by approx. 56 % of those questioned. Since 1995, this has consistently been the second most frequent naming directly after "Quality/Reliability" of the vehicle, which was cited by 71 % of the respondents (ADAC, 2011a). However, road safety is an important topic not only in Germany. In 2010, the European Commission set itself the goal of halving the number of crashes across Europe by 2020 (European Commission, 2010a). To achieve this goal, it is important to identify the most frequent causes of crashes and to take appropriate countermeasures. This is easier said than done.

Figure 1.1: Progress of crash victims in German road traffic from 1950-2011 divided into injured (black) and killed (grey) (Statistisches Bundesamt, 2012b).

The steady decline in the number of fatalities in Germany between 1991 and 2011 (Figure 1.1) shows that we have already brought many of the common sources of danger under control. The fact that this number rose last year for the first time in 20 years seems to confirm that it is becoming increasingly difficult to combat the remaining causes of crashes. When the automobile was introduced, the focus was on reducing flaws in the design of the vehicle. This development led to the fact that nowadays technical defects are rarely responsible for crashes. In 2010, only 0.7 % of crashes with personal injury in Germany were due to technical defects (Statistisches Bundesamt, 2011b). Besides the involvement of ice, rain, snow or impaired visibility in 17 % of the cases, driving errors were the main cause of crashes (Statistisches Bundesamt, 2011b). Today's crashes are thus largely caused by humans. In order to avoid as many crashes as possible, future measures should therefore start with the driver to eliminate him as a source of error.

1.2 Are autonomous vehicles the better drivers?

The reduction of human error as a cause of crashes can be achieved in principle in three ways: Either one supports the driver in the driving task, leaves parts of the driving task to the vehicle itself or hands over the driving task completely to the vehicle. Would this even be possible today? Vehicles are already technically capable of detecting driving errors. However, there are clear legal limits to the intervention of a system. The use of FAS in vehicles is regulated by the Vienna Convention on Road Traffic of 1968, among other things. There it says: "Every driver must be able to control his vehicle or lead his animals at all times." (Die Bundesbehörden der Schweizerischen Eidgenossenschaft, 1968, Art. 8, para. 5). Thus, a human being must have control over his vehicle at all times and may not give it completely to a machine. Exceptions are only permitted to reduce the consequences of a crash that can no longer be avoided.

Assessment of complete automation But suppose one could simply change the law and allow autonomous vehicles. Can cars already move safely in traffic on their own? Initial demonstrations by Google and the TU-Braunschweig show that autonomous vehicles are no longer science fiction (Buehler et al., 2008; Thrun, 2011). Despite optimism, however, a closer look at the examples makes it clear that these autonomous vehicles are not yet ready for the market. Even if the technical difficulties were already completely solved and autonomous vehicles could be launched on the market tomorrow, there would still be another hurdle to overcome: These vehicles would be very expensive due to their technical equipment and would therefore probably have only a weak impact on crash statistics due to low sales figures. Furthermore, it is questionable whether drivers even want to become passive passengers in their own vehicles. On the one hand, people certainly enjoy driving, and on the other hand, not everyone is likely to be comfortable with the idea of handing over control of their vehicle to a machine. A complete replacement of the driver is therefore not a realistic option, at least not yet.

Assessment of partial automation An alternative would be to relieve the driver by partial automation. In this case, certain driving tasks would be left to the vehicle, while the driver would have to be ready to take control again if necessary. This would be the case whenever a situation occurs for which the system is not designed or the system simply fails. The driver would thus change from an actor to a supervisor. However, this would create new problems, because people are not very good at staying alert when they are not involved in a task themselves.

In a simulator experiment of Niederée and Vollrath (2009) test drivers drove with an assistance system that automatically controlled the speed. However, the system failed after a certain period of time and the test drivers had to take over control themselves quickly in order not to drive too fast through a curve. It turned out that the test drivers who drove with a highly reliable system drove into the curve much faster than the test drivers with the less reliable system. The drivers with the reliable system apparently relied more on it and had difficulty regaining control in the emergency. The observed effect was stronger the more reliable the system was. This example shows that a semi-autonomous system can even facilitate driver errors. Therefore, driver errors, which are responsible for a large part of crashes today, cannot be effectively prevented by automation or partial automation at the moment.

Assessment of driver assistance While the first FAS such as the electric starter (1912), the automatic transmission (1940), the power steering (1952) or the brake booster (1955) were aimed at increasing driving comfort (ADAC, 2011b), later developed systems such as the Electronic Stability Program (ESP), the Antilock Braking System (ABS) or the Brake Assistant (BAS) were designed to improve safety by actively intervening in driving behavior. Current FAS systems are increasingly focusing on supporting the driver with warnings and information. This means that the driver remains constantly involved in the driving task and retains control of his vehicle. If the vehicle then foresees a crash based on sensor data but is not allowed to intervene itself, it can at least transmit all relevant information to the driver. In this way, the assistance system helps the driver to make the right decision.

The support of the driver through driver assistance is a proven method to effectively eliminate driver errors as a cause of crashes. Crash analyses can be used to determine common causes of crashes in road traffic and to calculate the safety gain from an FAS intervening there. It is assumed that 17.5 % of the serious crashes in Germany with personal injury could be prevented by distance-regulating assistance (Vollrath, Briest, Drewes, Schießl, & Becker, 2006). Lane keeping assistants could prevent 49 % of truck crashes caused by lane departure on highways (Gwehenberger, Schwertberger, & Daschner, 2006) and lane change assistants have the potential

to prevent 26 % of lane change crashes (Farmer, 2008).

The potential of crash prevention through FAS is therefore great and still seems to be the best option to increase road safety at the moment. It is therefore essential to improve the effectiveness of assistance systems in order to further reduce the number of road crash victims.

The Importance of Human-Machine Interaction A special role in the development of FAS is played by the interface of information transfer between the system and the driver. If well designed, it will cause the driver to react quickly and correctly. In this way, the human-machine interface of a FAS indirectly influences the severity of crashes. It is therefore necessary to further increase the effectiveness of existing warning systems and to look for new possibilities to improve the transmission of safety-critical information between the vehicle and the driver. In the design of an optimal human-machine interface, human perception and information processing are at the forefront, because the technology must be tailored to these. The safe design of our vehicles thus moves away from a purely technical problem to a psychological one. As a result, engineers are increasingly dependent on the expertise of psychologists in order to achieve smooth cooperation between the vehicle system and the human system.

The role of displays in driver assistance While human-machine interfaces can be realized via different modalities (visual, acoustic, haptic), visual interfaces of FAS play a special role. After all, seeing is of great importance for driving (Sivak, 1996). People perceive their environment predominantly through their eyes and can obtain a great deal of information in this way. One glance is often enough to perceive the location, size, shape, color, texture, speed and direction of movement of objects (Purves & Williams, 2004). In contrast to acoustic and haptic perception, this is even possible without loss of information through physical barriers such as glass or plexiglass. It is therefore not surprising that much of the information in the vehicle is conveyed via the visual channel in the form of displays. This applies to basic vehicle information such as speed, fuel level, engine speed and engine temperature, but also to navigation and consumer electronics such as radio, CD and Mp3 players. FAS such as parking aids and Adaptive Cruise Control (ACC) also use displays to communicate with the driver. Finally, emergency situations, such as low oil levels, are indicated by a flashing warning symbol. Visual displays thus represent an intensively used form of human-machine interface for informing and warning the driver in the vehicle.

Limits of current visual assistance However, all displays used in current vehicles have a disadvantage. While driving we use the information of these displays depending on the situation and interest. Our gaze alternates regularly between the road and the displays in the vehicle. This is problematic because we are driving almost blind for the duration of our averted vision. According to results from the USA, averted vision plays a role in 78 % of crashes and 65 % of near-crashes (Dingus et al., 2006). Drivers appear to be aware of this and on average do not take their eyes off the road for more than one second (Gellatly & Kleiss, 2000). Nevertheless, every time they look away from the road, drivers increase their chances of overlooking a critical event and becoming involved in a crash (Wierwille, 1995). Classic displays in the vehicle therefore have a dangerous side effect.

To counter this problem, the Head-Up Display (HUD) known from airplanes was adapted for motor vehicles. This is a display which is shown in the windshield close to the focus of the view. By mirroring this display, it can be presented in such a way that it is perceived further away than the location of the medium on which it is projected. This reduces the distance of the necessary gaze shift and the duration of the necessary accommodation of the lens of the human eye to see the newly fixed target sharply. However, the technology, which was originally developed for the support of pilots in air traffic and is successfully used there, can only be

transferred to the situation of a vehicle in road traffic to a limited extent (Gish & Staplin, 1995). Thus, displays of instruments in the aircraft are the primary source of information, while the view from the cockpit is secondary. In the vehicle this is reversed. While a HUD in an airplane can simply be superimposed over the view of the sky, the outside view is also very important in a vehicle, so that it should be occluded as little as possible (Gish & Staplin, 1995). Furthermore pilots are specifically trained to understand the symbolism of a HUD and to fly alone according to instruments. Drivers on the other hand do not receive special training in handling HUDs and must learn how to use them themselves. This is rarely done in a protected learning environment but rather directly in the field: for example by buying a new vehicle or driving a rental car. This is another difference between the use of HUDs in air and road traffic (Gish & Staplin, 1995). Unfortunately, today's displays cannot prevent the negative effects of the gaze aversion required for reading, although they can be reduced by using HUDs.

Unused potential: The peripheral field of vision If classical displays force averting glances from the street and HUDs solve this problem only rudimentarily, what alternatives are there? In everyday life the human body uses the peripheral field of vision to quickly recognize potentially relevant objects and especially hazards. It would therefore probably be advantageous to use these already existing mechanisms of human perception in a targeted way also in road traffic. An alternative to bringing the display closer to the fixation point in order to reduce averted vision from the road is to design a display in such a way that it can be perceived from the corner of the eye. However, design adjustments must be made here because peripheral vision differs considerably from central vision. The photoreceptors of human eyes, which are involved in peripheral perception, are not capable of providing sharp vision. However, they are very sensitive to movements and changes in the field of vision (Jonides, 1981; Lambert, Spencer, & Mohindra, 1987; Remington, Johnston, & Yantis, 1992). A display optimized for peripheral perception must be adapted to these special features. Due to the comparatively low visual resolution in the peripheral field of view, the display must not require sharp vision. This means that symbolic and textual information must be avoided. Instead, areas, colors and animations can be used to convey information. In addition, a display should be presented larger in order to be perceived despite limited visual acuity. These requirements result in a warning concept that uses the properties of peripheral visual perception to achieve a high warning effect with little distraction. In this thesis, such a concept was implemented and investigated in the form of a Fuzzy Warning.

1.3 The Fuzzy Warning

The term Fuzzy Warning can be derived in several ways. The term is derived from the warning message as well as from the way in which the display is perceived. In relation to the warning message, it stands for an unspecific warning, which is in principle very generic due to the limitation of the display to light bars. Thus it does not convey the cause of the warning as specifically as a classical symbolic warning. If it is related to visual perception, the term means that in normal use the display can only be seen blurred in the low-resolution peripheral field of view.

The display used in this work consisted of a LED bar, which was placed under the windshield in the vehicle (similar to Figure 1.2). It was positioned in such a way that it was visible in the peripheral field of vision during a normal view of the road and differed from classical warning systems in that it had a larger display area and did not display symbolic messages in the form of letters or signs. With the help of 128 three-color Red, Green, Blue (RGB) LEDs could display light bars that differ in size, color, brightness and animation.

Figure 1.2: A prototype of the Fuzzy Warning. Multi-colored LEDs under the windshield and on the A-pillars can inform or warn the driver. The use of the image is courtesy of Volkswagen AG.

Due to these characteristics, the Fuzzy Warning has the potential to have three advantages over classical FAS:

Less Gaze Aversions Using only symbol-free displays sounds like a restriction at first, but this can be an advantage. On a vehicle display, characters and symbols must be viewed directly in order to be read. A light bar, on the other hand, can also be seen from the corner of the eye. Due to the symbol-free display, there is no information in the case of the Fuzzy Warning, which can be obtained by looking directly at the display as opposed to looking out of the corner of the eye. This should result in drivers turning their gaze away from the road less often to look at the display.

Better reactions Due to its width from the left to the right A-pillar, the Fuzzy Warning used here has a larger area than displays shown in the combined display behind the steering wheel or similar displays in the center console or the HUD. It is known from basic research that larger stimuli can generally be responded to more quickly than smaller ones (Osaka, 1976). In addition, the LED bar of the Fuzzy Warning is located at the base of the windshield, close to the driver's usual visual focus when looking at the road. People usually respond more quickly to stimuli presented closer to the current viewing direction than to stimuli presented further away. In an experiment by Cohen (1987), drivers responded to lights presented in the windshield area during a car trip. The response to lights presented within a radius of 10° was about 700 ms faster than to lights presented within a radius of 30° or more. Due to its size and proximity to the visual focus, the Fuzzy Warning should therefore lead to faster reaction times in case of danger than classical displays. The advantage should be stronger over warnings in the combination display than over displays in the HUD, since the Fuzzy Warning has more favorable characteristics over the combination display in both size and proximity to the focus of view, and over the HUD in display size only.

Targeted gaze control The unusual width of the Fuzzy Warning still allows to present directed signals in the actual direction of danger. This is not possible due to the locally very limited space in a combi-, head-up or multimedia display. Classical displays can only

implement directional warnings in the form of directional symbols, such as an arrow. With the Fuzzy Warning it is possible to really display a warning of a head-on hazard at least horizontally where it is located relative to the driver. In principle, it is quite possible to direct the eye using light signals (Lambert et al., 1987; Remington et al., 1992; Irwin, Colcombe, Kramer, & Hahn, 2000). It is possible to react faster to stimuli that are displayed offset in the direction of the target than to a central cue that only points in the direction of the target (Remington, 1978). It remains to be seen whether this effect can also be demonstrated in the vehicle by means of assistance systems.

1.4 Goal of this thesis

In order to reduce the driver errors that are today mainly responsible for crashes, further developments in FAS are needed. A peripheral display represents an alternative to classical displays in the motor vehicle. The Fuzzy Warning as a prototypical implementation of a peripheral warning promises to have several advantages over classical displays. In the future, it could be used in vehicles to reduce dangerous averted glances from the road, accelerate reactions in critical situations and direct the driver's attention to safety-relevant areas.

If it were to meet these requirements, it would offer the potential to significantly increase road safety. In the context of this thesis, the system was therefore investigated in various aspects and application areas. Based on the knowledge gained, a final evaluation will be made at the end of the project as to whether the Fuzzy Warning is suitable as an indicator for FAS for use in road traffic.

1.5 Structure of this thesis

This work investigated the interaction between a new display and the driver. The characteristics of human visual processing form the conditions to which the display must be tailored. Therefore, the work starts with an overview of the mechanisms of human information processing that are relevant for the effect of the display (Chapter 2). Before selecting the research questions, it is also important to give an overview of the empirical findings on Fuzzy Warnings that have been made so far. Chapter 3 therefore presents the current state of research. Since there are only few studies on Fuzzy Warnings in automobiles so far, studies that have investigated systems similar to Fuzzy Warning are also considered. This is followed by an evaluation of the previous findings and a derivation of open questions. These are finally empirically investigated starting in Chapter 4 in the main part of this thesis.

The work thus represents a link between the findings of basic psychological research and their application in practice. The entire concept of the display is based on findings on human visual perception and information processing. Based on the models presented there, hypotheses about the effect of a Fuzzy Warning could be derived. By applying this knowledge to the design of a new display for road traffic, this work contributes to the examination of the extent to which these findings can be transferred to practice. Furthermore, it expands the psychological understanding of the warning concept of Fuzzy Warning, which in turn can be used in the design of further systems.

In this way, this work contributes to expanding knowledge in the field of peripheral warnings in the motor vehicle and to searching for possible applications for driver information and warning. A better understanding of the importance of peripheral perception for the driving task can in turn help to effectively use a previously neglected aspect of human perception in the design of FAS in road traffic and thus increase road safety.

2 Human visual processing

The operating principle of the Fuzzy Warning is based on fundamental findings and theories of visual perception and attention. Therefore, it is important to give a short overview of the corresponding basics of visual information processing at this point. Visual perception is influenced on the one hand by the biological conditions of the visual system and on the other hand by cognitive processing in the brain. Visual resolution is of great importance for the perception of potential hazards and warning signals. The higher the resolution, the more details from the environment can be perceived. A human eye already shows great differences in different areas of the field of vision. These are briefly described below (Section 2.1). The information received via the eye is further processed in the brain. In this way, the perception of individual aspects can be specifically enhanced or inhibited. These processes are described in Section 2.2. Peripheral perception is only one aspect of human vision. However, since the display examined in this work is designed for this area, the special features of peripheral vision are summarized in a separate section (Section 2.3).

In this thesis the evaluation of a specific display is in the foreground. Therefore, a detailed description of the basics of visual processing is omitted and instead the importance of these processes for the context of driver assistance is emphasized.

2.1 Human vision

Although we usually do not notice it, we perceive a large part of our field of vision only very roughly. To find out how much our visual acuity decreases towards the periphery, Loschky, McConkie, Yang, and Miller (2005) performed a clever experiment. In this experiment, they showed different photos to the subjects. While the subjects were looking at a photo, certain areas of the image were artificially blurred synchronously to their saccades, for the period of fixation. In each case, the current direction of gaze was taken into account and the blurring occurred only in the area of the image that lay in the peripheral field of vision. When the next saccade occurred, the original image was displayed again. Of five investigated blur levels, two were practically unnoticed (Figure 2.1).

So we can only see sharply in the area that is currently fixated. This is partly due to the anatomy of our eye and partly to the neural weighting of the visual information that is passed on to our brain. There are two types of photosensitive receptors in our eye: cones and rods. While cones are able to pick up color information and process incident light at a high resolution, rods only provide a coarsely resolved image of the environment, but are specialized in detecting subtle differences in brightness and movement. The rods still provide information even in very low light and thus enable us to see in darkness to a certain extent. This advantage is achieved, among other things, by a strong convergence of information from adjacent rods. The price for this, however, is a much worse visual resolution compared to the cones.

The place of sharpest vision is the fovea. It is a small, relatively central area of the retina that consists almost entirely of cones. Towards the periphery, the concentration of cones decreases sharply, while that of rods increases sharply (Curcio, Sloan, Kalina, & Hendrickson, 1990). In the human eye of an adult there are on average 4.6 million cones and 92 million rods (Curcio et al., 1990). This is 20 times as many rods as cones. The rods thus cover a large part of the entire retina. When we look directly at an object, the light reflected from it falls on the fovea,

Figure 2.1: Stimulus material from the experiment of Loschky et al. (2005). The blurring of the middle image compared to the left image was hardly noticed. The image is used with kind permission of Taylor & Francis online.

thus enabling a good, sharp perception of the object in color (foveal vision). However, this area of sharpest vision covers only about 2° of our field of view and at an eccentricity of 6° the visual acuity is already reduced by 75 % (Purves & Williams, 2004). Although the non-fixated environment is not perceived sharply, we are very sensitive to movement here and perception still works in low light (peripheral vision).

Our visual acuity is thus largely determined by the type of receptor (cones, rods) and the receptor density. However, there is another factor that plays a role: The number of neurons in our brain involved in processing (receptive fields). The size of the receptive fields of our photoreceptors increases from the periphery towards the fovea (Cowey & Rolls, 1974; Purves & Williams, 2004). Although the fovea represents only a relatively small part of the retina, a large number of nerve cells from the primary visual cortex are involved in the processing of foveal signals. The relatively small area of the fovea is therefore cortically overrepresented. Due to this neural weighting, the information of the fovea is processed more intensively and thus the perception in these areas is further improved.

2.2 Visual attention

However, how well we can perceive a visual stimulus does not only depend on physiological factors. In addition to the number, type and density of photoreceptors and the number of brain cells involved in the processing of visual signals, we have the ability to pay attention to various objects in our environment in order to perceive them better (Posner, Snyder, & Davidson, 1980; Reynolds & Chelazzi, 2004). The price for this is that other, unnoticed stimuli are simultaneously neglected (Posner et al., 1980; Reynolds & Chelazzi, 2004). This effect has been extensively investigated in studies in general psychology. In an experiment by Posner, Nissen, and Ogden (1978) subjects had to respond to a stimulus that could appear either to the left or right of a fixation cross. The subjects were also assisted by a cue that indicated

the position of the target stimulus. In this way, the subjects were informed in advance of the position of the target stimulus. However, the reliability of the cue was varied. It was found that subjects responded 60 ms faster on average with a reliable cue that indicated the correct direction in 80 % of cases than with a cue that was correct in only 20 % of cases.

The process of focusing on a feature to improve its perception is called attention. It is not even necessary to really focus the gaze on an object, because attention can also improve peripheral perception (Posner, 1980). Furthermore, attention is not limited to seeing. Thus, through targeted concentration, the perception of auditory (Moray, 1959) or tactile (Evans & Craig, 1991) stimuli can also be enhanced.

Attention can be directed consciously or unconsciously. Many have certainly experienced it themselves. A flashing light or a fast moving object in the peripheral field of vision has attracted attention without any explicit intention to do so. Perhaps by means of an advertisement that catches your eye while driving through the streets at night or an animated banner that distracts you while surfing the Internet. When our attention is directed towards an object against our will, we speak of distraction. In fact, this is a well-studied effect in attention research. Regardless of the stimulus dimension, foveal attention is automatically directed to salient stimuli without us being able to prevent it (Theeuwes, 1991, 1992; McCormick, 1997). We can only speculate about the reason for this effect. But it is certainly plausible that this ability is useful for survival when it comes to reacting to a rapidly approaching danger. If we better understand the laws of attention, we can use it to improve FAS. For this reason, the most important findings are presented below.

2.2.1 How exactly does attention work?

Nowadays it is assumed that four processes are involved in the phenomenon of attention: Working memory, top down control, bottom up salience filter and a competitive selection (Knudsen, 2007). These will be briefly explained using the example of visual attention, which has been the best studied so far.

Figure 2.2: Attentional model according to Itti et al. (1998). In cognitive processing, the visual scene is divided into individual maps on the basis of various characteristics (left). For each of these maps a normalization process takes place, which reinforces features that deviate relatively from the general activation (right). The use of the image is courtesy of IEEE.org – © 1998 IEEE.

Working memory At the center is the working memory, which represents the content of the things one deals with at any given moment (LaBar, Gitelman, Parrish, & Mesulam, 1999). Only what enters the working memory is processed more intensively by the human brain. However, its capacity is limited (Baddeley, 2003). In this way it forms a natural resource for attention.

Bottom up Salienzfilter How this resource is distributed depends on the nature of the environmental stimuli. Basically, this is the process of selecting stimuli that differ strongly in one characteristic from the environment. These can be flashes of light, movements, objects with a certain color or shape or any other feature. It can be imagined as if an internal representation of each characteristic (shape, color, movement) is created in the form of maps of the visual scene (Itti & Koch, 2001). For each location on the map there is an activation level for each feature. If a feature has an unusual activation level, it is salient and is taken into account (Figure 2.2). It is the size of the relative differences to the environment that counts, not a simple high or low activation (Itti & Koch, 2000).

Top Down Control However, the decision as to which of the environmental stimuli reach the working memory is not made solely by the nature of the stimulus. Internal processes such as experience and current goals influence the weighting of the incoming information. Thereby, characteristics of high importance are specifically strengthened in processing and characteristics of low importance are inhibited (E. K. Miller & Cohen, 2001).

Competitive Selection At any given time the visual scene is thus represented in parallel on different feature maps. If several conspicuous stimuli occur at the same time, the strongest stimulus is selected and this location is considered; this process is called competitive selection (Desimone & Duncan, 1995). The sequence of these four processes will be explained using an example:

When we look at the road in front of us during a night drive, the visual scene is predominantly gray and colorless. A feature map of the visible scene of the color white would therefore have little activation. The color red would have practically no activation.

Bottom up Salience Filter If an oncoming vehicle now lights us up with its headlights, the white feature map at the location of the headlights shows a very high level of activation, which is very different from the rest of the scene. We would pay attention to the light. An animal at the side of the road could be overlooked in this way because it stands out only slightly from the surroundings. However, if an assistance system activates to warn us about the animal and a red warning is displayed, the red feature map will show a high level of activation at that location, which is very different from the activity in the rest of the scene.

Competitive Selection It is quite conceivable that the red warning stands out more than the white light because there are different shades of grey in the scene, but hardly any shades of red. It also differs by novelty, since it has just appeared. The place that makes the biggest difference attracts our attention – in this case the position of the red warning.

Top Down Control The warning is known to us and we associate it with a possible source of danger outside the vehicle. We now begin to search for the cause and selectively ignore both the white headlights and the red warning. In doing so, the processing of the red and white feature map at the location of the warning and the headlights is inhibited and that at the dark edge of the road is intensified.

Working memory Our perception around the edge of the road is improved and we see an animal that might run on to the road in front of us.

In summary, the result is a very flexible attention system that can adapt its processing method according to the task requirements. However, there remains a limitation of attention capacity: if it is used more in one area, it must be taken away elsewhere. Furthermore, attention is not given, but is a constant process which can be directed in a certain direction by stimuli from the environment and our intentions.

2.2.2 Location and object-related attention

Up to now, only location-based attention has been described. Salient stimuli or conscious interest lead us to focus on a place in our field of vision and improve our perception at that location. This is done either with or without turning our gaze. Attention can thus be seen as a kind of spotlight that is deliberately or involuntarily directed at specific stimuli (Posner et al., 1980). However, this metaphor is not perfect. It has been shown that perception can also be improved on the basis of objects (Duncan, 1984).

In a well-known video one is asked to observe a group of students playing ball and to count the rallies between the team with white t-shirts while at the same time a team with black t-shirts is shown (Chabris & Simons, 1999). Before reading on, I recommend to try this effect yourself on the Internet <http://www.theinvisiblegorilla.com/videos.html>.

Most people succeed quite well. What few people notice, is that during the ball game a black gorilla runs centrally through the picture and looks into the camera. If attention were only localized, we would have to perceive the gorilla, but since we selectively focus on the color white, other stimuli that occur in the same place are ignored.

The contradiction between references to location-based and object-based attention led to the rejection of the spotlight metaphor and the search for a more general theory that could also explain object-based attention. Eventually, it was concluded that attention is feature-based and that the location of any stimulus, along with color, motion and orientation, is only one feature among many on which we can focus (Treue & Trujillo, 1999; Maunsell & Treue, 2006).

2.2.3 How to direct attention?

Now that the basics of attention are known, some Factors that influence attention alignment are presented.

Uniqueness As mentioned above, the visibility of a stimulus does not depend on its features, but on its features relative to its environment. The more intensely a stimulus differs from its environment in one characteristic and the fewer other stimuli there are that differ strongly from the environment in another characteristic, the faster this stimulus can be found by us or even attract our attention (Theeuwes, 1992). If a target stimulus differs strongly from the environment in one characteristic, it is irrelevant for the search duration how many other stimuli are located in the visual scene. The target stimulus is always found equally quickly. This indicates a parallel search process (Treisman & Gelade, 1980). If there are stimuli in the environment that are similar to the target stimulus in one dimension but not identical to it, two or more characteristics must be used for identification. In this case, the search duration increases with the number of similar distractor stimuli, indicating a serial search (Treisman & Gelade, 1980). In order for a target stimulus to be perceived well and quickly, it must therefore be clearly distinguishable from its surroundings in a single characteristic.

Abrupt change We react particularly strongly to sudden appearance (Jonides, 1981; Lambert et al., 1987; Remington et al., 1992) or disappearance (J. Miller, 1989) of stimuli. Usually an orientation reaction is then carried out by turning our gaze in the corresponding direction (Irwin et al., 2000). However, by directing attention to another feature, this automatic reaction can be strongly suppressed so that abrupt changes in another feature do not distract (Folk, Remington, & Wright, 1994). However, this applies primarily to stimuli presented in the central field of vision. A reaction to peripheral stimuli is more difficult to suppress (Jonides, 1981). An abrupt change is therefore a good means of directing attention. It is particularly effective when used in the peripheral visual field.

Novelty Another factor that influences visibility is the familiarity of a stimulus. New stimuli are more salient and are found faster than known stimuli. For example, an upside down letter is found more quickly under upright stimuli than an upside down letter under upside down stimuli (Reicher, Snyder, & Richards, 1976; Richards & Reicher, 1978). The more familiar a new stimulus is, the weaker the reaction to it becomes (Li, Miller, & Desimone, 1993). New stimuli therefore also attract attention. However, this effect decreases the longer a person is exposed to a stimulus.

Perception gap In connection with the theory of location-based attention, an interesting discovery has been made: When a target stimulus is presented at the same location shortly after a distracting stimulus, the perception of the target stimulus is impaired at a duration of less than 0.5 s (Welford, 1952). This effect is stronger the shorter the interval between the two presentations. It became known as the psychological refractory period. A place that has just been observed cannot therefore be observed again immediately. If you want to direct attention, you should avoid presenting the target stimulus where another change took place shortly before.

Conclusion on visual attention All in all, the following instructions result from basic research: If one wants to make a stimulus as visible as possible in order to influence the behavior of a person, the stimulus should be of such a nature that it is new (Reicher et al., 1976; Richards & Reicher, 1978), suddenly appears or disappears (Jonides, 1981; Lambert et al., 1987; Remington et al., 1992; J. Miller, 1989) and differs strongly from the environment in one characteristic (Theeuwes, 1992). It should not be presented in a place where another salient stimulus was visible before 0.5 s (Welford, 1952) and it should be presented rarely (Li et al., 1993).

2.3 Peripheral perception

In this thesis, a new type of display is investigated, the Fuzzy Warning, which is to be perceived mainly peripherally. This is the core feature in which it differs from previous display concepts. For this process to work, the special characteristics of peripheral vision must be taken into account when designing the display. These are summarized in the following. Due to the scope of knowledge in this field, it is not possible to give an exhaustive description in the context of this thesis. Instead, selected findings relevant to the work are reported. A more detailed description can be found at Yu (2010).

An important aspect for the design of a peripheral warning system in a vehicle is the human color perception in the periphery. While symbolic displays should have a high contrast to increase readability, a symbol-free warning must use other dimensions to convey messages. Together with size, brightness and animation, the color design of the display offers many possibilities to inform and warn drivers without symbols. In the following, the effectiveness and design of these different aspects for peripheral perception in the vehicle will be discussed.

Strictly speaking it must be noted that the effect of these different aspects on peripheral perception is not constant. In fact, it changes according to the driving experience and current stress. For this reason, these relationships will also be briefly discussed. In addition, the paper describes the role peripheral vision already plays for driving today, even without Fuzzy Warnings, and how drivers usually see their environment.

Since the size of a stimulus on the retina changes with distance to the eye, the distance and size of visual stimuli are often given in angles that refer to the visible area in the eye. For example, eccentricity describes how far a stimulus lies in the periphery. It indicates the angular distance of the stimulus from the area fixed with the fovea. Similarly, the size of a stimulus can be given in the angular range it covers if two straight lines are drawn from the upper and lower ends to the eye of the observer so that they intersect in the lens. This range is called the angle of vision.

In the following, periphery is understood to be the area on the retina outside the fovea. This begins at an eccentricity of approximately 3° from the fixation point (Purves & Williams, 2004). This means that everything that is visible to us, but is not being looked at directly, belongs to the periphery. The LED-bar used in this work was mounted at the root of the windshield and is thus located about 4° away from the foveal viewpoint when looking at the road (Lamble, Laakso, & Summala, 1999). This means that in a normal driving situation the LED bar is located in the peripheral field of view.

Color vision in the peripheral field of view As already mentioned in section 2.1, perception in the peripheral visual field has only low spatial resolution. Another special feature is the visibility of colors in the periphery. While we can perceive all colors of a wavelength of about 400 nm (blue) to 700 nm (red) in the fovea, the visibility of the different colors decreases unevenly towards the periphery (Woodson & Conover, 1964). Sorting the colors according to the proportion of their visibility in the entire field of view results in the following order (Table 2.1):

Rank	Color	Nasal	Temporal	Total
1	White	60°	90°	150°
2	Blue	33°	65°	98°
3	Yellow	25°	50°	75°
4	Red	15°	50°	65°
5	Green	10°	50°	60°

Table 2.1: Visibility distribution of colors in the visual field of the human eye. Created from the data of Woodson and Conover (1964). It indicates the area in which a color can be seen, relative to the fovea, in the direction of the nose (nasal) or temple (temporal).

While the colors white and blue can still be perceived very far in the periphery, the colors red and green are only visible in a small area around the fovea. Sivak, Flannagan, Miyokawa, and Traube (1999) have especially investigated the colors red and yellow, which are relevant for traffic, with regard to their perceptibility in the periphery. While in darkness all stimuli in the range of $0-30^\circ$ from the fixation point could be perceived well, both colors were perceived less well in daylight conditions (Sivak et al., 1999). As expected from the results of Woodson and Conover (1964), this effect was more intense for the red stimuli than for the yellow (Sivak et al., 1999).

It is worth mentioning for this work that when looking straight ahead at the road, all colors can still be recognized in the area under the windshield. The smallest field of view of the color green goes up to an eccentricity of 10° temporal and 50° nasal (Woodson & Conover, 1964).

As already mentioned above, the position at the root of the windshield is approximately at an eccentricity of 4° and thus still falls within this range. This means that for the position of the Fuzzy Warning used in this thesis there are no restrictions in color perception, although the display is located in the periphery. In principle, however, peripheral light stimuli should be white or blue so that they are also clearly visible in the outer periphery.

Influence of color, shape, blinking and size From basic research we know how stimuli must be designed to attract attention (see chapter 2.2.3). But what does this mean for the design of a real assistance system? Can the findings be directly transferred to the application case or are there circumstances that need to be taken into account? How must a peripheral warning in a typical driving situation be designed so that it can be reacted to quickly? These questions have been addressed by Werneke and Vollrath (2011). In order to investigate peripheral stimuli in a standardized way in a paradigm adapted to the automotive context, they developed the Signal Evaluation Environment (SEE). In this experimental setup, the scenario of a right turn from a side street to a main road is simulated in a very abstract way. A typical driving error in the equivalent real-world situation is that drivers overlook right-of-way traffic participants when turning (Summala, Pasanen, Räsänen, & Sievänen, 1996). This seems to be mainly due to the fact that drivers regularly focus their attention on the vehicles crossing to their left and overlook a potential cyclist crossing from the right (Räsänen & Summala, 1998). It is precisely this aspect of the distribution of attention that is simulated by the SEE (Werneke & Vollrath, 2011). Subjects must primarily pay attention to stimuli presented directly in front of (Figure 2.3, A-1) and to the left of them (Figure 2.3, A-2), but occasionally also react to a secondary stimulus presented in the peripheral visual field to the lower right in front of them (Figure 2.3, A-3). The reaction time to the secondary stimulus was measured. Werneke and Vollrath (2011) have examined various peripheral stimuli that differ in color, shape and size (Figure 2.3, B). In general, the subjects responded more quickly to larger stimuli. Furthermore, a difference between the examined colors was found, but only for small stimulus sizes of 1° angle of vision, not for 5° angle of vision. Here, the response to gray and red stimuli was slower than to blue, green and white. It turned out that the shape had no influence on the reaction time and no differences were found by mere appearance or different blinking frequencies (Werneke & Vollrath, 2011).

Movement perception in the periphery One aspect that was not investigated in the work of Werneke and Vollrath (2011) was peripheral motion perception. Basically we perceive motion in the periphery if it exceeds a distance of $0.15^\circ/s$ (Summala, Lamble, & Laakso, 1998; Lamble et al., 1999). But the visual perception of movement is not evenly distributed over the field of view.

Lamble et al. (1999) examined how quickly subjects noticed the slowing of a vehicle in front, depending on how strongly they looked away from the road. They found that the change in speed with increasing eccentricity was noticed later. Lappin, Tadin, Nyquist, and Corn (2009) studied the visual perception limits for different speeds of movement in connection with eccentricity over the entire field of view. They were able to show that at low speeds of less than $0.5^\circ/s$ faster responses were made to centrally presented stimuli. With fast movements of over $0.5^\circ/s$, stimuli in the periphery were detected earlier. In addition, Fahle and Wehrhahn (1991) found that movements in the temporal periphery, i.e. the outward-facing side of our field of view, were detected somewhat better than in the nasal periphery. Furthermore, movements in the periphery that were directed outwards were better detected than those directed inwards (Fahle and Wehrhahn (1991)).

In general, peripheral vision seems to work better in the lower field of view than in the upper (He, Cavanagh, & Intriligator, 1996). Furthermore, humans can adapt to moving visual stimuli

Figure 2.3: The SEE used by Werneke and Vollrath (2011) (A) represents the view from a vehicle cockpit (dark area) onto the road (light area) in a highly simplified way. Drivers have to pay attention to stimuli at different positions at the same time (1, 2), just like when turning at an intersection. To determine the optimal warning signal for such a situation, the reaction time to additional stimuli presented in the dark area was measured (3). The stimulus size, color, shape and blinking frequency of the examined peripheral stimuli were varied (B). The figure shows the structure of the task schematically.

particularly quickly if they are located further out in the periphery (70° eccentricity) and move slowly (0.05 revolutions per second) (Hunzelmann & Spillmann, 1984).

Taken together, these findings suggest that a peripheral warning at the base of the windshield is well placed in the lower visual field. If the display were animated here, even slow movements would be clearly visible.

Limitations of the peripheral vision In addition to the basic ability to perceive color, shapes and movement in the periphery, peripheral vision is also influenced by psychological factors such as driving experience. Experienced drivers make more use of peripheral vision than novice drivers by using a wider area in the periphery while driving (Mourant & Rockwell, 1972). And this behavior seems to have a direct impact on the quality of perception: Crundall, Underwood, and Chapman (2002) has shown that experienced drivers perceive peripheral visual stimuli better than novice drivers. This was true for critical and non-critical situations.

Another factor that can impair peripheral vision is the current stress level of the subjects. Crundall et al. (2002) showed subjects a video recording of a car journey from the driver's perspective and gave them the task to pay attention to potentially dangerous situations and react to them by pressing the pedal. At the same time, stimuli in the peripheral field of view were presented to the participants, to which they had to react with a mouse click. They varied the temporal distance to critical events. It was found that the subjects reacted to the peripheral stimuli worse, the shorter the duration to a critical event. The detection rate was lowest shortly before the critical event (approx. 1 s). Here, a peripheral visual stimulus was perceived five times worse than 4 s before or after the critical event (Crundall et al., 2002).

In a similar experiment by Chapman and Underwood (1998), the eye movements of subjects in critical and non-critical traffic situations were recorded. Here, too, it was shown that the horizontal and vertical field of view of drivers in a dangerous situation was reduced and individual objects were fixated for longer. When we have to react to a critical situation in road traffic, our field of view narrows and we perceive peripheral stimuli less well.

These findings suggest that experienced drivers should benefit more from a Fuzzy Warning than novice drivers. In addition, it is expected that the perception of the Fuzzy Warning is

reduced if it is presented simultaneously with a critical event. However, this also applies to state of the art symbolic warnings when they are in a critical situation, especially in the driver's peripheral field of view. To avoid this limitation, displays which are in the driver's peripheral field of view at the time of a critical event should either be presented early (>1.5 s) before the critical situation occurs or be particularly salient.

Relevance of peripheral vision for driving When we look at the road while driving, it is obvious that we use our foveal vision in a targeted manner to sharply perceive the objects of the driving situation and environment that are important to us. But what role does our peripheral perception play at this moment? As we have already learned, we see only blurredly in the corner of our eye, but are sensitive to movements and salient stimuli that differ strongly from the background in one feature. This leads us to focus our attention on potentially relevant stimuli by means of peripheral vision. But peripheral vision has another important function when driving a car: When drivers divert their attention from the road for a moment, they use the peripheral visual field to keep in lane (Summala, 1998). Especially experienced drivers with more than 100 000 km of total driving experience can cover a longer distance with their eyes turned away without leaving the lane than novice drivers with only 10 000 km of total driving experience (Summala, 1998).

However, driving performance deteriorates with increasing distance from the foveal visual range when the driving task is performed by peripheral vision only (Summala, Nieminen, & Punto, 1996; Summala, 1998). Thus, peripheral vision plays an important role especially when looking away from the road, namely for lane keeping. In addition, it is also used more intensively with increasing driving experience. But even if peripheral vision supports lane keeping, direct vision is still superior when it comes to hazard recognition. If a vehicle, suddenly braking in front, is only seen out of the corner of the eye, reactions to it are slower with increasing eccentricity (Summala et al., 1998; Lambale et al., 1999). Foveal vision has a clear advantage over peripheral vision due to its much higher spatial resolution.

Peripheral vision for secondary tasks Even in uncritical situations, we find it easier to drive the vehicle if we can see the road ahead of us directly. Zschoernack, Göbel, Treugut, and Yoo (2010) were able to show that in a simulator drive, the further away from the direct line of sight to the road a simultaneously executed reading task was, the more impaired the lane keeping was. Horrey and Wickens (2004) specifically compared two typical display positions in a similar task and found that drivers showed greater lane keeping variance when the information was presented on a head-down display than when presented on a head-up display in the windshield. To see the Head-Down Display, drivers had to look away from the road.

So if we look away from the road because of a secondary task, be it looking at the speedometer, radio or a map, our vehicle control and reaction time to potential hazards is impaired. And the further we look away from the road, the more severely. It is therefore all the more important to ensure that activities performed while driving distract our attention from the road as little as possible. It may be that a vehicle can be kept on track even for a short time out of the corner of our eyes, but if a critical event occurs exactly at the moment we avert our eyes, we are severely restricted in our ability to react.

Gaze behavior in the vehicle Where does a driver normally look while driving? Besides the advantages and disadvantages of peripheral and central vision, the driver's gaze behavior is also relevant for the optimal presentation of driver information.

To perceive their environment as comprehensively as possible, drivers fixate on about three targets per second under natural conditions (Mourant & Rockwell, 1970). Normally, drivers fixate on their own lane, vehicles and traffic signs, but occasionally they also look into the

vehicle. The drivers themselves seem to have an intuitive understanding of the danger associated with a prolonged absence of vision from the road. For when they perform a secondary task, regardless of the complexity of the task, they turn their gaze away from the road for only about 1 s on average (Gellatly & Kleiss, 2000). To accomplish a challenging side task, they increase the frequency of looking at the road for the side task instead of the time it takes to look away from the road (Gellatly & Kleiss, 2000). However, this also increases the total duration of the interaction and does not prevent a negative effect of distraction from the side task. Despite frequent changes of gaze, the risk of accidents increases with more demanding secondary tasks (Wierwille & Tijerina, 1998).

Conclusion on peripheral perception What significance do the special characteristics of peripheral perception have for the design of a display? In summary, it can be said that peripheral perception is already used today while driving, especially when the gaze is turned away from the road (Summala, 1998). Experienced drivers use their peripheral vision more effectively than novice drivers (Summala, 1998). Depending on how far a signal is presented in the periphery, the color scheme plays a role in visibility (Woodson & Conover, 1964). White and blue signals are best perceived (Woodson & Conover, 1964). In addition, stimulus size and direction of movement of peripheral stimuli have an influence on reaction times. Large stimuli are perceived better than small ones (Werneke & Vollrath, 2011) and there is an uneven distribution of motion perception in our visual field (Fahle & Wehrhahn, 1991). We already perceive very slow movements out of the corner of our eye, but respond better to fast movements (Summala et al., 1998; Lamballe et al., 1999). In a critical situation our field of view narrows and peripheral stimuli are perceived less well (Crundall et al., 2002).

3 Previous findings on Fuzzy Warning

After having described the biological basis of vision, visual attention and core features of peripheral perception, an overview of previous empirical findings on concrete implementations of peripheral warning systems will be given. In this work, peripheral warning means basically any warning concept that is designed to be perceived from the visual periphery. Although the concept is still quite new, there are already some approaches to its implementation. Since there are only a few studies dealing with peripheral warnings in the vehicle so far, similar concepts that do not represent a peripheral warning in the strict sense will be included here.

3.1 Peripheral Night Vision

The first concept of a peripheral warning in the form of a LED bar was presented by Mahlke, Rösler, Seifert, Krems, and Thüring (2007) in a comparison of six different night vision systems. Five of the displays consisted of displays placed directly behind the steering wheel (head-down) or above the steering wheel on the windshield (head-up) (Figure 3.1, right). The sixth display consisted of a LED bar placed at the base of the screen in the area behind the steering wheel (Figure 3.1, left). In real-life nighttime tests, the effectiveness of the displays in helping drivers to recognize pedestrians at the side of the road was investigated. The number of correct identifications, the detection time and distance were evaluated. In addition, subjective stress and gaze behavior were measured.

The display-based systems showed a simple video image of the night scene in front of the vehicle, generated by near or far infrared sensors. The LED bar indicated the direction of pedestrians in the form of a narrow yellow light bar. It was very similar to the LED bar used in this work, except for size and color. In total, two systems used near infrared sensors and four used far infrared sensors. The LED bar belonged to the group of systems based on far infrared. Both one of the displays and the LED bar worked with automatic pedestrian detection. In the case of the display, the pedestrians were highlighted by a box frame. In the case of the LED-bar, this was necessary to determine the direction of the potential danger. The other four systems had no highlighting and only displayed the night vision video image.

Of all systems examined, the pedestrian detection rate for the LED bar was closest to the control condition without display. In the detection distance, the two near-infrared systems and the LED bar were the only systems above the detection distance of the control condition. However, none of these differences became significant. On the other hand, pedestrians were detected 3.5 s earlier with the LED bar or a mirrored HUD bar than with three other systems. Mental stress was measured with the NASA-TLX questionnaire. It was found that only two systems did not differ significantly from the control condition: the near-infrared head-down display and the LED bar. These two systems were subjectively found to be the least stressful. Furthermore, eye movements during the ride were recorded. It turned out that the LED bar was fixated significantly less often (6 %) than the systems based on video images (11 %-18 %).

In the study of Mahlke et al. (2007) it could not be shown that any of the systems supported the drivers significantly compared to the control condition. However, when looking at the differences between the systems, it is noticeable that the LED bar contributed to the highest detection rates and the shortest detection times. The subjectively perceived distraction is very small. But it stands out from the other displays in particular in that the drivers have

Figure 3.1: Two of the displays used in the experiment of Mahlke et al. (2007). The LED bar (left) and an exemplary display (right). The illustration is used with the kind permission of Sage Journals.

only turned their eyes away from the road half as often, despite the tendency towards better support.

The results indicate an advantage of the LED bar compared to display-based assistance systems. In particular, the observed low level of gaze aversion from the road supports the hypothesis that the LED bar is perceived peripherally due to its symbol-free presentation.

3.2 Peripheral Collision Warning

The effect of a LED strip as an assistance system for hazard warning has also already been investigated in a collision scenario. Fricke (2009) dealt with semantically enriched warnings in her work. By this she means warnings that not only indicate the presence of a danger but also provide additional information about other features. In the case of the LED bar, the warning provided early information about an approaching cyclist or a suddenly braking vehicle in front (Figure 3.2). In addition, the direction of the danger was communicated via the position of the light signal on the bar. This is therefore a directional warning, as in the previously described experiment of Mahlke et al. (2007). Three independent variables were examined: LED warning (with/without), the type of auditory warning (auditory icon/sound) and the sequence of the scenario (car->bicycle/bicycle->car). Therefore, there was a warning sound in the condition with and without the LED bar. A control condition without warning was not examined. The reaction time to the hazard, the minimum distance to the hazard object and the number of collisions were measured.

The warnings were triggered in the bicycle situation at a Time To Collision (TTC) of 3-4 s. A special feature of the study was that the warning occurred 1 s before the cyclist became visible. The system thus had information about the position of an occluded road user and indicated this early on in the form of a moving light. Although this is a very desirable requirement, it is unfortunately not yet practically feasible at the moment. In the future, it could be achieved via real-time communication systems that connect different road users. The warning of the suddenly braking front vehicle was given at the time of braking. The brake lights of the vehicle did not work in this situation. The drivers were therefore able to orientate themselves exclusively on the distance to the front vehicle and the warning. Both scenarios showed a significant advantage for warnings with LED bar and sound compared to warnings with sound only. The reaction time with bar to the cyclist was on average 135 ms and to the braking vehicle 371 ms faster than without bar. In the bicycle scenario, the minimum distance to the dangerous object with bar was on average 148 cm greater than without bar. The warning combination

Figure 3.2: Fricke (2009) used two critical situations. A suddenly appearing cyclist (left). A suddenly braking vehicle (right). The illustrations are used with the kind permission of Nicola Fricke.

LED-bar and warning sound thus accelerated the reaction of the riders to a warning with warning sound only and shortened the braking distance.

3.3 Multimodal Warning Kit

Maier, Hellbrück, Sacher, Meurle, and Widmann (2011) presented the most advanced approach to integrate a LED strip into a warning system. In their paper, the authors present a modular warning system with several warning modalities that are combined depending on the hazardous situation to provoke the most effective driver reaction. In four studies multimodal warning concepts were investigated. A visually peripheral warning element, which is very similar to the system used in this work, was implemented by a red LED bar at the windshield root. Maier et al. (2011) investigated the effectiveness of the system in terms of reaction times by presenting it either alone or combined with a brake jerk or warning sound.

In the first study the Vehicle-in-the-loop paradigm was used (Bock, Maurer, & Färber, 2007). Here, the subjects drove in a virtual reality, which was communicated via a closed head-mounted display, but were simultaneously in a real vehicle. Thus, any desired test conditions could be created without danger and yet a realistic haptic driving experience could be maintained. Among the unimodal warnings, the fastest response was to a brake jerk. The subjects reacted second fastest to the warning via LED bar or warning tone. There was no significant difference between the two conditions. The response to a LED bar or a warning tone was significantly faster than to a warning displayed on the windshield (Maier, Sacher, & Hellbrück, 2010). However, drivers responded most quickly to a multimodal warning. Here, the LED bar even showed a slight advantage of 93 ms over the warning tone with brake jerk when combined with a brake jerk. The peripheral warning stood out in this study in that, although it did not produce the best reaction times, it was just as good as a classic system (warning tone) or even better (fade-in in windshield).

In the second study, Maier et al. (2011) was able to replicate the results of the first study in a rear-end collision scenario with a dummy trailer. The subjects were distracted in this experiment to increase the element of surprise.

While in the previous studies only aggressive warning elements were used, which warned only very shortly before a critical situation to elicit a maximum reaction, in the third study an early warning in the form of a dim red LED bar was introduced (Maier et al., 2011). The purpose of this was to prepare drivers for a possible impending intervention. In addition,

this study also investigated false triggers of this pre-warning. The main warnings were again a warning tone and a peripheral warning via LED-bar. The drivers were confronted with different dangerous situations one after the other. The results show an advantage of the directed LED warning compared to the warning tone of 457 ms under unimodal conditions, while the undirected peripheral pre-warning did not differ significantly from the warning tone. Drivers responded to the less reliable early warning more more hesitantly than to the main warning, but the early presentation gave them more time to react. In the last study, the already known peripheral warning concepts LED bar and warning tone were again examined in different dangerous situations. In addition, these concepts were compared with a classical warning consisting of a display in the instrument cluster behind the steering wheel accompanied by the familiar warning tone. Basically Maier et al. (2011) were able to replicate the results from the previous studies. However, there was no significant difference between the LED bar and the classic combi display, but there was a tendency towards an advantage of the LED bar of 141 ms.

In summary, Maier et al. (2011) similar to Mahlke et al. (2007) could demonstrate an equally good effect of the LED bar with a tendency towards an advantage compared to other warning systems. This means that the LED bar always warned at least as effectively as a traditional display. If one now takes into account that the LED bar attracts less attention than video-based displays (Mahlke et al., 2007), an advantage of the LED bar can arise despite the equally good response time. However, the transferability of the results from the night vision scenario with video-based displays to daytime driving with symbolic displays still has to be proven.

Maier et al. (2011) also mention that at the moment, confusion about the reason for warning can arise for the driver due to the non-uniform use of warning signals. For example, a warning tone is certainly used to warn of a collision, but also to inform the driver that the windshield wiper fluid or tank is low. A separation of the display concepts from informative and warning systems seems to make sense here. The LED bar could fulfill this function with the same warning performance (Maier et al., 2011).

3.4 Design of a peripheral display

Laquai, Rigoll, Duschl, Popiv, and Rakic (2010) have investigated new display concepts for warnings in a study. They concentrated on using displays with as large an area as possible, since classic displays are usually only moderately visible due to the small display size. They decided to use chevrons for this purpose. These are arrows arranged in a striped pattern. They are sometimes placed on roads to increase the subjectively perceived speed (Katz, 2007). The chevrons used by Laquai et al. (2010) were superimposed on the windshield in the form of a HUD. In addition, LED strips were attached to the left and right of the steering wheel (Figure 3.3).

In the test, the chevrons were faded in during dangerous situations and moved towards the driver. The animation speed as well as the number of chevrons increased with the degree of required deceleration. The LED strips consisted of RGB-LEDs and were able to show the degree of necessary deceleration in green, yellow, and red, with green representing a small and red representing a large necessary deceleration.

Laquai et al. (2010) had both concepts subjectively evaluated by subjects using a video recording. The subjects saw a car drive along a country road, in which the vehicle approached a concealed end of a traffic jam and a concealed construction site each once. The subjects then experienced the warning systems, which indicated a necessary delay early in three levels.

In general, the subjects assessed the chevrons somewhat more positively than the LED strips. However, the freely formulated statements suggest that this is mainly due to the design of the display and not to the concept itself. The participants complained that the LEDs were set

Figure 3.3: Laquai et al. (2010) investigated two display concepts that were intended to encourage the driver to reduce speed. Chevrons that were displayed via a head-up display (left) and two LED strips that were mounted next to the steering wheel (right). The images are used with the kind permission of Florian Laquai.

too bright and suggested using them as ambient light rather than being directed at the driver directly. They also wanted smooth transitions between the warning levels, both in terms of fading and in the temporal sequence of the warning levels. It is interesting to note that the subjects would have preferred to leave out the green warning level. They only wanted to be warned in case of an urgent situation. The idea of warning by means of LED stripes was considered reasonable by 30 % of the subjects.

In a subsequent study, the authors improved the display concept of the LED strip based on the subjects' comments and investigated the driving behavior in a simulator experiment (Laquai, Chowanetz, & Rigoll, 2011). For this purpose, they used two displays that were intended to encourage drivers to reduce their speed at an early stage due to an upcoming construction site or a speed limit (Figure 3.4). The first concept consisted of a 160 cm wide LED bar, which was attached to the root of the windshield. It reported back the necessary delay using three color levels. Taking off the throttle: yellow, light braking: orange and heavy braking: red. A green level was not used because of the earlier results. In addition, the size of the display increased with the proximity of the location where the target speed should be reached from a small bar of three LEDs to the width of the entire bar. The second concept consisted of two opposing LED bars mounted on the hood. These signaled the difference between the current and target speed to the driver in the event of an event for optimal deceleration. This was done in the form of an animated running light. If the speed difference was large, the running light was animated quickly and if the difference decreased, it was animated more slowly. In addition, the same color coding was used in this display concept as in the first system.

It was shown that both displays had a positive effect on braking behavior. Compared to the control condition, both systems showed that the drivers reduced their speed more evenly. The first static display also caused drivers to react earlier than when driving without a display. With the animated display, only the drivers with system slowed down their speed to the target speed (Laquai et al., 2011). In addition, both display concepts were evaluated more positively than those of the previous study. This was probably due to the fact that, based on the experience of the preliminary study, care was taken when designing both displays to ensure that the LEDs were not directed at the drivers directly and that the light was presented in a more diffuse manner.

The results of Laquai et al. (2010, 2011) show that a Fuzzy Warning can encourage drivers to adjust their driving behavior early. They also show which factors have to be considered in the design. Since LEDs can be very bright, the brightness must be adjusted to the respective environment. It should be considered to omit a green warning level and only warn when a reaction is really necessary. In general, there is an interest in this new warning system. The

Figure 3.4: Laquai et al. (2011) improved their display concept and implemented this in two displays. One long LED bar on the windshield root (Static Guiding Point) and two parallel short LED bars on the hood (Dynamic Guiding Point). Schematic diagram (left) and active displays from the driver's view (right). The illustrations are used with the kind permission of Florian Laquai.

results thus encourage further research into the topic.

3.5 Trials with a LED Matrix

Also with a LED display, but in a slightly different way, Kienast et al. (2008) investigated a hazard warning. Instead of a LED bar, they used a LED matrix mounted between the steering wheel and the windshield, which could symbolically convey warning messages to the drivers (Figure 3.5).

Figure 3.5: In the experiments of Kienast et al. (2008) and Henning et al. (2008), LED matrices were used to alert drivers to pedestrians at the roadside. Left: Small prototype from Henning et al. (2008). Right: Final system from Kienast et al. (2008, p.3). The illustrations are used with the kind permission of Matthias Henning and Henning Kienast.

Special attention was paid to the design of a contact analog display. A contact analog display shows the direction of an object outside the vehicle not by a fixed position, but relative to the position of the driver and the object. The signal is placed on an imaginary line between the driver's head position and the object and also adjusts its position in real time. A form of augmented reality is created, relevant objects from the environment are highlighted by a display.

In their study, Henning et al. (2008) compared the LED matrix with a HUD using a night vision scenario as an example. The subjects watched video recordings of a night drive and had to react to pedestrians at the side of the road as in the experiment of Mahlke et al. (2007). They could stand either to the left or right of the roadside. The drivers were supported by either the LED matrix or a HUD (Figure 3.6).

Figure 3.6: The subjects from the Henning et al. (2008) experiment saw video recordings of a night drive and had to recognize pedestrians at the side of the road. They were either detected by a HUD (left) or a LED matrix (right) is supported. The use of the images is courtesy of Henning Kienast.

In order to prevent a blind reaction to the illumination of the display, false alarms have been built into both systems. The LED-matrix differed from the HUD especially in that the display was directed. While the position of the pedestrian was indicated by the HUD, the display was always in the same position.

Both display concepts increased the detection rate compared to the control condition. The authors report this result in another publication, which seems to be based on the same data (Kienast et al., 2008). Henning et al. (2008) could not find any difference between the systems in terms of the number of pedestrians detected or the speed at which they responded.

However, this does not mean that a contact analog LED display has no advantage over the HUD with fixed position. A possible advantage would be the attention control of the driver. A directional warning has the advantage of not only indicating the presence of a hazard but also its position. To measure a directional effect it is better to detect where a target object is located rather than just checking whether it is present. This could be shown by eye movements or directional information. However, these were not included in the presented study. The directional detection is indirectly included in the detected detection time, because the subjects had to check the presence of the pedestrian before reacting to false alarms, but a direct detection of the direction or eye movements would allow stronger statements about attention control.

In the trial of Mahlke et al. (2007) the LED bar showed a high potential for fast hazard detection with low distraction compared to video-based night vision systems. Henning et al. (2008) substantiate this advantage on the basis of the visual-spatially directed display, but it is also quite possible that the low distraction from the experiment of Mahlke et al. (2007) was achieved by the non-symbolic display. It would be very interesting in a future investigation to keep the medium LED-display constant and only to directly compare the effect between symbolic and non-symbolic display in an experiment with LED-bar and LED-matrix. This would help to find out whether rather the directional display or the symbol-free display contributes to less distraction. In summary, the study of Henning et al. (2008) could not show an advantage of the LED-matrix compared to a more conventional HUD.

3.6 Conclusion

The first approaches to peripheral warnings in motor vehicles presented in this Chapter support the idea of a Fuzzy Warning as a promising alternative to classical warning systems. The following picture emerges from the studies conducted so far: The LED bar puts less strain on drivers than video-based night vision systems (Mahlke et al., 2007). It is suitable as an efficient warning system for occluded road users (Fricke, 2009) and in collision scenarios reliably leads to at least as good reaction times as classic systems (Maier et al., 2011). It is also suitable for use as an early warning system (Maier et al., 2011). Drivers can imagine the display as a warning system and would like to see smooth transitions between warning levels (Laquai et al., 2010). They prefer a display that only becomes active when an intervention is necessary and suggest that a green warning level be omitted when the danger is low (Laquai et al., 2010). Due to the high luminosity of the LEDs, it should be adjusted to a reasonable level, taking into account the ambient brightness (Laquai et al., 2010).

3.7 Open questions

Although there are already some studies on LED systems as a display concept, a systematic examination of the effect process of an Fuzzy Warning on the driver is missing. The studies carried out so far only examine one particular application case and differ from each other in many factors.

In some studies a symbol-free LED display was investigated (Mahlke et al., 2007; Fricke, 2009; Maier et al., 2011; Laquai et al., 2010, 2011), other researchers concentrated on symbol-based displays (Kienast et al., 2008; Henning et al., 2008). Specific accident scenarios were investigated in which the drivers had to react to an immediate danger and were warned by the system (Fricke, 2009; Maier et al., 2011). However, there were also investigations in which the LED display provided more information about a potential danger (Mahlke et al., 2007; Laquai et al., 2010, 2011). The indicator was either attached to the windshield root (Mahlke et al., 2007; Fricke, 2009; Maier et al., 2011; Kienast et al., 2008; Henning et al., 2008), next to the steering wheel (Laquai et al., 2010) or on the hood (Laquai et al., 2011). The applications varied between night vision systems (Mahlke et al., 2007; Kienast et al., 2008; Henning et al., 2008), collision warnings (Maier et al., 2011; Fricke, 2009) and information about upcoming obstacles on the roadway and speed recommendations (Laquai et al., 2010, 2011). The size, symbolism, position and color of the display as well as the scenario vary between the studies. This makes it very difficult to find regularities in the effect of Fuzzy Warnings. However, this is necessary in order to be able to make general statements about the design of such a display beyond a concrete warning concept. Without a specific investigation of individual factors it remains unclear how an optimal Fuzzy Warning should be designed. Therefore, this thesis examines a total of seven elementary questions in order to close these knowledge gaps.

In this thesis, the potential of the display to increase safety in road traffic shall be investigated and the effect of this new display shall be better understood. The following chapters are therefore partly concerned with the investigation of safety-related aspects, such as the distraction of the gaze from the road, reaction times to different systems and the targeted gaze orientation. However, aspects are also investigated to optimize the design of the display, such as the visibility of the display and its intuitive comprehensibility. In addition, design aspects are considered using the example of using a display for multiple messages and the effect of varying the warning transition of a multi-level warning. The knowledge gained about the different features of the display concept allows a final evaluation at the end of the work.

How well are peripheral light signals perceived under the windshield? Nearly all the concepts of a Fuzzy Warning presented in the previous section are located under the windshield. In this way, information can be presented close to the focus of vision without obscuring the view of the road. Surprisingly, none of the studies presented has investigated the general visibility of light signals at this position. This is an important step in determining how well the windshield root is suited as a position for displays. This question is discussed in Chapter 4 of this thesis.

Is a Fuzzy Warning intuitively understood? A warning system should be intuitively understandable in order to trigger the appropriate driver reaction even in time-critical situations. This is particularly important for the LED bar under investigation here, as it does not have any symbols or lettering that could help with interpretation. In previous experimental studies, drivers had been instructed in the test and thus got to know the display beforehand. In normal road traffic this is normally not the case. The intuitive comprehensibility of fuzzy displays is therefore investigated in Chapter 5.

Will the Fuzzy Warning be perceived peripherally? The design of the Fuzzy Warning aims to enable peripheral perception and thus to distract the driver's attention less from the road. This aspect has so far only been investigated by Mahlke et al. (2007) for a night vision assistance and even if the results speak for a peripheral perception, they unfortunately cannot be generalized to other application scenarios without further ado. Mahlke et al. (2007) compared the symbol-free LED bar with night vision systems based on analog video streams. Video images are visually very complex and require direct eye contact to be useful. Since they are much more sophisticated than simple symbolic displays, they are very well suited to demonstrate an effect of visual distraction. However, video-based assistance is rarely used in cars. Besides the night vision investigated by Mahlke et al. (2007), there are parking systems that make use of video images. However, the vast majority of assistance and warning systems are based on pictogram-like displays rather than video-based displays. It is therefore still unclear whether the positive effect of the LED bar can be shown in comparison with simple symbolic displays and also outside the night vision scenario. This question is therefore examined in Chapter 6.

Is a classic display sufficient for a Fuzzy Warning? To judge the usefulness of a warning, it is not sufficient to demonstrate its effect alone. Especially for a new assistance system, it must also be shown that it has an advantage over already available systems, otherwise its use is not worthwhile. The expected advantages of Fuzzy Warning are based to a large extent on its symbol-free presentation. However, in addition to an LED bar, this can also be achieved via displays already in the vehicle, such as the combined display behind the steering wheel or the multimedia display in the center of the vehicle console. Wouldn't it be most efficient to use an already existing system? Using an already existing display would be more economical and lead to lower costs of the system. This in turn would increase market penetration and thus the potential of the system to improve road safety. The question now arises whether a LED bar is needed at all to achieve a positive effect of the Fuzzy Warning. None of the reported studies has tried to realize a Fuzzy Warning using already existing display elements. This gap is closed in Chapter 7.

Can the gaze be directed with the Fuzzy Warning? Besides the potential of being perceived peripherally, the Fuzzy Warning has another advantage over classical displays. Due to the size of the display area it is possible to display warnings directly in the direction of danger. This should lead to a more efficient guidance of the eye than by a fixed positioned central clue stimulus (Remington, 1978). This provides the opportunity to direct the driver's gaze to the danger in critical situations when he is looking in a different direction. However,

this aspect of the display has not yet been investigated either. Although Mahlke et al. (2007) recorded the direction of gaze of their test subjects with the support of the night vision systems, they only evaluated the gaze allocation to the system used and not to the pedestrians to be recognized. It is therefore still unclear whether the Fuzzy Warning can also direct the gaze in a targeted manner. This question is examined in Chapter 8.

Can the Fuzzy Warning be used for more than one message? The concept of Fuzzy Warning is not limited to a single application. So far it has been investigated in the areas of night vision (Mahlke et al., 2007), collision warning (Fricke, 2009; Maier et al., 2010; Kienast et al., 2008; Henning et al., 2008) and as information for speed reduction (Laquai et al., 2010, 2010). From the results it can be concluded that the display is suitable for various application scenarios. However, this raises the question of whether the concept must be restricted to one function or whether different functions can be combined within one display. In classical displays it is quite common to use the same display for different messages. However, the messages can be distinguished from one another there due to their symbolic character. This is not easily possible with the Fuzzy Warning. How do drivers react when they receive a critical message followed by a non-critical message about the Fuzzy Warning? Will drivers react blindly to the previously experienced function or will they recognize the difference and adapt their reaction to the new situation? It would be very dangerous if drivers overreacted to an information based on a previous experience with a warning. In order to avoid this, it is necessary to study the reaction of drivers to the combination of different messages within the Fuzzy Warning. In Chapter 9 this is done using a fog information on a highway trip which is compared to a collision warning from the city area.

What provides the better warning effect, a soft or a hard warning transition? Since the Fuzzy Warning must convey messages without symbols or characters, the remaining features of color, size and animation play an even more important role in the optimal design of the display. The color scheme can be derived mainly from the codes commonly used in road traffic (red, yellow, green) and the size of the display is already examined in Chapter 7. However, it is not yet clear how animations can be used to convey messages via the LED bar. Previous studies on Fuzzy Warning also use animation, but do not manipulate it specifically. Animation can help to make a display more understandable. Using the example of a warning transition, Chapter 10 examines the effect of warning transition and animation direction.

4 How well are peripheral light signals perceived under the windshield?

Summary This study investigated how well light signals can be perceived peripherally at the front windshield root. Visibility was compared for people of different heights in two different vehicle types. The light signals were seen better in a mid-size car than in a small car. Concealment occurred only in the small car behind the steering wheel. There were no limitations in visibility due to body height, but there were limitations due to seat height. For low seated participants, masking occurred. These could be compensated by increasing the height of the strip by 11 cm. When looking straight ahead, the visibility of the signals decreased significantly from the center of the windshield. Peripheral displays should be animated from this position on, so that they are still well perceived.

4.1 Introduction

The Fuzzy Hazard Warning is a completely new display for motor vehicles. It differs from classic systems by its shape and positioning in the vehicle. In contrast to classic systems, it is mounted directly under the windshield and can use the entire length between the two A-pillars to display information. The first step in understanding its effect is to describe how well a display can be perceived at the intended location. In this case this means investigating the visibility of peripheral light signals at the base of the windshield. Although we know from basic research that spatial visual resolution generally decreases toward the periphery (Loschky et al., 2005), for the optimal design of a Fuzzy Warning at the windshield root it is important to know how well individual light signals can be seen at specific positions. Since the warning is presented visually, the effect depends directly on the visibility of the narrow display. It would easily be possible that occlusions occur or that the light signals are hardly visible due to their size. So it could be that especially people with small body size see the signals less well than those with large body size. This should be avoided in the design to maximize the usefulness of the display.

Previous findings on perception in the peripheral field of vision have mainly been derived from basic research. Although this knowledge can be used to derive general rules for the design of a peripheral warning system (section 2.2.3), it does not allow conclusions to be drawn about the specific visibility of a particular warning system at a certain location in the vehicle. The findings cannot necessarily be transferred to the automotive context. An important difference to the automotive context is the accommodation of the eyes to the correct distance. While subjects in the laboratory usually fixate on a screen or a projection screen on which the stimuli are also presented, there is a difference in distance between the fixated outside world and the displays in the vehicle when driving a car. In order to measure the actual perception of peripheral light signals at the front windshield root when the eyes are accommodated on something far away on the road, it is therefore best to recreate the natural driving situation as realistically as possible.

In fact, there are already several studies that have investigated various aspects of peripheral vision in the vehicle (Cohen, 1987; Trösterer, Dzaack, & Zschoernack, 2010; Zschoernack et al., 2010), but none of them specifically addresses the area under the windshield, which is particularly well suited for use due to its proximity to the gaze focus while driving and its

property of not occluding the traffic situation. To optimize the effect of this display, the visibility must be measured directly at the location of its intended use.

It is assumed that, due to the anatomy of our eyes, the entire light strip cannot be seen equally well when looking at the road normally (section 2.1). Instead, the visibility of the signals should decrease towards the A-pillars. But how strong is this effect and how is it influenced by the height of the driver? Another factor that could affect the visibility of the light signals is a Multimedia Interface (MMI) that protrudes from the center of the vehicle console. Mid-range cars sometimes have such a display and therefore this aspect was also considered in the study.

More accurate data can be obtained by simulating visual conditions in the vehicle. However, a simulation can also only take into account factors that are already known before the investigation and are explicitly included in the model. For the warning investigated in this thesis, visibility in the peripheral visual field is particularly relevant. A concrete measurement of the visibility of peripheral light signals at the root of the windshield in a motor vehicle has not yet been performed.

Hypothesis The aim of this study was to measure the visibility of peripheral light signals at the root of the windshield exploratively and to derive design criteria for a display to be placed there. In particular, body height was considered as an influencing factor.

4.2 Method

4.2.1 Study Design

In this experiment, three factors were investigated in a repeated measurement design. The »vehicle«, the »direction of view« and the »signal position« were varied. Three configurations were examined for the »vehicle«: »Opel Corsa«, »VW Passat without MMI« and »VW Passat with MMI«. The »direction of vision« was tested in four stages: »street«, »left rearview mirror«, »right rearview mirror« and »directly to the light signal«. The »signal position« was varied in ten steps (Figure 4.5). The visibility of the light signals was recorded as a dependent variable. A distinction was made between three levels of visibility. In the first two levels, the drivers looked straight ahead and perceived the signals only peripherally. A signal was regarded as »briefly seen« if it was detected when it was switched on, but the subjects could no longer indicate afterwards whether the signal had already been switched off again or was still lit. A signal was classified as »consistently seen« if it was seen when it was switched on and the test subjects could then indicate whether it was still lit. To determine occlusions, the third stage »seen directly« was also recorded if the subjects could see the light signal when looking directly in that direction.

4.2.2 Sample

A total of 20 subjects (55 % female) aged 20 to 48 years (mean: 27 years) and an average size of 1.67 m participated in the study. In order to specifically include people with extreme heights, four subjects were under 1.53 m and five were over 1.93 m tall. They thus belonged to the 5 % largest or smallest people in Germany (DIW Berlin, TNS Infratest Sozialforschung, 2006). The subjects had normal vision or vision corrected to a normal level and all but one had a driver's license. The average driving performance was under 9 000 km per year. For their participation, the subjects received either an expense allowance of 15 euros or 1.5 Versuchspersonenstunden (VP hours). Students have to collect a certain amount of voluntary participation (VP hours) in scientific experiments for their studies.

4.2.3 Material

Test vehicles It was assumed that cockpit design and vehicle equipment influence the visibility of the windshield root. While in inexpensive vehicles there is little space available and hardly any individual adjustments of the vehicle are possible, a vehicle of higher class offers more space and comfort. In order to be able to make statements for different vehicle types, the test was carried out with a small car (Opel Corsa) and a medium-sized car (VW Passat) (Figure 4.1). In addition to their size and model, the two vehicles differed in that the seats and steering wheel of the Passat were height-adjustable.

Figure 4.1: Two test vehicles were used in this experiment: An »Opel Corsa« (left) and a »VW Passat« (right).

Multimediainterface In order to take into account the possible concealment by a MMI protruding from the center of the vehicle console, a dummy display was installed in the VW Passat. This was comparable in position and size to a real MMI. It had the dimensions 22x11 cm and was mounted above the center console of the vehicle. The MMI was only tested in mid-size cars, since small cars rarely have such a display.

Light strip For this experiment a flexible light strip with 10 bulbs (12 V, 40 mA, 6 x 3.15 mm, clear) was made. This could be placed in both test vehicles and adapted to the individual curvature of the windshield (Figure 4.2). Using the light strip, light signals could be displayed at different positions under the windshield. The individual signals were controlled by a microcontroller and could be switched on and off one after the other in a random sequence without repetition.

Although the Fuzzy Warning should work later with LEDs, bulbs were used in this experiment. This decision was made because of the different beam angles of both light sources. LEDs spread their light over a relatively narrow angle. Therefore their orientation strongly influences the visibility. Bulbs, on the other hand, radiate uniformly in all directions and are therefore equally well visible without special positioning. The light strip had to be changed frequently between the two test vehicles for the test. It was therefore more economical to use small bulbs, as they did not have to be realigned each time the vehicle was changed.

The signals were not evenly distributed at the windshield root, but positioned in such a way that especially the relevant areas near the left and right A-pillar, behind the steering wheel and, if necessary, the MMI were covered. The exact signal positions can be found in Table 4.1.

Figure 4.2: Example construction of the light strip in the test vehicle *VW Passat*.

Signal No.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	Total
Position Opel Corsa	3	20	31	39	62	72	81	97	110	119	120
Position VW Passat	4	21	32	40	63	73	82	98	111	129	130

Table 4.1: Signal positions in both test vehicles. Distances are given in cm to the left A-pillar. The total width of the windshield root is given on the far right.

4.2.4 Procedure

The subjects filled out a demographic questionnaire and were informed about the experiment and the background of the study. They also agreed to the anonymous processing of the data collected in the trial. The experiment took place in a quiet parking lot of the Technical University of Braunschweig. This minimized distraction from passing people or passing cars. The vehicles were parked in front of a hall and the test took place at the stand with the engine switched off during the day between 10 a.m. and 6 p.m. The weather changed during the tests between sunny and cloudy. It was mostly cloudy. Only two subjects experienced rain.

At the beginning, the height of the subjects was measured without shoes. The subjects then sat in the test vehicle in the driver's seat. Visibility was to be measured under as natural conditions as possible. The subjects were therefore asked to adjust the position and height of the seat and steering wheel as they would during a normal drive. Two of the smaller participants therefore used seat cushions, which they also used during private journeys, to adjust their seat height.

All subjects received a short introduction to the test procedure. In twelve trials, the visibility was tested in both test vehicles one after the other by switching on all signals individually in random order and asking for the visibility (Table 4.2). The sequence of visibility conditions was kept constant.

In order to exclude guessing in the measurement of the signals, the direction of the signal was additionally asked for each pass in which the subjects claimed to have seen a signal. The subjects then indicated the signal position by hand gesture without turning their heads towards the signal. Only statements with correct direction were included in the evaluation. The subjects assessed the visibility for each condition in three steps: They first assessed whether a signal was visible in the periphery when they switched on (»briefly seen«) and then whether they could still perceive it (»continuously seen«). To check for occlusions, the subjects also looked directly at the signal once and indicated the visibility (»directly seen«). If at least one signal was obscured when viewed directly, the height required for visibility was determined. This was done in an additional pass in which the light bar was slowly moved upwards from the pane root until the subjects indicated that they could see all signals. The distance between the bar and the root of the windshield was measured along the windshield.

Trial	Vehicle	Direction of view	Visibility of signal
1	Opel Corsa	street	peripheral
2	Opel Corsa	left rear view mirror	peripheral
3	Opel Corsa	right rear view mirror	peripheral
4	Opel Corsa	to the light signal	direct
5	VW Passat without MMI	street	peripheral
6	VW Passat without MMI	left rear view mirror	peripheral
7	VW Passat without MMI	right rear view mirror	peripheral
8	VW Passat without MMI	to the light signal	directly
9	VW Passat with MMI	street	peripheral
10	VW Passat with MMI	left rear view mirror	peripheral
11	VW Passat with MMI	right rear view mirror	peripheral
12	VW Passat with MMI	to the light signal	directly

Table 4.2: Test sequence of the examined conditions. All subjects were tested in all conditions in the order listed here.

4.3 Results

There was no indication that the subjects tried to guess the signal position. All directions were correct.

Occlusions Occlusion only occurred in the Opel Corsa and only affected signals 2, 3 and 4 directly behind the steering wheel. Here five subjects did not see all signals. These were between 130 and 165 in size and thus only tended to be the smallest persons in the sample (Figure 4.3). A better indicator of occlusion was the eye distance to the vehicle ceiling. The five subjects whose vision was obscured sat deepest in the vehicle. The very small drivers benefited from their seat cushions and were able to compensate for visual restrictions themselves. As a result, taller drivers who sat lower could perceive the signals more poorly than smaller drivers who sat higher up. In the Passat there were no occlusions and it did not matter whether a MMI was installed or not. When compensating for the occlusions behind the steering wheel, it was found that an average raised mounting of the light strip of 11 cm above the windshield root was sufficient to compensate for all occlusions.

Visibility in the periphery In the peripheral visual field, differences in visibility were found both in the »signal position« and between the »direction of view« and »vehicles«. In general, the peripheral light signals were seen better in the »VW Passat« than in the »Opel Corsa«. When looking in the left rearview mirror, most of the peripheral signals were overlooked, while few were overlooked when looking straight at the road (Figure 4.4).

Visibility decreased with increasing distance from the focus of the view. This effect was stronger in the small car than in mid-size car (Figure 4.5). When looking at the road, only 55 % of the signals at the right A-pillar could be seen constantly from the corner of the eye. A further 40 % of the signals in the VW Passat and 25 % in the Opel Corsa could only be perceived briefly when they changed. The subjects were thus able to see the change in a signal state (»briefly seen«) better than the continuous light signal itself (»continuously seen«) (Figure 4.5).

Gaze direction The orientation of the head had a strong influence on the visibility of the signals. While when looking at the road, the least visible signal was still 95 % in the VW

Figure 4.3: Overview of subjects with occlusions, subdivided by body height and sorted by distance between eye level and vehicle ceiling. The significance of the ceiling distance was only recognized and recorded from the fourth subject onwards.

Figure 4.4: Proportion of signals not seen peripherally, divided into »direction of view« and »vehicle«.

View to the left rear view mirror

View to the street

View to the right rear view mirror

VW Passat

Figure 4.5: Relative frequencies of peripheral visibility of light signals in the Opel Corsa (above) and VW Passat (below) when looking at the left rearview mirror, at the road and at the right rearview mirror. The labeling of the X-axis shows the signal number counted from the left, the white dots below it show the actual signal positions. The empty area up to the 100 % of each column indicates how many subjects have not seen the signal

Passat and 80 % in the Opel Corsa, when looking at the left rearview mirror, these values fell to 60 % in the VW Passat and 65 % in the Opel Corsa (Figure 4.5). The strongest restrictions were found in the area of the right A-pillar when looking at the left rearview mirror.

Orientation reaction Some subjects reported that in rare cases they looked directly at the signal, contrary to the test instructions and without intending to do so.

4.4 Discussion

The aim of this investigation was to determine the visibility of peripheral light signals at the front windshield root. The results support known effects from basic research and also provide specific distributions of the relative visibility of peripheral light signals at the front windshield root in a motor vehicle. The measured decrease of the constantly visible light signals corresponds approximately to the course of the density of the cones on our retina that are responsible for sharp vision. Particularly in the extreme periphery, the signals are only briefly seen when switched on, which represents a change in brightness. This effect can be explained by the rods that predominate in the periphery, which are particularly sensitive to movement and changes, and the low density of cones that enable sharp vision. The boundary between permanent and only temporary visibility was located approximately in the middle of the windshield root. Signals presented here or further in the periphery were only briefly seen at power-on. The results indicate that a peripheral display can be perceived better if it is animated from this point on.

Peripheral perception of the display The view of the road is the natural line of sight when driving a vehicle. It could be shown that most of the peripheral light signals examined here were seen in this gaze direction. Only 6 % of the signals in the small car and less than 2 % of the signals in the mid-size car were overlooked when looking at the road. Overall, visibility was also better in the mid-range car for all directions of vision. Only half as many peripheral signals were overlooked here as in the small car. However, this value could be reduced significantly in the small car by placing the lightbar about 11 cm above the windshield root. Overall, the light stimuli were perceived much better at the time of lighting up (»briefly seen«) than afterwards (»continuously seen«). This effect shows the importance of an eye-catching presentation by changing the brightness of the display. It can be assumed that the visibility could be additionally increased by larger and brighter displays or the use of animations. Thus, the front screen root is well suited for peripheral displays.

Guidance through a peripheral display Sudden changes in brightness in the field of vision can direct a person's attention in a targeted manner (Theeuwes, 1991; Remington et al., 1992; McCormick, 1997). This well-researched effect of involuntary attention could also be observed in this experiment. The observed orientation reaction to changing stimuli in the periphery shows the potential of a peripheral display to direct the driver's gaze. This can be useful in alerting drivers to the direction of hazards. This effect could be further enhanced by the targeted selection of the display position. When looking in the left or right rearview mirror, the point of best visibility shifted to the left or right, respectively. One possible consequence for the design would be that the direction of the driver's gaze would be taken into account when a peripheral warning is displayed. While a warning is displayed directly in front of the driver when he is looking straight ahead, it could be displayed offset in the direction of vision when he is looking straight to the left or right. Also an eye-catching animation could be conceivable, which starts offset in the viewing direction, but is then animated in the target direction to lead

the driver's gaze there. This could also be a dynamic location, like the hazard direction. If the driver is looking straight to the left, a light signal is best visible in the area of the left A-pillar. However, if a hazard is approaching from the right, an attempt could be made to draw the driver's attention to the hazard by animating from the viewing direction to the hazard direction. Such a concept is examined later in Chapter 10.

Seat height affects visibility Another aspect of this study was to determine whether there are limitations in peripheral or direct vision in the area of the frontal windshield root for particularly small or large people. Using two vehicle classes as examples, it was shown that these restrictions were only present in small cars. The observed occlusions were less related to body height than to seat height. This is relevant in that when optimizing the visibility of a display at the front windshield root, only people sitting low down need to be considered. Small people in particular already adapt their vehicles individually by themselves and therefore sometimes have fewer visibility restrictions than their larger fellow human beings. Height-adjustable seats are a simple solution for visibility restrictions.

Occlusions behind the steering wheel Occlusions only occurred in the area behind the steering wheel. This area is therefore critical for a Fuzzy Warning directly aimed at the driver. An indirect presentation, e.g. via a mirroring at a higher position in the windshield, could counteract this negative effect. The MMI used had no effect on visibility. However, since the MMI condition was only tested in the Passat, occlusions by the MMI in the Corsa cannot be ruled out.

Conclusion and Outlook The results of this study confirm the transferability of basic research on peripheral perception to the automotive context. They not only show that the front windshield root is suitable for peripheral warning, but also provide information about the optimal position of the display within the strip and highlight the significance and potential of changes in brightness.

When interpreting the results, however, it must be taken into account that only two vehicles were examined here as examples, which means that the results are not directly transferable to other vehicles that differ significantly in their design from the tested models. The study provided first findings regarding the use of peripheral vision for warning systems and which factors have to be considered technically. These results can serve as a basis for further investigations. In order to be able to make statements that are as representative as possible, the test vehicles were specifically selected from two widely used vehicle classes. However, since different vehicle models differ in the design of the driver's cab, the statements initially only apply to the tested vehicles, and models with similar interior structures.

As briefly mentioned at the beginning, the light bulbs used here were used for practical reasons of test execution. Due to their low latency, low power consumption and high light output, LEDs are more suitable for use in a Fuzzy Warning. It is possible that the visibility distributions of LED displays look slightly different. However, a generally higher visibility is more likely to be expected due to the stronger luminosity than a change in the shape of the curve.

Perceptibility and understanding of the displayed message are basic requirements for every assistance system in the vehicle. While this study was able to show that the Fuzzy Warning is clearly visible in the periphery, it is still unclear whether its meaning is also understood. This question will be examined in the next Chapter.

5 Is a Fuzzy Warning intuitively understood?

Summary The Fuzzy Hazard Warning displays warnings and information without symbols or characters. The following study investigated whether a peripheral warning message is intuitively understandable and can influence driving behavior. Drivers successively experienced a speed warning, a rear-end collision warning and a lane departure warning without having been told the purpose beforehand. There was also a control condition without warning. It turned out that the function of the three warning systems investigated were intuitively understood. In addition, drivers with a speed warning were more likely to adhere to the prescribed maximum speed, although they were not instructed to react to the warning. The Fuzzy Warning is intuitively understandable and drivers adapt their behavior independently based on the display.

5.1 Introduction

After it could be shown in Chapter 4 that the area under the windshield is basically suitable for displaying peripheral signals, this study will examine a second important requirement for the use of a Fuzzy Warning. If no symbols can be used and the display is only seen from the corner of the eye, it is very generic in principle. To use the information conveyed by this display, drivers must understand the reason for the warning or information.

The question arises whether a warning message designed in this way is intuitively understood and can influence driving behavior at all. To answer these questions, this study compared three warning systems with a control condition without a system. The systems came from different fields of application in order to give enough leeway for the interpretation of their function. The subjects consecutively drove with a »speed warning«, a »collision warning« and a »lane departure warning«. In order to observe the natural reaction of the drivers to the warnings and to check whether they intuitively understand the meaning, the function of the warnings was not explained. Nevertheless, the three systems studied had the objective of encouraging drivers to adopt a safer driving style in terms of the three areas of cruising speed, safe distance or lane keeping.

Research question The main question was whether the subjects were able to correctly describe the function of the experienced systems after 20 min of driving. Additionally, it was assumed that the subjects would adjust their driving behavior based on the displays.

5.2 Method

5.2.1 Study Design

The question was investigated in a field study in a single factor repeated measurement design with the factor »warning system« and the factor levels »speed warning«, *rear-end warning*, »lane departure warning« and without warning as a »control«. The driving behavior, the system evaluation and the functional description of the systems were evaluated as dependent

variables. The repeated measurement design was chosen to exclude the influence of differences between the subjects as an interfering variable. It was not assumed that an all too strong learning effect would occur, since the three systems were very different. On each of the four sections of the track a different warning was used. The order of the warnings was distributed among the sections according to the Latin square method, so that across the subjects all conditions occurred equally frequently on all sections. In this way it was prevented that the different sections of the route had a systematic influence on the dependent variables.

5.2.2 Sample

24 subjects (50 % female) aged 18-33 years (median 21 years) participated in this study. All subjects were in possession of a valid driver's license. None of the subjects had unusually intensive experience with FAS and thus had an advantage in recognizing the systems. Most of them were students of the TU-Braunschweig, who had held their driver's license for four years (median). The median driving performance was less than 9 000 km per year. The sample contained about the same number of drivers who said they had a »calm« or »dynamic« driving style. To avoid perception problems due to visual acuity, the subjects had normal vision or vision corrected to normal levels. The participants received either an expense allowance of 30 euros or three VP hours, which they needed for their studies.

5.2.3 Material

Test vehicle A converted VW Golf V was used for data collection. It had a LED bar, which was attached to the root of the windshield. In the trunk was a computer with which the driving data was recorded during the test. The vehicle also had a driving school pedal set on the passenger seat so that the test operator could intervene in an emergency.

LED-bar and brightness adjustment The bar used was 120 cm long and thus reached over the entire width of the windshield. It consisted of 120 RGB-LEDs, which could be individually controlled by a microcontroller. Taking into account the results of Laquai et al. (2010), the brightness of the LEDs was adjusted to the lighting conditions of the environment to avoid glare for the drivers. As an objective reference value, the resistance of a photodiode was measured before each ride. In order to compensate for fluctuations, five measurements were taken at different orientations of the diode and the average value was determined. The first measurement was made with the diode pointing to the sky in the middle between driver and passenger seat at a height of approx. 40 cm. The further measurements were made with an inclination of 45° from the starting position towards the passenger door and then from this orientation in distances of 90° around the starting position.

In order to determine the ideal brightness values, six test drivers were asked to adjust the brightness of the LED strip to a level that was comfortable for them under different ambient lighting conditions. The ambient brightness was measured with the photodiode. Based on this data, a distribution function could be calculated to adjust the brightness of the LEDs to the respective lighting conditions during the experiment.

Test track In order to increase the representativeness and to obtain sufficient opportunities for the activity of the assistance systems, a test track was chosen which had both different guideline speeds and a medium traffic density. The influence of other road users besides motor vehicles should be minimized. Therefore the data collection was carried out exclusively on the freeway. The drivers drove once from Braunschweig to Echte and back during the test. The route took the A39 and A7 and was divided into four sections (Figure 5.1). The sections were

about the same length (A and D = 40 km, B and C = 33 km). On sections A and D there were some construction sites and therefore several speed limits between 60 and 120 km/h. On sections B and C there were hardly any construction sites and only very few speed limits. The driving time per section was 20-25 min. Between the sections there was a short break at a rest area.

Figure 5.1: The Test Track. The test drivers drove from Braunschweig to Echte and back. The sections with a high number of construction sites are marked schematically, but the symbols do not indicate the actual number and position. The map material was kindly provided by OpenStreetMap under the CC-BY-SA 2.0 license. © OpenStreetMap Contributors <http://www.openstreetmap.org/> copyright

Warnings All three warning systems examined were presented purely visually and only via the described LED bar. In order to clarify the function, all warnings were designed in such a way that the drivers received direct feedback on their behavior. Instead of a simple limit at which the warning became active, the display reacted continuously to the behavior of the drivers. The size, position, brightness or color of the warning was adapted to the driving speed, the distance to the vehicle in front or the lane position. In this way, the drivers received evaluative feedback on their driving behavior in the form of a smooth transition between normal driving situation and warning event. In this way, an accompanying system activity was created. To avoid distracting the driver, the feedback was designed to be as non-invasive as possible. Only if the permissible maximum speed was significantly exceeded, if a vehicle approached too fast in front or left the lane, a salient warning was given.

The »speed warning« consisted of a 40 cm wide red light bar, which was displayed in the middle in front of the driver. The warning only became active if the vehicle was driving at least 10 km/h too fast. The brightness was regulated equivalent to the intensity of the violation. In case of a slight violation the display lit up only weakly, in case of a strong violation it lit up intensively. After a speeding violation of 20 km/h, the display began to pulsate slowly by fading the brightness up and down at 0.3 Hz (Figure 5.2, A).

Figure 5.2: Drivers were confronted with a total of three warning systems. The speed warning (A) became active only when driving more than 10 km/h above the current speed limit. It was visible in the form of a red bar in front of the driver. The brightness of the bar increased with stronger violation and started pulsating in the brightness at a violation of 20 km/h above the limit. The collision warning (B) was visible in the form of a small green bar in front of the driver when a vehicle was in front of the driver. The size and color of the bar changed as the distance decreased, taking into account the current speed. The smaller the distance, the redder and larger the bar became. When the distance was very small, the bar flashed to indicate the danger. The Lane Departure Warning (C) was constantly visible as a white bar in the middle in front of the driver. As the vehicle approached the edge of the lane, the bar moved in the opposite direction. This indicated the direction in which the vehicle should be driven to get back to the center of the lane. When the vehicle crossed over a lane mark, the display flashed. The course of all warnings is shown here schematically for better readability and does not correspond exactly to the sequence of events.

The »collision warning« was only activated if another vehicle was in the sensor area in front of the ego vehicle. If this was the case, a bar lit up in the middle in front of the driver, which indicated the distance to the vehicle in front based on its color and width. If the vehicle was far away, the bar was only 2 cm wide and colored green. If the distance decreased, the bar grew and turned orange at a Time Headway (TH) of less than 1.3 s and later red at a distance of less than 0.7 s. When an impact was imminent, the bar grew to the full width of the bar, turned red and flashed at 4 Hz (Figure 5.2, B).

The »lane departure warning« consisted of a 20 cm wide white bar whose position depended on the position of the vehicle on the lane. If the driver was driving in the middle of the lane, the bar was exactly in front of him. If the driver deviated to the left or right, the beam moved in the opposite direction. In this way, the beam was always on the side of the driver that he would have to drive to get back to the center of the lane. The system also flashed to indicate that the driver was leaving the lane. When a lane mark was crossed, the bar flashed at 4 Hz. If no lane was detected, the bar jumped to the center of the LED bar and was dimly lit. This was to indicate system inactivity (Figure 5.2, C).

5.2.4 Procedure

The subjects filled out a demographic questionnaire and were informed about the trial and the background of the study. All subjects also agreed to the anonymous processing of the data collected in the trial. They then adjusted the seat and rearview mirrors to their size. Care was taken to ensure that the view of the LED bar was not obscured by the steering wheel. They then drove a 1 km distance to a parking lot. During this short drive, the test drivers were able to adjust to the test vehicle. The parking lot was used to adjust the brightness of the LED bar to the given lighting conditions.

The test drivers were informed that they would be driving with three novel assistance systems, the effect of which is to be investigated. However, they were not told which systems would be involved. Their task was to find out what message the respective system was supposed to convey to them. Thereupon, the test drivers drove to the freeway access road and the test drive began with the first condition.

In addition to the test driver, there were two other people in the vehicle. The test supervisor sat in the passenger seat in order to be able to intervene via the second pedal in an emergency. An assistant to the test supervisor sat in the back seat behind the driver. While driving, she entered the current speed limits into the system, as these could not be detected automatically. The new speed became active the moment a sign with the limit was passed. The input was quiet and could hardly be heard over the engine noise. After the test, several test drivers inquired about how the system could automatically detect the speed limit so well. This indicates that the test drivers did not notice the manual input.

After completing a section, the test drivers answered a short questionnaire in writing in which they assessed the warning and described the presumed function of the warning. While driving, conversations with the driver were avoided to minimize distraction. The test duration was about three hours.

5.3 Results

5.3.1 Data preparation

All effects are reported to be significant from $p < .05$ onwards. Since the variance between the test drivers can be ignored in repeat measurement designs (Loftus & Masson, 1994), error bars for repeat measurement designs are shown corrected in all diagrams. In all evaluations

where it was appropriate, the assumption of normal distribution of the data was checked both visually and with the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test. In the following, we will only report whether there were indications of violation of the assumption.

Weather The experiment took place in January and February 2010. During the data collection the weather alternated between snowfall and bright sunshine. Although the weather hardly affected data collection as a whole, there were two cases where subjects' data could not be used. The vehicle's lane detection and distance sensors were severely affected by snow in these cases. These two test drivers were replaced by two new test drivers.

5.3.2 Were the warnings intuitively understandable?

After each warning they experienced, the test drivers briefly noted down their suspected function of the system in their own words on a questionnaire. After data collection, these answers were read and classified independently by two raters. The raters had the task to decide in each case whether the function of the display was described correctly or not. An answer was considered correct if it described the driving behaviour to be achieved or the reason for the warning. Examples of correct answers for the »speed warning« are "The system indicates when driving too fast", "Check for Speeding" or "Check for Speed". Example of an incorrect response for the »speed warning«: "Construction sites entrance/exit or narrowing or fewer lanes". Only the answers marked as »correct« by both raters were included in the trip data evaluation. The agreement between the two raters was $\kappa = .70$ and can therefore be considered good (Landis & Koch, 1977).

It was shown that the subjects were very well able to recognize the function of the warnings, although they were not given any information about the system (Figure 5.3). Over 87 % of the drivers recognized the system function independently of the experienced system.

Figure 5.3: Test drivers who correctly recognized the system function, by experienced system. Regardless of the experienced warning, at least 88 % of the test drivers correctly recognized the function.

There were some situations in which the display could not be experienced in function as intended. For example, sometimes the track sensors malfunctioned due to missing track markings at construction sites or markings covered by snow. This affected the function of the »lane departure warning«. Also, some test drivers were not confronted with certain warnings due to their driving style or the traffic situation. For example, there was one test driver who never drove too fast and therefore did not experience the »speed warning«. If the measured values are adjusted for these impairments, which can be traced back to the sensor technology and the driving behavior, the correct system recognition increases to over 95 % of the drivers.

5.3.3 Was the driving behavior influenced by the warnings?

Speed warning The goal of the »speed warning« was to get drivers to adhere more closely to speed limits. To test the effect, the average duration and the number of speed violations with »speed warning« and without any warning (control) were compared. Both conditions were compared using a t-test for paired samples. Without warning the drivers drove significantly longer too fast than with »speed warning« $t(22) = -5.03, p = .001, r = .73$ (Figure 5.4).

The number of speeding violations was considered another indicator of the effect of the warning. Again, both conditions were compared using a t-test for paired samples. It was found that significantly more speeding violations occurred when driving with »speed warning« than without warning $t(22) = 3.12, p = .005, r = .55$ (Figure 5.5). This result seems surprising at first. If the speed warning was used more often, how can the average duration of the violation be lower with warning? To investigate this, the driving patterns of the individual test drivers were examined more closely. It was found that drivers without warning maintained their speed if they were too fast, while drivers with »speed warning« oscillated around the speed limit (Figure 5.6). The test drivers adapted their driving behavior to the warning, but tried to drive faster, only to brake again when the warning became active.

Furthermore, there was evidence that the drivers reacted even to a weak illumination of the warning. A light up was classified as weak if the light intensity was less than half the maximum luminosity. This corresponded to a slight speeding of less than 15 km/h. Now, when drivers were warned by the »speed warning« that they were driving too fast, 67 % of the violations were slight, as opposed to 41 % for driving without warning and thus without any indication (Figure 5.7).

Figure 5.4: Mean duration of speeding violations by experienced system. On average, without the speed warning, the drivers were speeding for 11 s longer.

Figure 5.5: Mean number of speeding violations by experienced system. With speed warning there were on average six more violations than without.

Collision warning The »collision warning« should avoid tailgating by visualizing the distance to the front vehicle relative to the current speed to the drivers. One effect should be that the drivers less frequently drive too close to the vehicle in front. In this study, a distance of less than 1.4 s TH was considered to be too close to the vehicle. The values were adjusted for sudden merging behind a vehicle and acceleration during overtaking. These events were identified based on the distance to the vehicle in front and the own lane changes. If the distance to the vehicle in front changed abruptly to a very low value and a lane change took place, this was considered close merging. If the distance to the front vehicle suddenly changed to a very high value and a lane change took place, this was considered an overtaking maneuver.

Figure 5.6: Driving behavior with and without speed warning relative to the speed limit (illustrated). With speed warning, drivers often drove too fast, because they oscillated around the allowed speed limit.

Figure 5.7: Number of light and heavy speeding violations by warning. With warning there were more minor violations (<15 km/h too fast) than in the control condition.

The number of situations in which the test drivers drove too close was compared between driving with the »collision warning« and driving without warning. The data were not normally distributed, so both conditions were compared using a Wilcoxon Sign-Rank Test for paired samples. With »collision warning« the subjects tended to drive too close less frequently than when driving without warning, but the difference was not significant $z = -1.76$, $p = .082$, $r = -.36$ (Figure 5.8).

Figure 5.8: Number of situations in which the vehicle was driven too close, by warning. Without a collision warning, the number of situations with tailgating was twice as high.

In order to check whether the general safety distance to the vehicle in front was affected by the warning, it was tested for differences between the condition with warning and driving without warning. The conditions were compared using a t-test for paired samples. The general safety distance to the front vehicle was not significantly influenced by the warning $t(22) = -.25$, $p = .804$, $r = -.05$. Independent of the condition, the subjects drove with a mean distance of TH = 2.5 s to the front vehicle on the highway.

Lane departure warning This system continuously informed the driver of his position in the current lane and warned him if he crossed the lane markings. A positive effect of the system was

to result in less unwanted lane departure or generally more accurate lane keeping. Undesired lane departure was not investigated in this study, because drivers usually only leave the lane if they are impaired in any way. For safety reasons, it was decided not to induce this condition during the test. Instead, the general lane keeping quality was evaluated. On the one hand, the mean deviation from the lane center and the mean deviation from the personal ideal line were considered.

The assumption of the normal distribution was violated for the mean deviation from the lane center, therefore the two conditions »lane departure warning«and without warning were compared with the Wilcoxon Sign-Rank Test. There was no significant difference between the conditions $z = -1.08$, $p = .292$, $r = -.22$.

The standard deviation from the personal ideal line is often a better measure of lane keeping, since drivers rarely drive exactly in the middle of a lane. Therefore, the conditions were compared with a t-test for paired samples. No significant difference was found between the two conditions $t(22) = -1.05$, $p = .305$, $r = .22$. Thus, there was no evidence that the »lane departure warning«influenced the driving behavior.

5.3.4 How were the three systems assessed?

The three warnings tested were also active during normal behavior while driving and were therefore visible for a longer time than other systems. The question here is whether the drivers felt disturbed or supported by the accompanying display. To investigate this, all test drivers were asked to rate the systems as either »helpful«, »neutral« or »annoying«. The majority of the test drivers assessed the »speed warning« and »collision warning« positively, only the »lane departure warning«was assessed very negatively (Figure 5.9). In addition, the test drivers were given the opportunity to make free comments on the warning systems.

Two statements were mentioned particularly frequently. On the one hand, the respondents wanted the warning to be activated only if there was a danger. Secondly, they wanted the warning levels to be linked to existing penalty systems. It was suggested that warnings should be displayed if the current driving behavior would lead to points in Flensburg (a strike model in Germany) or when a speed camera is upcoming.

Figure 5.9: Evaluations of the investigated systems. While the speed and rear-end collision warnings were assessed as neutral to helpful, the lane departure warning was found to be rather disturbing.

5.4 Discussion

The aim of this study was to find out whether Fuzzy Warnings are intuitively understood and whether drivers adapt their behavior based on the display.

The Fuzzy Warning is intuitively understandable The subjects were able to independently recognize the system function within a 20 minute drive without any additional explanation of the function. The high recognition rate is probably due to the animation of the displays, which is analogous to the driving behavior. The drivers experienced how the display reacted to their behavior and had many opportunities to observe the reactions of the display through the accompanying activity of the display. A classic warning signal is only shown briefly in a rare dangerous situation. The advantage of the continuous presentation is that drivers can experience the animation of the display as a reaction to their driving behavior and thus associate it with a function. The meaning of the display is thus easier to understand. For the concept to work, the display must be able to react to different driver reactions in several subtle gradations. For example, a directional indication with 30 steps would be better than one with 3 steps, since the many degrees of freedom allow a higher correlation to one's own behavior. As a result, the feedback from the display can be more precisely traced back to the driver's own behavior. Probably the display would be less well understood if it was less active or had a rougher resolution. These hypotheses should be investigated in future studies.

The few inaccurate descriptions of the system function were mainly from test drivers who, due to their driving style or the natural traffic situation, were unable to experience the system in action, or only to a limited extent. Although the display here had to be evaluated as *not recognized*, this was not a weakness of the display, as it was simply not relevant for this driver.

The warning influences the driving behavior It is particularly interesting that the test drivers drove too fast by themselves less often when driving with the »speed warning«, although they were not instructed to adjust their behavior according to the warning. The test drivers did this on their own initiative. Why did they adjust their behavior based on the »speed warning« but not on the other two systems? A possible reason would be the design of the systems. But it could also be that the »speed warning« had the highest immediate relevance for the drivers. While driving, there was definitely the danger of being caught by a speed camera and having to pay a fine for speeding. On the other hand, it was very unlikely that drivers would be held accountable for driving too close or leaving their lane. In contrast to the other two systems, the »speed warning« was therefore an indicator for a possible punishment, which could directly affect the driver. This is interesting because the speedometer provided the drivers with the necessary information even in the control condition. Nevertheless, only driving with a Fuzzy Warning led to speed adjustment. A possible explanation would be that the Fuzzy Warning was more salient and therefore more difficult to ignore. Another explanation would be that the »speed warning«, unlike the speedometer, actively indicated the moment of speeding. Especially the oscillation around the maximum permitted speed indicates that the active hint and thus the memory of the misbehavior played a role. The cause could also be the fuzzy presentation. Since the speedometer is labeled with small numbers, the effort of reading it while driving is greater than with the larger and symbol-free LED bar. Maybe the drivers reacted more often to the bar, because it was possible without much effort.

Regardless of the cause, a slight lighting up of the display has already been reacted to. So the peripheral weak illumination of a red light bar could influence the behavior better than the regular display of a speedometer. In the most conservative interpretation, this at least shows the potential of displays that have the information of current speed limits and report these back to the driver dynamically. Again, additional research is needed to determine whether this

effect is due to the Fuzzy Warning, the dynamic presentation, the large display or possibly even the presence of the test supervisors in combination with the large display.

The warnings are judged predominantly positive The subjects welcomed the new form of assistance and judged both the »collision warning« and the »speed warning« predominantly positive. The »speed warning« was also often assessed neutrally. This was probably due to the fact that drivers do not like to be patronized when choosing their speed. The »lane departure warning« was predominantly assessed negatively. This was probably due to the design of the display. The »lane departure warning« was the only display that was white and therefore the brightest compared to the other displays. It was also active longer than the other warnings due to continuous feedback, but still had the least relevance to current driving behavior. Since normal lane changes were also indicated by a flashing light, this indicator was very noticeable even with normal correct driving behavior.

Conclusion and Outlook The intuitive comprehensibility of the Fuzzy Warning found here cannot easily be generalized to all peripheral displays, because it is not yet clear which factors are responsible for understanding the displays. Nevertheless, the results show that it is basically possible to convey intuitively understandable messages with a symbol-free display. However, this applies first of all to individual warnings, which are displayed via the LED bar. It remains unclear whether the comprehensibility decreases if several warnings are presented alternately or even combined. Since there are already many displays in the vehicle, it cannot be a long-term solution to introduce a new display for each new function. Sooner or later, drivers would simply be overloaded and would be distracted rather than benefit from the displays. One way to avoid this would be to combine warnings in one display. This is quite common for displays in a combined display, but does the differentiation of the individual messages also work with symbol-free warnings? Further research is needed to find out. An important aspect of this question is the driver's reaction, which should also be appropriate when combining warnings in a display of the warning message. This topic is covered in Chapter 9.

Another aspect that was not addressed in this study is the long-term effect of the display. Although a change in behavior could be induced in the short time frame of the study, it is unclear whether this effect will persist for a long time with daily use or whether there will be a habituation effect. To test this, long-term studies are necessary.

While performance in driving behavior was examined in this study, it remains unclear how the information presented is perceived. Driving performance depends not only on lane keeping, speed selection and safety distance, but also on the ability to react quickly to suddenly appearing hazards. The direction of attention is relevant here, because if a display distracts attention from the road, important events on the road can be overlooked (Wierwille, 1995). How does this new type of Fuzzy Warning influence the distribution of vision and how does it compare to the systems currently in use? Initial findings in this area have already been collected by Mahlke et al. (2007). However, their results are limited to the comparison of the LED warning with night vision systems based on analog video images. Also, these systems are still very rarely found in vehicles. They therefore have a small market share and little impact on road safety. They are also characterized by the fact that they are visually very complex. The more widespread systems with simple symbolic displays will probably attract less attention than an analog video image. It is therefore necessary to compare the gaze behavior between a LED display and a classic symbolic display again. This will be addressed in the next study.

6 Is the Fuzzy Warning perceived peripherally?

Summary The aim of this study was to find out whether the Fuzzy Hazard Warning actually attracts the gaze less than a classic display. To this end, a series-produced warning system consisting of a black-and-white combined display with a warning tone and a red LED warning without a warning tone was compared in an inner-city rear-end collision scenario. In addition to eye movements, the test subjects' reaction times were also recorded. The gaze data showed that the LED warning was viewed less frequently than the combined display. The results support the assumption that the LED warning is perceived more peripherally than centrally and thus distracts the gaze less from the road.

6.1 Introduction

In a previous study, it was already shown that light signals under the windshield are easily perceived by people of different heights and that the appearance of a signal is better perceived than its continuous illumination (Chapter 4). It has also been demonstrated that even a non-symbolic Fuzzy Warning is intuitively understandable and can influence driving behavior (Chapter 5). Both findings confirm the assumption that the Fuzzy Warning under the windshield is basically suitable as a warning concept. The next step is to investigate whether the display offers an advantage over previous display concepts. As already discussed in the introduction, the display on the LED bar should also be perceptible from the periphery in contrast to classical displays. If this is the case and drivers make use of this option, the LED bar should distract the driver's attention less from the road than a classic display.

The comparison should be made in a scenario that occurs frequently and where a symbolic display is already in use. Therefore, a collision warning was chosen. In this study, the gaze behavior was examined in three critical rear-end collision situations. The drivers were supported either by a black and white combined display with a warning tone or a red LED warning without a warning tone. This comparison seems unfair favoring the combined display, since the warning tone probably binds the attention of the driver more than a purely visual warning. However, the comparison is appropriate in that this audio-visual warning represents the system currently in use on the market. This system would not be installed today without a warning sound. A new system must therefore be measured against this standard, and a comparison with a combined display without warning sound would have little practical relevance.

In the past, multimodal warnings have proven to be advantageous in terms of reaction times (Diederich & Colonius, 2004; Forster, Cavina-Pratesi, Aglioti, & Berlucchi, 2002). Previous research on multimodal displays suggests that, in terms of response times, Fuzzy Warnings will also benefit from a warning tone. However, the warning potential of a purely visual Fuzzy Warning is already comparable to that of a warning tone (Maier et al., 2010). In this study, the display, in contrast to the combined display, is closer to the driver's visual focus and, with a size of 126 cm x 0.5 cm, has a much larger warning area than the combined display of 5 cm x 7.5 cm used. This makes it possible to achieve the same warning effect despite the omission of the warning sound. To justify the use of a new type of display, it is more effective to show its advantage over a real system than over a system that is not installed. And the effect is all the

more convincing if the same effect can be achieved with fewer means. Therefore, it was decided here to follow the practical approach.

Hypothesis It was suspected that the LED warning on activity is viewed less frequently than the combined display. It was further assumed that the LED bar is responded to at least as quickly as the combined display. In addition, it should be determined exploratively which of the displays is preferred by the drivers.

6.2 Method

6.2.1 Test Design

In this study, the factor »warning« was investigated in a between subject design. The two levels »combined display with sound« and »LED-warning without sound« were varied. Eye movements, reaction time to three critical events and subjective ratings of the displays were considered as dependent variables. The group design was chosen to minimize the influence of the expected learning effect on the critical events.

6.2.2 Sample

A total of 22 subjects (46 % female) aged 19-33 years participated in the study (median 22 years). Most of them were young beginners who studied at the TU-Braunschweig. All test drivers had normal or corrected vision at a normal level. The participants received either an expense allowance of 15,- Euro or 1.5 VP hours, which they needed for their studies.

6.2.3 Material

Driving simulator The test took place in the driving simulator of the engineering and traffic psychology department of the TU-Braunschweig. The driving simulator consisted of a seat box with real driver's seat and a force feedback steering wheel (Figure 6.1). This made it very similar to driving in a real vehicle. The visibility of the rearview mirrors and instruments was displayed on LCD screens. The simulation environment was presented via three projectors with a resolution of 1 400 x 1 050 pixels each on three screens. The screens had a size of 220 x 200 cm and were positioned at an angle of 110° to each other. They covered a total field of view of 180°. The simulation software SILAB 2.1 on Windows XP was used. With SILAB a variety of environments (inner/outer city routes) and situations (crossroads, traffic circles, crosswalk) can be created. A high degree of manipulation of the involved objects (vehicles, pedestrians, objects) is possible. The vehicles have a realistic physics model, which is based on the driving behavior of real reference vehicles. The simulator also had a fully functional gear shifting system, but this was set to automatic for the experiment.

LED bar The warnings were displayed via a 126 cm long and 0.5 cm high LED bar, which was placed in front of the driver (Figure 6.1). The position of the bar relative to the driver corresponded to the position of the windshield root in a PKW. It was slightly curved to simulate the diffraction of the windshield. The bar consisted of 120 RGB-LEDs whose light was scattered through a diffuse plexiglass pane, creating a smooth transition between the active and inactive LEDs.

Figure 6.1: The driving simulator of engineering and traffic psychology at the TU-Braunschweig (left) with the used LED bar (right).

Figure 6.2: Left: Dikablis Eye-Tracking Glasses. The Fieldcam captures the field of vision of the test driver, the Eyecam captures the left pupil. Right: Test driver with Dikablis eye-tracking glasses

Eye tracking In order to be able to measure the line of sight while driving, the eye tracking system Dikablis was used. This system consists of light glasses (79 g), which record the eye movements with 25 Hz monocular by a camera on the left eye. Another camera records the observed scene (Figure 6.2). Dikablis can also be used by wearers of contact lenses or glasses. For a quantitative evaluation of the observed areas, head movements after the recording are deducted. This is done with the help of special markers, which are placed in the field of vision of the test drivers. In this experiment, two markers were displayed in the upper left and right corner of the front screen.

Test track The route consisted of a single inner-city straight section with three intersections, which was traversed a total of 27 times (Figure 6.3). This section began and ended with a bend. The first intersection was located directly behind the first curve of each section. Here the subjects had to stop at a traffic light. A straight line of 580 m followed. At the end of the section, the second and third intersection were located at a distance of 120 m. These were traffic light free and the test drivers had right of way at both crossings. A small number of pedestrians walked beside the road on the sidewalk in a random pattern and there were some vehicles coming towards the driver. In their own lane there was a vehicle that was already in front of the test driver at the beginning of the section and waiting at the traffic lights. The test drivers were instructed not to overtake this vehicle. The vehicle normally drove along the

Figure 6.3: Schematic test track. This section was passed through again and again during the test. Only the events were varied.

section at a speed of 45 km/h and turned left at the third intersection. An exception were three passages with critical events, in which the vehicle also braked or stopped on the open road.

Critical Events The front vehicle, which was in its own lane, was used to trigger three critical events. The events were each intended to provoke a rear-end collision, but were slightly different to reduce predictability. In order to reduce the expectation of the test drivers, there were eight trials between each event in which nothing critical happened. The first critical event happened in the 9th trial. While the test drivers in the first eight trials were used to the fact that the front vehicle only turned at the third intersection, it suddenly braked here without a turn signal and turned already at the second intersection. The second critical event occurred in the 18th turn. After the test drivers experienced again several times that the front vehicle turned at the third intersection, it suddenly stopped in this passage in the middle of the straight section between the first two intersections and activated the hazard warning lights. In pass 19 to 26, the front vehicle braked slightly twice on the straight section before the second intersection, but did not stop. The test drivers thus became accustomed to reacting to the light braking. The last critical event followed in the 27th gear. Here, too, the front vehicle braked twice, but stopped completely the second time and activated the hazard warning lights as in the 18th pass (Figure 6.4).

Warnings Two warning systems were investigated. The first warning consisted of a black and white combined display (7.5 x 5.0 cm), which was shown on the display behind the steering wheel, next to the speedometer. It was modelled after a system found in production vehicles and corresponded to it in size and color scheme (Figure 6.5, right). This warning was accompanied during activity by a 2 kHz tone, which was played once for one second at each activation. The second warning consisted of a 126 cm wide and 0.5 cm high red light bar, which was displayed by a LED bar. This bar was placed in front of the driver at the height of the windshield root. Both warnings were activated when the distance to the front vehicle was less than $TH = 0.9$ s and remained active until the minimum distance was restored. Thus the warning was very late, but realistic for a city trip. Since drivers within a city usually drive up close, an earlier warning would have become active very often during normal driving behaviour and would have caused many false alarms. This should be avoided.

Figure 6.4: Schematic test procedure. In every 9th trial a critical event occurred. Trial 9: sudden turn without turn signal. Trial 18 and 27: sudden stop on the road. In all three critical events the front vehicle suddenly reduced its speed. The drivers had to brake quickly to avoid a collision. In trials 19-26, a new expectation was built up by briefly braking the front vehicle before the critical event occurred.

Figure 6.5: The two warning systems studied. The LED warning was displayed over the entire width of the LED bar (left). The combined display was shown in the display behind the steering wheel (right). For better legibility it is shown enlarged again at the edge.

6.2.4 Procedure

At the beginning of the trial, all test drivers agreed to the anonymous processing of the data collected and the possession of driving licenses was checked. They received a written instruction in which the driving task was explained to them. They then sat down in the driving simulator and adjusted the seat so that they could easily reach the pedals and steering wheel as in a normal vehicle. The test drivers were informed that they could stop the test at any time if they notice signs of discomfort or nausea.

Training In simulator experiments, the test drivers may sometimes drop out mostly due to nausea and discomfort. These symptoms, known as »Simulation Sickness«, can be prevented by training (Hoffmann, Krüger, & Buld, 2003). To reduce the risk of dropout in this study, subjects were trained before the trial. Our experience has shown that simulation sickness rarely occurs on straight country roads and often occurs when turning in the city. Therefore, the training route was designed in such a way that the drivers slowly got used to more complex sections of the road. The ride started with a straight country road, which after a few kilometers turned into a track with slight curves. The curvature of the curves increased over the following kilometers. After about 15 min of driving, the test subjects arrived in a city where they drove straight ahead on a priority road. A little later, there were intersections with traffic lights where the test subjects had to stop. The training took about 30 min.

Test drive After the training, the subjects checked their seat once again and care was taken to ensure that they could see both the road and the LED bar clearly and that they were not occluded. The test drivers were then randomly assigned to one of the two test groups and received the corresponding test instructions in writing to rule out any influence of verbal presentation. The driving task and the respective assistance system were explained in the instructions. The task was to drive as accurately as possible 50 km/h, but they were not allowed to overtake moving vehicles. They were also informed that they would be supported by a collision warning system. The system was demonstrated once in a stationary position before the journey. Afterwards the eye tracking system was installed and calibrated. Then the test drivers were left alone in the room, which was darkened except for the simulation, to avoid disturbances by the test supervisor. The simulator drive lasted about 40 min, the total test about 90 min.

6.3 Results

There was no dropout due to nausea during the experiment. All effects are reported as significant from $p < .05$ onward. The variance homogeneity and normal distribution of the data were checked with the Levene Test and the Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test. Only when there was evidence of a violation of the assumptions they are mentioned below.

6.3.1 With which warning did the drivers react better?

Although the warning was given only at a short distance from the vehicle in front, 88 % (»combined display with sound«) and 94 % (»LED-warning without sound«) of the critical events resulted in a warning. Surprisingly, drivers often reacted so quickly to the vehicle in front that they applied the brakes before the warning was even activated: 76 % (»combined display with sound«) or 45 % (»LED-warning without sound«) of the warnings only began after the drivers had already braked. A look at the average distance to the vehicle in front while driving shows that the drivers in the group »combined display with sound« kept a slightly

larger safety distance to the vehicle in front on average (1.2 m). However, this difference was not significant. Since the drivers in the group »LED-Warning without sound« thus drove a little closer behind the vehicle in front, they had a little less time to react in case of a critical event.

Due to the reaction before the warning became active, the majority of the reaction times could therefore not have been accelerated by the warning. It was possible, however, that the reaction of the drivers during the execution was further accelerated by the warning. In this case, the minimum distance to the potential collision object is a better indicator for an effect of the warning. Irrespective of whether the critical events involved faster reactions, more severe braking or longer braking, positive effects of the warning systems can be seen in the minimum distance to the vehicle in front. Therefore, in addition to the reaction time, the minimum distance was also evaluated.

From the three critical events, the mean minimum distance to the front vehicle was calculated for each subject. These distances were then tested for differences between the two groups using a t-test for independent samples. The minimum distance tended to be slightly larger under the »combined display with sound«. However, there was no significant difference to the »LED warning without sound« $t(20) = 1.56, p = .133, r = .33$ (Figure 6.6).

In some cases, the warning was given before the drivers' braking response. It was therefore possible that the warning might have had at least a small influence on the braking reaction. Therefore, the reaction times to the braking front vehicle were averaged over all critical events. A t-test for independent samples showed no significant difference between the conditions $t(20) = .15, p = .886, r = .03$ (Figure 6.7). Thus no difference in the reactions to the warnings could be detected.

Figure 6.6: Minimum distance to braking front vehicle averaged over all critical events by examined group. A larger distance indicates a better reaction.

Figure 6.7: Reaction times to the braking front vehicle averaged over all critical events by examined group.

6.3.2 Which warning was being looked at more frequently?

To check which of the warnings the test drivers looked at more frequently, the gaze behavior was evaluated. For the evaluation, only those looks at the warning were used which the test drivers actively experienced. The evaluation concentrated on the moments when the warning became active. In a previous study it had been shown that the test drivers sometimes looked at the warning only after a peripheral light signal had gone out. In order to capture these glances, the observed interval of warning activity was extended by 2 s after the warning had gone off. The cumulated duration of the gaze as well as the number of glances were considered

separately. In total, the warnings were only rarely looked at when they were active. In both data sets the assumption of normal distribution was violated. Therefore, the evaluation was performed with the parameter-free Mann-Whitney test.

Cumulated gaze duration First, the cumulated gaze duration was evaluated. It gives an overall view of the gaze behavior. While overall there were only few glances towards the displays, drivers looked significantly longer at the »combined display with sound« than at the »LED-warning without sound« $U = 27.5$, $z = -2.43$, $p = .014$, $r = -.52$ (Figure 6.8).

Number of views Since the cumulative duration of gaze does not provide information about whether the test drivers looked at a location very often or only for a very long time, the number of glances was also evaluated. Even with warning activity, drivers looked significantly less often at the »LED warning without sound« than at the »combined display with sound« $U = 29.00$, $z = -2.35$, $p = .028$, $r = -.50$ (Figure 6.9).

Figure 6.8: Cumulated gaze duration for warning only for the warning activity plus two seconds. If the warnings were active, the total viewing duration was longer for the »combined display with sound« than for the »LED-Warning without sound«.

Figure 6.9: Number of views with warning only for the warning activity plus two seconds. If the warnings were active, the »combined display with sound« was viewed more often than the »LED-Warning without sound«.

Proximity of combined display and speedometer In contrast to the »LED warning without sound«, the »combined display with sound« was very close to the speedometer. Thus, if the gaze detection had been inaccurate, it would have been possible in principle that glances at the speedometer would have been mistakenly interpreted as glances for the »combined display with sound«. However, the gaze detection in this experiment was accurate enough to distinguish between the two locations. This is shown in a comparison of the basic gaze frequencies for both warning systems. Looking at the gaze frequencies to the warning, which the test drivers did not experience, one obtains the basic frequency of gaze allocations, which are not due to the warning activity. This should be higher for the »combined display with sound« than for the »LED-warning without sound«, if the proximity to the speedometer should play a role. This was not the case (Figure 6.10).

6.3.3 Which warning was preferred by the test drivers?

Due to the group design, the subjects only experienced the tested system up to this point. To enable them to make a comparison with the system they had not experienced, the test drivers

Figure 6.10: Number of views to the respective warning system, which was inactive in the tested condition, during the whole trip. If the proximity of the »combined display with sound« to the speedometer had an influence on the number of glances, more glances would have been made to this system despite the inactive warning than to the »LED warning without sound«.

were demonstrated the system they had not driven with in a stationary position after each drive. They were then asked to indicate which of the two systems they liked better. In response, 77 % of the subjects responded that they preferred the »LED warning without sound« regardless of the system they had been driving with (Figure 6.11).

Furthermore, the test drivers were asked to imagine how acceptable they would find false alarms of the respective warning if the system could warn them earlier. In this case, the test drivers only evaluated the system they were driving with. In the group »LED-warning without sound« more than twice as many drivers were able to accept false alarms compared to the »combined display without sound« (Figure 6.12).

Figure 6.11: Response frequencies for assessing which system is preferred in each case. All subjects assessed both systems. The LED warning without sound was preferred.

Figure 6.12: Response frequencies on the acceptance of false alarms. In the group »LED-warning without sound« more drivers judged potential false alarms as acceptable (46%) than in the group »combined display with sound« (18%). All test drivers assessed only the system they were driving with.

6.4 Discussion

The aim of this study was to find out whether a Fuzzy Warning in the form of a display via LED bar is looked at less than a currently available symbolic classical display in the combined display. This was the case: The »LED warning without sound« was viewed less frequently than the »combined display with sound«. This result indicates that the LED bar is more likely to be perceived from the periphery.

The result thus complements the findings of Mahlke et al. (2007), who also showed a lower gaze attraction for night vision systems in the scenario of a pedestrian warning on rural roads. In the study presented here, the result could be replicated in the scenario of a rear-end collision warning in urban areas. The assumption of a peripheral perception of the Fuzzy Warning is thus strengthened. The LED bar in the form investigated here thus has a high potential to warn a driver and to distract his attention less from the road than a classic warning.

For this study, however, the statement initially applies only to the gaze attraction. Due to the fast reaction times of the test drivers, it cannot be conclusively clarified here how good the warning effect of the LED bar was compared to the classical warning. In principle, it could also be possible that the LED bar was looked at less, but also had a weaker effect on the reaction time.

Confounding of display form and sound Care must be taken when interpreting the causal factor for the differences in gaze distribution. Due to the confounding visual and acoustic characteristics of the warning systems in this study, it cannot be said with certainty whether the LED warning was viewed less because it was fuzzy or simply because it was presented without a warning sound. The statement about the difference therefore only refers to the systems as tested. This was, as explained in the introduction, intended in this study. The constellation under investigation came about because a unimodal form of the Fuzzy Warning should be compared with a warning that is as realistic as possible. Here, the decision was made in favor of maximizing the external validity against a separate consideration of the influence of different modalities. Further investigations would be necessary to determine whether the effect can be shown in comparison to a purely visual rear-end collision warning in the combined display or a combination of Fuzzy Warning with warning sound. However, the resulting gain in knowledge would be of little practical relevance. Nowadays, a unimodal warning in the combined display would not be used any more due to the weaker warning effect (Diederich & Colonius, 2004; Forster et al., 2002) and with an unimodal Fuzzy Warning comparable reaction times to an acoustic warning can already be achieved (Maier et al., 2010).

LED-Warning without sound is preferred In the subjective evaluation, the »LED warning without sound« was preferred by the drivers and they indicated that they were more forgiving of false alarms. This speaks for an advantage of the Fuzzy Warning. Again, it cannot be said definitively whether this advantage is due to the visual design, the warning sound or a combination of both.

Reactions before the warning When comparing the early reactions of the drivers, it was noticeable that there were differences between the two groups. Drivers from the condition »combined display with sound« reacted more frequently before the warning began. This could be due to the fact that the drivers found this warning so unpleasant because of the sound that they tried harder to prevent the system from being triggered. The assessment of the systems and the slightly larger safety distance in the group »combined display with sound« support this assumption. This is an advantage of the »combined display with sound«, because to avoid accidents, it makes sense for drivers to keep a greater safety distance. However, it is questionable

whether this advantage would also be apparent in reality. During the test, drivers had no way of switching off the warning, but in road traffic, drivers can certainly decide whether or not to use an assistance system. Due to the high traffic density, a rear-end warning can often be triggered in urban traffic. It can therefore be assumed that a rear-end collision warning that is designed too aversively would soon be switched off by the drivers.

Conclusion and Outlook Overall, these results indicate that the LED bar is perceived peripherally and disturbs drivers less than a classic combined display with an acoustic signal. The question remains as to whether the LED bar can have a similar effect on reaction time as a classic warning. Especially interesting is the question whether a unimodal Fuzzy Warning can achieve at least as good response times as a bimodal combined display. The »LED-warning without sound« preferred in this study would prove to be more advantageous in this respect if it leads to a comparable acceleration of the reaction time even without a warning sound. In order to clarify this relationship, a follow-up study was conducted that specifically investigated the reaction times to various fuzzy and a classic symbolic warning system (Chapter 7).

7 Does the driver react faster to a Fuzzy Warning than to a symbolic warning in the combined display?

Summary To find out whether fuzzy warnings have an advantage over symbolic warnings, the response times of a symbolic combi warning and six different fuzzy warnings were compared. The subjects were either distracted by a secondary task or not. The drivers reacted to all fuzzy warnings with a warning tone faster than to the black-and-white combi warning with a warning tone (bimodal vs. bimodal). Reactions to fuzzy warnings without a warning tone were about the same as to the black-and-white combi warning with a warning tone (unimodal vs. bimodal). In addition, the drivers reacted more slowly if they performed a secondary task simultaneously. The fuzzy warnings thus warned equally well under less favorable conditions (unimodal) and even better than a classic symbolic warning under comparable conditions (bimodal).

7.1 Introduction

The fuzzy hazard warning in the form of a LED bar is a new type of assistance system that must prove itself against classical systems if it is to be used in road traffic. The design promises less distraction for drivers and a faster reaction to critical events. In the previous study it could already be shown that the LED bar is looked at less often during warning activity than a warning on the combi display. This indicates a lower distraction in critical situations. The reaction times were also investigated. However, since the drivers in the study often braked before the warning was activated, the results were of limited value. This study is now intended to supplement the findings from Chapter 6 and achieve better reaction time measurement. The focus was on the question of which system can be reacted to most quickly. In order to exclude the disturbing influence of the warning time relative to the critical event, the pure reaction time to the presentation of the warning without critical event was examined in this study. Differences in the reaction times can thus be attributed solely to the displays. The data was collected in a repeated measurement design to allow a more accurate reaction time measurement and to achieve a higher power at the same sample size.

Ideally, warnings only occur in dangerous exceptional situations. This can happen in the vehicle if the driver does not perform the driving task correctly. Such an impairment can be caused by distraction, for example. In this case, a warning should trigger a quick reaction by the driver. In order to take this scenario into account, a secondary task was introduced as a factor which the drivers had to deal with while driving.

In total, four visually different warning systems were investigated to compare different design aspects. The first system consisted of the black-and-white combined warning system that was already used in the previous Chapter and represented the current status of today's assistance systems. This is a classic symbolic warning, which is presented behind the steering wheel in the combination display.

This system was compared with three fuzzy warnings: two LED warnings of different width and one fuzzy warning in the combi display. The length of the LED warning has been varied

in two steps to be able to make a statement whether the size of the LED warning has an influence on the reaction time. Furthermore, a fuzzy combination warning was implemented, which matched the black and white collision warning in size and positioning, but consisted of a completely red display instead of the colorless symbol (Figure 7.2). This stage was included to test whether it is possible to react faster to a fuzzy combination warning than to a classic symbolic combi warning. If a reaction time advantage over a conventional display could be achieved, the implementation of a new display would not really be necessary. A redesign of the display on the already existing display would then be a more cost-effective alternative for vehicle manufacturers and customers.

Previous studies have shown that multimodal warnings lead to faster reaction times (Diederich & Colonius, 2004; Forster et al., 2002). In order to test whether this effect also occurs with the Fuzzy Warning, the presentation of a warning tone was varied with all systems except the black-and-white combination warning. For this warning, the examination of the system without warning tone was again omitted, since it would not be installed today. Thus, the warning tone was not varied as a separate factor and the data was evaluated two-factorially.

Hypothesis In this study it was examined whether it is possible to react faster to different uni- and bimodal fuzzy warnings than to a classical bimodal symbolic warning. Additionally, the effect of distraction by a secondary task was investigated.

7.2 Method

7.2.1 Study Design

In this study, the factors »warning« and »secondary task« were investigated in a 7x2 repeat measurement design (Table 7.1). As a dependent variable, the braking response time to the illumination of the warnings was recorded.

		Secondary Task	
		with	without
Warning	Combi black-white (with sound)	1	2
	Combi red (without sound)	3	4
	Combi red (with sound)	5	6
	LED big (without sound)	7	8
	LED big (with sound)	9	10
	LED small (without sound)	11	12
	LED small (with sound)	13	14

Table 7.1: Schematic experimental design. Seven warning systems were investigated both alone and in combination with a secondary task. All 14 subjects were tested in all 14 conditions.

7.2.2 Sample

In this experiment, 14 subjects (64 % female) aged 19-56 years (median: 22.5 years) participated. Most of the test drivers had experience in using driving simulators. All drivers were in possession of a valid PKW driver's license, which they had held for about five years (median). Most of them were beginners who have driven a total of 27 500 km (median). The test drivers had normal vision or vision corrected to a normal level. For their participation they were paid either with a test person hour or an expense allowance of 10,- Euro.

7.2.3 Material

Driving simulator For this experiment the same driving simulator as from the study in Chapter 6.2.3 was used. The gear shift was set to automatic and therefore did not need to be operated while driving.

Test track In this study only the reaction to the warnings and not to the driving environment was of interest. Therefore, the test track was designed very simple. It consisted of a country road with very little oncoming traffic (one vehicle approximately every 15 s) and no traffic in the own lane. There were no intersections or villages. The route thus put the test drivers in a driving situation without putting too much strain on them. The driving speed was kept constant by instructing the test drivers to drive with the accelerator pedal depressed and limiting the maximum speed to 80 km/h.

Secondary task The secondary task consisted of the Surrogate Reference Task (SURT). This is a visual search task presented on a computer screen that can reliably cause visual and cognitive distraction (Wynn & Richardson, 2008). Subjects were asked to find a target stimulus among several distractor stimuli and to indicate its position on a touch screen by tapping it (Figure 7.1). The touch screen had a size of 20.8 x 16.0 cm. It was mounted on the passenger seat next to the driver in such a way that it could be comfortably operated while driving.

Figure 7.1: Example for a search task of the used SURT (left). The target stimulus, a slightly larger circle, is located in the left field slightly below the vertical center. Subject operates SURT in the simulator (right).

In SURT, the difficulty of the task can be varied by the difference in size between the target stimulus and the distractor stimulus. A distractor size of 4 mm and a target stimulus size of 9 mm were used for the experiment. Thus the task was difficult enough to distract the drivers from the road for a few seconds at a time. The position of the stimuli was determined randomly for each pass. The number of distractor stimuli was constant and was set to 200 for the experiment. The SURT only requires tapping the half of the screen with the target stimulus to capture the response. To increase the distraction effect, the task was made a little more challenging. The subjects were instructed to tap the target stimulus directly.

Furthermore, the SURT offers the possibility to confirm the correctness of the answers via visual feedback (green = correct, red = incorrect). This option was deactivated in this study to avoid interference with the red warnings.

Warnings Seven warning systems were investigated in this study. These consisted of four visually different warning types (Figure 7.2), four of which were examined with and three

without a warning sound. All systems were presented alone without a critical event. The warnings of the conditions »LED big« and »LED small« were presented on the LED bar described in Chapter 6.2.3. The big LED warning had a length of 126 cm, the small one of 45 cm. The small warning was centered in front of the driver, the big one on the whole width of the bar. The dimensions and design of the warnings in the combined display corresponded to a reference system used in real vehicles and had a dimension of 5.0 x 7.5 cm. The warnings and, if applicable, the warning sound were presented for one second during the presentation.

Figure 7.2: The warnings used in this study. The small LED warning was displayed centered in front of the driver. The combined warnings were shown on the combined display behind the steering wheel. They are shown enlarged again on the right. Their dimensions corresponded to a warning actually used in vehicles.

7.2.4 Procedure

At the beginning of the experiment, all test drivers agreed to the anonymous processing of the data collected in the experiment and the test instructions were given in writing in order to rule out any influence of different formulations. Their task was to drive along the test track with the accelerator pedal depressed, to make an emergency stop as soon as possible in the event of a warning, and then to continue driving. The eye tracking system was put on the test driver and calibrated. Before the test started, the test drivers drove a short training session on the test track without warnings but with a secondary task in order to get used to the task. During the training, correct and incorrect answers in the secondary task were visually reported back to the test driver. The test drivers were informed that they could stop the test at any time if they showed signs of discomfort or nausea. The test was started when the subjects indicated that they were familiar with the task.

All warning systems were presented in a stationary position before the drive. For the test drive, the test drivers were left alone in a darkened room to minimize external disturbances. In total there were two test drives of about 12 min duration each. In one condition the test drive was done with, in the other »without secondary task«. The sequence was balanced over the test drivers. The drivers were instructed to pay equal attention to the driving and secondary tasks. This was done to ensure distraction from the secondary task. The different warnings were presented in random order. The viewing direction of the test drivers was observed while driving. In the condition »with secondary task«, a warning was only displayed if the subject was looking at the secondary task. In the condition »without secondary task«, the warnings were only displayed when the drivers were looking at the road. Measurement times in which this was not possible were excluded from the evaluation. This ensured that the warnings were actually displayed with or without visual distraction. Furthermore, the minimum time interval between warnings was at least 20 s. In order to increase the accuracy of measurement, each event was tested four times per subject and the mean value was calculated for the evaluation.

After the test drive the systems were evaluated by the test drivers on a questionnaire. The system to be evaluated was briefly presented to the test drivers in the booth and the test lasted about one hour.

7.3 Results

7.3.1 Data preparation

The latency between the onset of the warning and the application of the brake was measured as the response time. The secondary task led to such a good distraction of the test drivers that almost all measurements could be used. There was no dropout due to nausea during the test. All effects are reported as statistically significant from $p < .05$ onwards. Since the variance between subjects can be ignored in repeat measurement designs (Loftus & Masson, 1994), error bars for repeat measurement designs are shown corrected in all graphs. In all evaluations where it was appropriate, the assumption of normal distribution of the data was checked with the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test. In the following, it is only reported whether there were indications of violation of the assumption. In cases where an analysis of variance was calculated and variance homogeneity was violated, the effects are reported corrected according to Greenhouse Geisser (Greenhouse & Geisser, 1959). For easier reading only the p-values are corrected and the degrees of freedom and F-values are reported uncorrected. Furthermore, the post-hoc contrasts Bonferroni calculated for variance analyses were corrected to counteract alpha error accumulation.

7.3.2 Which of the warnings was responded to most quickly?

There was no evidence of a violation of the assumption for a normal distribution in the response times. Therefore, they were evaluated by means of a variance analysis for repeated measurements. with the factors »warning« and »secondary task«. For a clearer presentation, the test statistics of the analysis of variance are reported in tabular form collected in Table 7.2. Significant Mauchly tests for the factor »warning« $\chi(20) = 42.46$, $p = .003$, $\varepsilon = .45$ and the interaction »warning« and »secondary task« $\chi(20) = 34.72$, $p = .026$, $\varepsilon = .49$ indicated that a variance homogeneity between the factor levels could not be assumed. There was no significant interaction effect between »warning« and »secondary task«, but a significant main effect was shown for the »warning« (Figure 7.3). Contrasts showed that the warnings »Combi red (with sound)«, »LED small (with sound)« and »LED big (with sound)« were responded to significantly faster than the black-and-white combined warning with sound. There was also a significant main effect for the »Secondary task«, (Figure 7.4). Drivers responded more quickly to the warning if they were driving »without a secondary task«.

Effect	Result
Interaction effect »Warning« and »Secondary Task«	n.s.
Main effect »Warning«	$F(6,78) = 4.11$, $p = .016$
Contrast »Combi red (with Sound)« to »Combi bw (with sound)«	$F(1,13) = 6.01$, $p = .029$, $r = .56$
Contrast »LED small (with sound)« to »Combi bw (with sound)«	$F(1,13) = 7.89$, $p = .015$, $r = .61$
Contrast »LED big (with sound)« to »Combi bw (with sound)«	$F(1,13) = 18.69$, $p = .001$, $r = .77$
Main effect »Secondary task«	$F(1,13) = 55.74$, $p < .001$, $r = .90$

Table 7.2: Overview of the test results of the analysis of variance for comparisons between the response times of the factors »warning« and »secondary task«.

Figure 7.3: Response times to all tested warnings. The drivers reacted differently fast to the different systems.

Figure 7.4: Response times to all tested warnings divided by secondary task. Without secondary task the drivers reacted faster to the warnings.

7.3.3 Was there a sign of an effect of the warning sound?

The warning tone was not systematically varied in this study. However, since all warnings were tested with and without a warning tone except for the system »Combi black and white«, the location of the data can be considered at least descriptively in order to formulate a hypothesis about an effect. Drivers tended to react somewhat faster to all warnings with a warning tone than to the same warnings without a tone (Figure 7.5). This indicates a main effect of the sound, which could be specifically tested again in a future study.

Figure 7.5: Response times to all tested warnings. The tone was not systematically varied in all conditions, but seems to have accelerated the response times. The effect of the secondary task on the reaction time is also clearly visible.

7.3.4 How were the systems evaluated?

In addition to the response time to the warnings, the subjects were also asked about each system after the test, how high their acceptance of false alarms was and how much they liked the system overall. For a clearer presentation, the test statistics of the analysis of variance

are also reported here in tabular form collected in the tables 7.3 and 7.4. A review of the distribution of system scores and acceptance of false alarms indicated that the data were approximately normally distributed. With one exception, this assumption was not challenged by non-significant Kolmogorov-Smirnov tests for the distributions of the individual warning conditions. The analysis of variance is robust to violations of the normal distribution assumption for the same group size. Therefore, the judgments were evaluated with an analysis of variance for repeated measurements with the factor »warning«.

Which system was most popular? A significant Mauchly test for the factor »warning« indicated that variance homogeneity could not be assumed $\chi(20) = 39.22, p = .008, \varepsilon = .46$. There was a significant main effect for the »warning«. Contrasts showed that the displays »Combi red (with sound)«, and »LED big (with sound)« were judged significantly more positive and »Combi red (without sound)« significantly more negative than the display »Combi black and white (with sound)«. The systems »Combi red« and »LED big« each with a warning tone were judged most positive (Figure 7.6).

Effect	Result
Main effect »Warning«	$F(6,78) = 6.17, p = .002$
Contrast »Combi red (with Sound)« to »Combi black-white (with sound)«	$F(1,13) = 5.96, p = .030, r = .56$
Contrast »LED big (with Sound)« to »Combi black-white (with Sound)«	$F(1,13) = 5.52, p = .035, r = .55$
Contrast »Combi red (without Sound)« to »Combi black-white (with Sound)«	$F(1,13) = 11.99, p = .004, r = .69$

Table 7.3: Overview of the test results of the analysis of variance for comparisons between the popularity ratings of the systems under investigation.

How acceptable are false alarms Again, a significant mauchly test for the factor »warning« indicated that variance homogeneity could not be assumed $\chi(20) = 50.95, p < .001, \varepsilon = .42$. There was a significant main effect for the »warning«. Contrasts showed that drivers rated possible false alarms of the warnings »Combi red (without sound)«, »LED big (without sound)« and »LED small (without sound)« significantly more forgiving than those of the »black-and-white combination warning (with sound)« (Figure 7.7).

Effect	Result
Main effect »Warning«	$F(6,78) = 4.56, p = .012$
Contrast »Combi red (without sound)« to »Combi black-white (with sound)«	$F(1,13) = 16.89, p = .001, r = .76$
Contrast »LED big (without sound)« to »Combi black-white (with sound)«	$F(1,13) = 4.71, p = .049, r = .52$
Contrast »LED small (without sound)« to »Combi black-white (with sound)«	$F(1,13) = 6.25, p = .027, r = .57$

Table 7.4: Overview of the test results of the analysis of variance for comparisons between the acceptance of false triggers of the examined systems.

7.4 Discussion

The main goal of the study was to find out whether it is possible to react faster to various fuzzy warnings than to a classic symbolic warning. Indeed, a difference was found. The bimodal fuzzy

Figure 7.6: Averaged information on the evaluation of the examined warnings. The systems with a warning tone tended to be assessed more positively than the systems without a warning tone.

Figure 7.7: Averaged information on the acceptance of false alarms of the examined warnings. False alarms from systems without sound were tended to be more acceptable than from systems with sound.

warnings were significantly faster than the bimodal symbolic warnings. This means that under the same conditions, the fuzzy warnings could be reacted faster to. Even if the fuzzy warnings were presented without a warning sound, the reaction was still comparable to the reaction to the symbolic warning with a warning sound. This indicates that reaction times to critical road traffic events can be accelerated by a fuzzy warning compared to conventional systems.

No significant difference was found between the fuzzy warnings tested. Thus, none of the systems was particularly superior to the others. The large-area presentation on the LED bar thus had no significant advantage over the small presentation in the area directly in front of the driver. Furthermore, the results indicate that a new type of display such as the LED bar is not necessarily required to achieve a reaction acceleration. They show that in previously used display locations, the introduction of a fuzzy warning produces similar positive effects. The positive effect of the fuzzy presentation on the reaction time could therefore be achieved here with little effort by means already available.

However, both results are initially only valid for the driving simulation carried out here. A replication of the results in the field is necessary to check whether these effects can be shown in reality.

Why was the response to the fuzzy warnings faster? The question remains, why exactly the subjects reacted faster to the fuzzy warnings than to the symbolic warning under the same conditions. The sound was present here in all conditions and can therefore be excluded as the cause. Otherwise, the displays differed in several factors. Based on the findings of basic research on human visual processing (Chapter 2), the display size, the color scheme and the distance to the focus of the gaze probably had an influence on the reaction time. Previous results on visual attention show that signals can be responded to more quickly if they are presented in a large (Duncan & Humphreys, 1989), conspicuous (Theeuwes, 1992) and close to the eye focus (Trösterer et al., 2010). The focus was either on the road or on the secondary task to the right of the driver. Due to the positioning of the systems, the warnings differed in their distance to the visual focus more intensively when looking at the secondary task than when looking at the road.

The two LED warnings were close to the eye focus and were colored, giving them two advantages over the black and white combination warning in the areas of color and distance. The big LED warning also had a larger warning area. The red combi-warning was in the same

location as the black and white one. It differed only in the colored design and a slightly larger area. Since the reaction time was already significantly faster here than with the black and white system, the factors color and display size probably had a strong influence on the reaction time. However, due to the confounding of the various factors in this study, no final statement can be made. It would be interesting to clarify in future studies exactly which factors are at work here and how strong their respective influence is.

Reference to system differences only under secondary task The secondary task led to slower response times to the warnings. This shows that the subjects' reaction was significantly impaired by the distraction. However, no significant interaction effect between »warning« and »secondary task« could be found. Thus, there were no warnings from which the drivers would have particularly benefited in case of distraction.

Multimodal warnings also favor fuzzy warnings Although the sound factor was not varied completely in this study, the results indicate an effect of the warning sound. On average, drivers in this sample responded more quickly to a visual warning presented with sound. This suggests that a fuzzy warning benefits from a warning sound. This observation fits in with previous findings which show that multimodal warnings can generally be responded to more quickly than unimodal (Diederich & Colonius, 2004; Forster et al., 2002; Maier et al., 2011).

System evaluation The subjective judgements of the subjects show that the drivers in this study prefer warnings with a warning sound. This result is surprising, since in the previous study (Chapter 6) the system with warning sound was assessed more negatively. The reason for this difference could be the nature of the task. In this study, subjects were asked to respond to the warnings as quickly as possible. This seems to be easier if this is accompanied by a warning tone. A slower reaction could be perceived as an error and therefore be evaluated negatively. The situation in the previous study differs in that the subjects were asked to drive normally in traffic. There, the warning was only an aid. In the critical situations, many subjects reacted before the warning was activated and probably felt disturbed by the sound, as this did not represent the event to which they had to react.

Is a fuzzy combination warning sufficient? The fuzzy warnings led to the fastest response times and overall performed well compared to the symbolic warning. Especially interesting is that the fuzzy warning in the classic combined display led to similar effects as the fuzzy LED warnings. To speed up driver reactions, the combined display could also be used for fuzzy warnings in the future. This would be more cost-effective than installing a new LED strip in the vehicle. However, this would inevitably result in a mixing of the new fuzzy warning with previous symbolic information on the same display and it is still completely unknown whether the different messages will interfere with each other. Maier et al. (2011) assume that drivers are more likely to be confused by the non-uniform use of warning signals. A new display, which is only used for one function, may even be useful in this case. Another advantage is that the LED bar is wider and therefore better able to display a directional warning. Due to the width, a signal can actually be displayed in the direction of a hazard, whereas a directional indication in the combined display is only possible by text or arrows. Both the effect of directional warnings and the combination of several warning messages within one display thus represent two new important topics that should be investigated for the Fuzzy Warning. Do drivers really get confused by a combination of different warnings within one display? Can the LED bar really indicate the direction of danger? To answer these questions, a double study was conducted. This will be presented in the next two chapters.

8 Can the gaze be guided with the Fuzzy Warning?

Summary Due to the small display, directing the gaze is only possible to a limited extent with previous displays in PKW. A fuzzy warning in the form of a LED bar can have an advantage over classic displays here due to its width and proximity to the visible environment. In this study, an attempt was therefore made to direct the test drivers' gaze to a pedestrian suddenly crossing the road. A two-stage warning system alerted the drivers to the hazard. The drivers were distracted by a secondary task. In total, three systems were compared: a directional pre-warning with an undirected main warning, only an undirected main warning and a control condition without warning. The results indicate a positive effect with increasing warning level on the collision speed and a slight visual guidance could be achieved. With directional warning, a pedestrian approaching the road was looked at more frequently.

8.1 Introduction

In this thesis it could already be shown that the LED bar is clearly visible (Chapter 4), is intuitively understood (Chapter 5), is less viewed (Chapter 6) and leads to faster reaction times (Chapter 7) compared to a classical warning system. It can therefore be stated that a LED bar is at least as good at warning as a classic display, but the bar distracts the driver's attention less from the road.

Another area in which the LED bar could be superior to existing display concepts is more effective eye guidance. It is known from basic research that attention can be directed specifically by light signals (Lambert et al., 1987; Remington et al., 1992; Irwin et al., 2000). This effect is usually studied in terms of reaction times to a target stimulus, which is announced by a hint pointing in the right or wrong direction. The reaction times accelerate with a correct and slow down with a wrong direction hint. This test setup is similar to a driving situation in which the driver has to react to a hazard (target stimulus) and is supported by an assistance system (hint). The effect should therefore also be able to be demonstrated in the automotive context. Due to the very small display areas, a directional warning in the combi, head-up or multimedia display is limited to directional symbols such as arrows. Due to the greater width of the LED bar, a warning can be dynamically presented to the left or right of the driver and thus actually displayed in the direction of a hazard. Stimuli presented in target direction have the advantage that they allow a faster response to the target stimuli than if only a central hint stimulus is displayed (Remington, 1978). The LED bar thus has the potential to direct the driver's gaze more precisely than is possible with classic displays. However, it is not yet clear whether this actually works.

If gaze directing can be achieved with the LED bar, this would offer great potential for avoiding crashes in which drivers overlooked another road user. Crashes in which lack of perception plays a role account for 38.2 % of serious crashes (Briest & Vollrath, 2006). There are situations in which drivers, under excellent visibility conditions, may look towards the hazard and still overlook it. This "Looked-but-failed-to-see" phenomenon is particularly observed at intersections where entering PKW repeatedly overlook cyclists with right of way (Herslund &

Jørgensen, 2003). Assistance systems that support the driver in his perception and inform him about relevant hazards can help to avoid these kind of crashes.

The evaluation of the display should be carried out on a scenario in which many crashes still happen and therefore there is a high potential for driver assistance. Inner-city crashes involving pedestrians represent such an area. Half of all road crash victims worldwide are pedestrians, cyclists and motorcyclists (World Health Organization, Juni 2009). In the EU alone, 20.4 % of all traffic crashes occur with pedestrians (European Commission, 2010b). One reason for this is that drivers misjudge situations, since 16 % of all pedestrian crashes are associated with driver errors of judgement or information (European Commission, 2010b). But on the other hand, pedestrians themselves are also responsible. It is estimated that illegally crossing pedestrians are involved in 58 % of crashes at intersections (King, Soole, & Ghafourian, 2009). A warning system that gives drivers early warning of an unexpected pedestrian crossing can help to reduce the frequency of crashes in this area. Therefore, for this study an inner-city street was chosen as the scenario in which a warning is issued to warn of a collision with a pedestrian. The dangerous situation that was warned of consisted of a pedestrian suddenly running onto the street, which was occluded until shortly before entering the street. In order not to endanger any test participant, this test was carried out in the driving simulator.

Mahlke et al. (2007) already investigated the eye movements of test drivers during night-time driving on country roads in dependence on different night vision systems. In the investigation, evidence was already found that the fuzzy warning was used more to detect pedestrians at the roadside than video-based night vision systems. However, in the study the direction of vision on the road was not evaluated in a differentiated way, but a gaze turning towards the system with subsequent correct identification of the pedestrian was used as an indicator. Whether or not the gaze of the test drivers was actually directed or not can therefore not be deduced from these results. Furthermore, the results found by Mahlke et al. (2007) only apply to driving in darkness.

This study examined whether the driver's gaze can be directed with the Fuzzy Warning in daylight conditions. In order to measure the effect of directing the gaze, this study therefore measured the actual direction of gaze through the windshield in three different stages (left, road, right) depending on the warning. In addition, drivers were distracted in this study and their vision was partially restricted by obstacles at the roadside to make it difficult to see pedestrians in daylight.

In contrast to the study of Mahlke et al. (2007), a critical crash scenario was examined here. Therefore, beyond the eye movement, the driver reaction could also be investigated. Independently of the eye movements, it was therefore possible to simultaneously record whether the warnings contributed to an improvement in reaction time. Due to the decision to use a critical event, it did not make sense to reuse the system of Mahlke et al. (2007) unchanged. It would not have been noticeable enough for the urgency of the reaction. Therefore, it was decided to use a two-stage warning, as Maier et al. (2011) did. They divided their system into a pre-warning, which indicated possible collisions at an early stage, and a later main warning, which warned of an imminent collision. In the study of Maier et al. (2011) the directed warning was in the first stage and the second stage consisted of an undirected but larger warning. Although the pre-warning was early, it was also less reliable. False alarms were more frequent.

In the study presented here, this design was chosen to achieve a realistic system representation. Vehicle sensors available today can detect potential hazards at a very early stage. However, it is only very shortly before a crash that they are able to determine with sufficient certainty whether or not a collision will actually occur. The two-stage warning is an adaptation to these conditions. It has the advantage of both indicating hazards at an early stage with minimal intrusiveness and, if the situation worsens, drawing attention to the necessary intervention. The directional warning was realized by a red light bar shifted to the left or right of the driver.

Due to the asymmetrical position of the driver in the vehicle, a warning presented centrally in front of him is displayed to the left of the vehicle center. In countries with right-hand traffic, this means that there is more space available to the right of the driver than to the left for a directional warning via the LED bar. In order not to give any side an advantage in this study, the entire width of the light strip was therefore not used.

Hypothesis This study investigated the question of whether a directional warning via the LED bar can be used to direct the attention of distracted drivers to the hazard. In addition, it was investigated whether the reaction of drivers is improved by the directed pre-warning or undirected main warning.

8.2 Method

8.2.1 Test Design

In this experiment, the effect of a LED warning on driving behavior was investigated. The factor »warning« was varied in the three levels »without warning«, »main warning« and »pre- and main warning« in the group design. As dependent variables, eye movements, speed reduction and the subjectively perceived eye guidance of the systems were measured. The group design was used to eliminate the expected strong learning effects after a single confrontation with the critical event.

8.2.2 Sample

36 subjects (47 % female) aged 19-55 years participated in the study. The median age was 23 years. All participants were in possession of a valid driver's license at the time of the study, which they had held on average for 5 years. Most of them were students of the TU-Braunschweig, who had an average total mileage of 60 000 km. All subjects had normal vision or vision corrected to normal level. In return for their participation, the test drivers received either VP hours needed for their studies or an expense allowance of 10,- Euro per hour.

8.2.3 Material

Driving Simulator and Gaze Detection The same driving simulator and the same eye tracking system as in the study in Chapter 6.2.3 was used in this experiment. The field of view was divided for gaze data evaluation (Figure 8.1). With the system used, the accuracy of gaze acquisition decreases the further the fixed point is located in the periphery. In order to compensate for the slight inaccuracies, the active areas were chosen more generously here. During a gaze jump between two areas, it may happen that a gaze is briefly registered in an area between them. For example, a gaze jump between »Tacho« and »Street« may result in a brief glance at the LED bar. Usually there is no conscious look at the LED bar, but the gaze jumps over the area. To avoid artifacts caused by this crossover, glances of less than 200 ms were excluded from the evaluation.

Trial The test drive took place on an inner-city route with seven identical sections. Each section began with a curve followed by a junction. Afterwards a straight road was driven along. At the end of the section, there were two more crossings and a final bend, which seamlessly merged into the next section. There was no traffic on the route, but some cars were parked at the side of the road in parking bays, which limited the view to the sidewalk. In addition, pedestrians walked on the sidewalks. Just after the first intersection, there was a large parking

Figure 8.1: The field of view of the test drivers was divided into six areas for the gaze evaluation. The reddish appearance of the displays is due to the fact that the eye camera works without infrared filter. This red cast was not visible for the test drivers. The reddish markers only shone in the infrared range and were not visible in the test.

lot on the right side of the road. It was constructed in such a way that parked cars and a truck severely restricted the view of the parking lot.

Figure 8.2: Overview of the sequence with relevant events. In the sections five to seven there was a pedestrian approaching the street, but only in the seventh section he ran onto the street to provoke a braking reaction.

The first four sections of the track were intended to give the test drivers the opportunity to get used to the secondary task and the simulator drive. In the last three sections of the route, the drivers were then confronted with three events (Figure 8.2). In sections five and six the drivers were confronted with two potentially dangerous situations. In each case, one of the pedestrians walking along the roadside approached the road slowly from the right (section 5) or quickly from the left (section 6), but stopped in time. For the drivers it was not obvious at first glance whether the pedestrian would cross the road or not. In addition, the pedestrians were not particularly conspicuous and it was possible to overlook them. Since there was only a potential hazard in both cases, that did not escalate, there was only a warning in the form of the first warning level for the »pre- and main warning« group. This was to check whether the driver's gaze could be directed to the pedestrians and how the driver would react. Only in the last pass (section 7) were the test drivers surprised by a pedestrian suddenly running onto the road from the right (Figure 8.3). The first two pedestrians walked in places that were clearly visible from the road (section 5 & 6). The last pedestrian who suddenly ran into the street was

heavily obscured by a parked truck and was therefore only visible just before he entered the street (section 7).

Secondary task As a secondary task the SURT already described in Chapter 7.2.3 was used. In order to be able to cause the distraction of the test drivers in a time-specific manner, a fixed interval was used in which the SURT had to be processed. A SURT task was displayed after every 98 m of driving. At an average speed of 50 km/h this corresponded to a driving time of about 7 s. Each new passage was announced by a short tone and the test drivers then had 3 s time to give their answers. The test drivers learned to react to the sound by working on the subtask. The time of the distraction could thus be controlled very precisely.

In order not to tempt the test drivers to postpone the processing of the subtask in favor of observing the road, the subtask was set in such a way that the timing of the first two uncritical pedestrian events fell exactly into a processing pause. Only for the last critical pedestrian event, on the other hand, a maximum distraction was desired. Therefore, the timing of the subtask here fell exactly at the point in time just before the pedestrian approaching the road became visible.

Warning system The warning system consisted of a two-stage hazard warning, which, however, was only completely displayed in the condition »pre- and main warning«. In the condition »Main warning« only the second level was displayed. The pre-warning had the task of alerting the driver to a potential hazard and consisted of a 15 cm wide red bar, which appeared in front of the driver slightly offset in the direction of the hazard (Figure 8.3, left). The main warning had the task of warning the drivers of an imminent crash and prompting them to brake. It consisted of a 45 cm wide red bar, centered in front of the driver and flashing at 4 Hz (Figure 8.3, right). The pre-warning was displayed 2.5 s, the main warning 1.0 s before a possible crash. While the pre-warning was visible for all three pedestrian events, the main warning was only visible for the crossing pedestrian. For the two pedestrians who stopped at the side of the road, the pre-warning went off again after the pedestrians had passed.

Figure 8.3: Non critical event in which a pedestrian runs to the side of the road and stops (left) The LED bar shows the pre-warning here. Critical event in which a pedestrian suddenly runs in front of the driver onto the road (right). The LED bar shows here the main warning.

8.2.4 Procedure

The test drivers were welcomed and their driving licenses were checked. All test drivers gave their consent to the anonymous processing of the data collected in the trial and filled out a

demographic questionnaire. Then they were randomly assigned to one of the three conditions by a dice roll. Each respondent adjusted the driver's seat in the simulator so that the road was clearly visible and the LED bar was not covered. They were then fitted with the eye-tracking system that was then being calibrated. The experimental instructions were given in writing in order to exclude influences of the experimenter in the wording. The subjects were informed that they could stop the test at any time if they showed signs of discomfort or nausea. They were instructed not to drive faster than 50 km/h due to driving within an urban area. If the speed differed more than 10 km/h from 50 km/h, the test drivers were automatically reminded by a recorded voice to adjust their speed.

In order not to draw the attention of the test drivers to the pedestrians right from the start, the participants from the groups with a warning were informed that they would be supported by a warning system while driving, which would alert them to possible collisions. The warning was then demonstrated to them using the example of a rear-end collision scenario. The drivers were also instructed to continuously perform the secondary task while driving when the sound was heard. To minimize disturbing influences, the drivers were alone in the darkened simulator room during the test. The door was closed for the duration of the test. Then the test drive was started. The data collection took about 8 min. At the end the test drivers filled out a system questionnaire, were compensated for their participation and were given a final farewell.

8.3 Results

All effects are reported to be significant from $p < .05$ onwards. In general, the secondary task resulted in a good distraction. Almost all subjects looked away from the road at the time of the critical event.

8.3.1 Did the LED warning direct the gaze towards the hazard?

8.3.2 Eye movements at potential hazard

In sections 5 and 6 the drivers were confronted with two pedestrians approaching the road, but they stopped at the side of the road in time. However, the drivers could not know this beforehand. It was therefore expected that the drivers would pay more attention to the two pedestrians. This can be operationalized by an increased frequency or a longer period of observation. In order to check whether the directed pre-warning directed the gaze towards the pedestrian, differences in cumulative gaze duration, number of glances and average gaze duration were tested.

Since these were two uncritical events, only the pre-warning of the group »pre-warning and main warning« became active. The other two groups did not experience any warning here. For this reason only the group »pre-warning and main warning« was compared with the group »without warning«. The interval between the earliest warning time ($TTC = 2.5$ s) and the passing of the pedestrian was considered.

In all comparisons, the assumption of normal distribution of the data was checked visually as well as with the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test. If there was evidence of a violation of the normal distribution assumption, the two groups were compared with each other using the Mann-Whitney test. Otherwise, a t-test was used for independent samples. In both sections, where pedestrians approached the side of the road and stopped in time, there was only a significant difference in gaze behavior. In section 5, drivers looked significantly more frequently at the pedestrian approaching slowly from the right when driving with a pre-warning $U = 40.0$, $z = -2.0$, $p = .041$, $r = -.58$ (Figure 8.4).

Pedestrian slowly approaches from right and stops

Figure 8.4: Gazes towards pedestrians approaching the street divided by two warning conditions. With a pre-warning, the pedestrian was looked at more often than without a warning.

8.3.3 Eye movements during the critical event

During the critical event in section 7, drivers were visually distracted from the road while a pedestrian covered by an obstacle suddenly ran onto the road. In this situation, it was important that the drivers reacted as quickly as possible to prevent a crash or at least reduce its severity. Early detection of the hazard was therefore more important here than the number or duration of the observation. Therefore, the eye reaction time was calculated here. This results from the time difference between when the hazard becomes visible and when looking in the direction of the hazard (right). Cases in which the test drivers already looked in the direction of the hazard when the pedestrian appeared, or no gaze in the direction of the hazard occurred within the time until the pedestrian was passed, were excluded from the evaluation. The number of cases that could be used was about 83 % in all groups and was evenly distributed over all conditions.

The directional cue in the pre-warning was intended to draw the driver's attention to the hazard. Therefore, the group »pre- and main warning« was specifically compared with the group »without warning«. A Kolmogorov-Smirnov test showed no evidence of a violation of the normal distribution assumption, so the two groups were compared with each other using a t-test for independent samples. There was no significant difference between the groups (Figure 8.5).

Figure 8.5: Required time for gaze in direction of hazard after the hazard becomes visible, divided by group. Drivers tend to look in the direction of the hazard a little faster with »pre- and main warning«. However, the difference was not significant.

8.3.4 Was the direction hint understood?

In addition to the objective direction of gaze, the subjective perception of the test drivers was also recorded. After the experiment, the subjects in the »main warning« and »pre- and main warning« groups were asked to assess whether the warning indicated the direction of the hazard. They rated the warnings on a scale from 0 (not at all) to 15 (very strong). The results show that most of the test subjects perceived both warnings as having little directional effect (Figure 8.6). However, the »pre- and main warning« was still considered more directional than the »main warning«.

Figure 8.6: Response frequencies on the effectiveness of the directional reference for the two conditions with warning. Both warning systems were found to be only slightly directional. With pre-warning this impression was somewhat stronger.

8.3.5 Was the LED warning able to improve the drivers' reactions?

In addition to the direction of vision, the test subjects' driving behavior was also evaluated. A look at the pattern of brake pedal activity indicates that both warnings have a positive effect on the drivers' braking behavior (Figure 8.7). Braking with »warning« was earlier and more intensive than »without warning«.

As a general measure for the severity of a potential crash, the reduced speed was considered more closely. This was calculated from the difference between the speed at the earliest warning time (at a TTC of 2.5 s) and the speed at collision with the pedestrian. If the drivers came to a stop in time, the initial speed was considered to be completely reduced.

Significant Levene and Kolmogorov-Smirnov tests indicated that no variance homogeneity or normal distribution of the data could be assumed. Therefore, the distributions of the three groups were compared using the parameter-free Kruskal-Wallis test. There was no significant difference between the warning conditions $H(2)=1.72, p = .423$. A look at the decreased speed box plots shows that the groups differed especially in their variance (Figure 8.8). While the test drivers without warning hardly reduced their speed at all, there were some drivers in the groups with warning who reduced their speed moderately to strongly. The positive effect of the warning thus occurred only in some subjects, but their share increased with increasing warning level.

8.4 Discussion

Weak influence on gaze behavior The aim of this investigation was to find out whether the eyes of car drivers can be directed in a hazard direction with the help of a directed LED

Figure 8.7: Progression of brake pedal activity during critical event as quantile distribution. For each metre of distance, the median and the 25 % and 75 % quantiles of brake pedal activity were calculated for all subjects. The medians of the activity under the different experimental conditions are shown as lines, the quantiles as areas. In this figure the medians are very close to the x-axis and only the upper quantile distributions are visible as areas. The graph is truncated at the end because the data collection was stopped when a subject came to a standstill or the hazard had passed and the data was only drawn as far as data was available from all drivers.

Figure 8.8: Decreased speed when reacting to suddenly crossing pedestrians divided by warning. The more intensive the warning, the more drivers reduced speed.

warning. Of three events investigated, only the pedestrian slowly approaching the road was shown to be steering the driver's gaze. This could mean that the drivers were more uncertain about their future behavior in this event than in the pedestrian approaching the road quickly. The potential hazard of a pedestrian quickly approaching the road is relatively clear, whereas a pedestrian slowly approaching the road is not recognized as an immediate threat. A warning therefore has a lower information content for a pedestrian approaching fast than for a pedestrian approaching slowly. This would explain why a slowly approaching pedestrian has more glances in the direction of hazard. Presumably, the drivers checked the pedestrian's behavior more often in order to be able to assess the hazard better. Thus, the warning had the greatest benefit for the drivers in the unclear situation.

In the last critical event, the drivers were strongly distracted by the secondary task and the pedestrian running onto the road was occluded. They had little time to react. As a result, eye tracking was possibly impaired. Since the pre-warning was designed to be unobtrusive, its intensity was probably not sufficient to direct the eyes of the distracted drivers.

Furthermore, it must be mentioned that the sequence of presentation cannot be excluded as the cause of the effect, since the event of the slowly approaching pedestrian was the first warning event for all test drivers. Only a specific variation of the sequence of events in future studies can clarify this question.

The results found here on the effect of eye tracking can be partly transferred to those of basic research. Although it was possible to achieve directing the gaze by means of a peripheral cue, this was weak and only detectable in one of three events. The subjective answers of the test drivers indicate that the effect was nevertheless sufficient to be perceived subjectively. These statements are consistent with the results of Fricke (2009). She also examined a directed peripheral warning in the form of a LED bar. Only 13.8 % of her test drivers stated that they recognized the directed display as such.

The main reason for the weak effect is probably the lower salience of the directional pre-warning used in this study. In classical perception experiments, only individual cues are varied while the rest of the visual scene remains the same. A situation in a driving simulator differs in that the visual scene as a whole is highly complex and moving. Therefore, a cue stimulus in a laboratory setting is certainly more conspicuous than when the same stimulus is presented in the driving simulator. This would mean that a more conspicuous pre-warning would probably be better able to direct the driver's attention. This could be achieved by animation, brighter display or flashing. In the experiment of Mahlke et al. (2007) the recognition performance of the test drivers was positively influenced by the LED bar. In contrast to this study, their warning was animated and displayed in color in darkness. As a result, their display had a higher salience compared to the one used here.

Another explanation for the low influence of the warning on the viewing direction could be the warning time. Although the 2.5 s used here are quite realistic for a hazard warning in city traffic, they are still relatively short for an appropriate response. It is possible that an earlier warning would be more effective. If this is true, then the directed early warning is particularly suitable for situations where drivers still have enough time to react.

Positive effect on driving response From a pragmatic point of view, it could also be argued that driver gaze control is ultimately irrelevant as long as drivers react better with the help of the warning and if the severity of the crash can be reduced with the help of a warning. For this reason, the braking response of the drivers was investigated in addition to the gaze behavior. The variance of the average reduced speed increased with increasing warning level. This indicates that the warning does not generally improve the reactions of all drivers equally, but that the number of drivers who benefit from it increases. Although the effect on the reduced speed was not significant in this study, this suggests that drivers benefited from an

earlier warning, although they hardly understood the associated directional warning as such. Again, the effect could probably be improved by a more conspicuous warning system or an earlier warning.

Conclusion The expected benefit of the LED bar in directing the driver's gaze was only weakly demonstrated in this study. However, there was evidence of a positive effect of the warning on the reduced speed during a critical event.

9 How do drivers react to fuzzy fog information?

Summary This study investigated how drivers react to fuzzy fog information if they have previously experienced the display as a hazard warning. Drivers were warned of the event 3 s before the occurrence of a fog bank by two flashing yellow lights or a constantly illuminated yellow bar. The lights only flashed for 3 s, the bar remained lit until the fog was passed through. Both systems proved to be effective in reducing the speed at which the fog was passed through. However, the group that experienced the bar experienced dangerous overreactions. This can probably be attributed to the greater similarity of this display to the hazard warning experienced previously.

9.1 Introduction

In previous investigations on fuzzy display the LED bar was mainly used as a warning (Fricke, 2009; Maier et al., 2011). But the display is also suitable as an information system. The two areas of application differ in that a warning system requires an immediate reaction, whereas an information system does not. An Information is used to prepare for action rather than for an immediate reaction. One could also make a temporal distinction. While a warning is usually presented only very shortly before the event, information can often be presented at an early stage. Mahlke et al. (2007) have already investigated the potential of the LED bar as an information display using the example of a night vision system and have been able to show a good effect of the display compared to video-based systems. However, here the drivers were only confronted with the informative system and there was no comparison to a warning system. Still, it is very likely that the display will be used in road traffic for both information and warning purposes. Also classical displays, like the combi-display, are used in many ways for different applications.

When a display is used in combination for more than one purpose, it is important that drivers can immediately tell whether it is a warning or information, because in both cases a wrong reaction can be fatal. If a warning system is wrongly interpreted as information a reaction will be too late. If, on the other hand, an abrupt braking action is taken in response to information, a rear-end collision may be unintentionally provoked.

With previous displays, differentiation is simplified by the symbolic representation of the message. This is not possible via the LED bar. The question arises as to whether a fuzzy display can be designed in such a way that drivers react appropriately to different messages. Möller and Frings (2010) have already been able to show, using the example of symbolic warning signals, that the response to an action-relevant warning was impaired by previous experience with an irrelevant display of similar visual design. It is therefore to be expected that a similar effect will occur with similarly designed fuzzy displays.

In this study, therefore, drivers were confronted with fog information on a freeway trip immediately after they had experienced a collision warning on the same display in a (near) crash with a pedestrian (Chapter 8). Two information systems were tested. While the first had a very high similarity to the collision warning experienced before, the similarity to the second information system was low.

A fog bank was chosen as the hazard zone. In fog, visibility is considerably limited and possible hazards can only be seen late. This shortens the available reaction time if a dangerous situation suddenly occurs. To be able to react quickly enough in an emergency, drivers must reduce their speed. For this reason, the two tested systems should cause drivers to drive more slowly through the fog.

Hypothesis The goal of this study was to find out how drivers react to fog information when they have received a critical warning message shortly before via the same display.

9.2 Method

9.2.1 Test Design

In this study the effect of fog information on driving behavior was investigated. The factor »fog information« with the steps »without system«, »warn blinking« and »bar« in the group design was examined. As dependent variables the brake pedal activity, the driving speed and the evaluation of the systems were recorded.

9.2.2 Sample

This study was conducted immediately following the previous study with the same 36 subjects. The sample is therefore identical to the trial in Chapter 8. In order to prevent the previous experience with the different pedestrian warnings from systematically influencing the effects of the fog information, the groups were divided. Half of the groups with pedestrian warnings were randomly assigned to a group with fog information. The drivers who drove in the preliminary test »without warning« were completely assigned to the group »without system«. The test drivers were remunerated for their participation in the previous study (see Chapter 8.2.2).

9.2.3 Material

Driving simulator Due to the risk of crashes and to be able to control the occurrence of the fog bank, it was decided to conduct this study in a driving simulator. The driving simulator already described in Chapter 6.2.3 was used for this purpose.

Test Track In this experiment, the test drivers drove along a 6 km long stretch of highway with light traffic. The route was constructed in such a way that the test drivers drove into a fog bank after about 2:30 min depending on their speed. The passage of the fog bank took about 30 s and the route ended shortly afterwards.

Information System The fog information used in this study was presented via the LED bar described in Chapter 6.2.3. Its purpose was to alert drivers to the difficult visibility conditions in fog and to encourage them to adjust their speed. Two information systems were designed for this purpose: The information »warn blinking« was based on the light signal of a vehicle with active hazard warning lights. It consisted of two 5 cm wide yellow light bars, which were displayed centered in front of the driver at a distance of 31 cm (Figure 9.1, left). The system »bar« consisted of a 45 cm wide yellow light bar, centered in front of the driver (Figure 9.1, right). Both information were displayed three seconds before the fog became visible. The information »warn blinking« should indicate that you are entering a hazard zone. It was only active for a short time and flashed for a total of three seconds at a frequency of 2 Hz in front of the driver. The information »bar« should indicate that you are entering a hazard zone,

but it should also report the increased hazard level as long as you are in the hazard zone. It was therefore continuously active until the fog bank was passed. While the similarity of the information »bar« to the previously experienced hazard warning was great, the information »warn blinking« differed greatly from it.

The color yellow is often used in road traffic in situations where increased attention is required without immediate hazard (traffic lights, turn signals, right-of-way signs). Red is more likely to be used in critical situations (traffic lights, brake lights, traffic sign surrounds). As the fog information is intended to be a general warning rather than an immediate hazard warning, it was shown in yellow.

Figure 9.1: In this experiment two fog informations were examined. Two yellow flashing lights, which resembled the warning flashing of a vehicle (left) and a yellow bar, which resembled the warning tested in the previous experiment in shape and size (right).

9.2.4 Procedure

As mentioned above, subjects participated in this study immediately after the trial described in Chapter 8. This means that all drivers had just experienced a critical event with a pedestrian suddenly running onto the road. The test drivers from the warning conditions also experienced a red collision warning, which was displayed via the LED bar. At the beginning, the test drivers were told that they would now be driving on a highway. They were instructed to drive as usual and to follow the highway regulations. Since the intuitive reaction to the fog information was to be investigated, the test drivers were not informed that they would drive through a fog bank.

To avoid distractions, the test drivers were left alone in the darkened simulator room during the test and the door was closed for the duration of the test. During the freeway journey, the test drivers did not have to work on any secondary task. The test drive was ended shortly after the fog bank was passed through. The test drivers filled out a short questionnaire and were then bid farewell.

9.3 Results

9.3.1 How did the drivers react to the fog information?

To check whether the fog information had an influence on the driving behavior of the test drivers, the course of the driven speed during the crossing of the fog was compared between

the groups. All test drivers reduced their speed in the fog bank (Figure 9.2). However, this effect was more intense in the subjects who were driving with fog information and also started earlier. It was found that the test subjects from the »bars« group reduced their speed most intensively shortly after the display lit up and also had the lowest average speed while driving through the fog (Figure 9.2).

Figure 9.2: Progress of the driven speed during the fog phase divided into groups. All drivers slowed down their speed at the beginning of the fog or when the warning was faded in. With warning system the reaction was stronger and the drivers with the display »bar« reacted most intensively. Despite the continuing fog, all drivers accelerated again evenly and slowly approached their previous cruising speed.

A closer look at the braking behavior shows that the drivers from the group »bar« reacted most intensively (Figure 9.3). Drivers who were driving with the »warn blinking« only braked once shortly after being informed and again when the fog began (Figure 9.3), while the group »without system« hardly braked at all and for the most part simply rolled into the fog.

Have the drivers overreacted? Looking at the speed profiles of the individual drivers, four drivers suddenly reduced their speed significantly (Figure 9.4). Here, the sudden braking could have led to rear-end collisions. These four drivers were all from the group »bar«. Another driver from the group »warn blinking« reduced his speed by a similar amount, but he braked gradually and thus hardly endangered his successors.

9.3.2 Speed reduction only of short duration

From the speed curves it can be seen that the driver's behavioral adaptation was only of short duration (Figure 9.2). Although drivers from the two groups with displays reduced their speed in the fog, this effect lasted only briefly. After a few seconds, the speed of the drivers returned to the control group.

9.3.3 What message was conveyed by the fog information?

Although the aim of the fog information was to inform the drivers about the fog bank without disturbing them, it was not clear until the test whether this was successful. Therefore the drivers were asked after the trip if they would have liked to switch off the fog information. From the group »warn blinking« 16 % of the drivers said yes, from the group »bar« 42 % of the drivers

Brake pedal activity during fog

Figure 9.3: Progress of brake pedal activity during the fog phase divided into groups. Drivers with a warning system responded to the warning by braking. The reaction to the system »bar« was the most intensive. The »without system« group also responded to the fog bank, but only with light braking. While drivers responded to the »bar« system with even, strong braking, drivers in the »warn blinking« group braked in two stages. Once slightly when the warning appeared and somewhat more intensively when entering the fog.

Speed profile in fog

Figure 9.4: Chart of the driven speed of individual drivers during the fog phase divided into groups. Here you can see that some riders from the group »bar« have reduced their speed considerably after the warning.

said yes. The »bar« information thus had a more disturbing effect on the test subjects. The free answers of the drivers showed that this was probably due to the long presentation time. The drivers of the »bar« information wanted either a shorter warning duration or the possibility to switch off the display at the push of a button.

9.4 Discussion

The goal of this study was to find out how drivers intuitively react to fuzzy fog information when they have just experienced a critical hazard warning on the same display.

The two systems tested caused drivers to slow down their speed in fog and thus move more safely through the hazard zone. With the warning system, the drivers drove through the fog at an average speed of 10.2 km/h slower than without information. So both systems basically reached their goal. However, the system »bar« led to dangerous overreactions in one third of the drivers, which would have endangered the following vehicles in real traffic. This indicates that when using the LED bar, a reaction transmission occurs for both information and warning systems. Presumably, drivers intuitively associated the broad bar of fog information with the collision warning they had just experienced and expected a source of hazard hidden in the fog. The reaction to the information system with high similarity to the previously experienced warning system was stronger than to the one with low similarity. This indicates that the negative effect can be reduced by a different design of the displays.

The results of Möller and Frings (2010) achieved in the laboratory thus seem to be confirmed in the applied driving simulator. It is interesting here that the effect could be observed in reverse order. While Möller and Frings (2010) feared that an early, non-critical preliminary stage of a warning would slow down the reaction to the late warning stage, an indication could be found here that experience with a critical system can lead to overreactions in a non-critical system.

It should be noted, however, that no group was tested in this investigation that had not previously experienced the hazard warning. Therefore, it cannot be conclusively determined whether the overreaction can be attributed to the design of the display itself or its similarity to the previously experienced system.

Furthermore, in this study it was found that the achieved speed adaptation was only of short duration, independent of the experienced system. This indicates that the drivers have a preferred speed that they try to establish. Although the drivers reacted to the systems, the later re-acceleration indicates that the drivers expect an immediate reason for the intervention. The fog itself did not seem to be a sufficient reason. The long-term presentation of the message showed no advantage over a short one and was even perceived as disturbing.

Conclusion While fuzzy fog information can cause a short-term reduction in speed for drivers, too much similarity with a collision warning system is likely to lead to overreactions. Additional research is necessary to clearly show this relationship. But considering the results of Möller and Frings (2010) it seems reasonable to avoid similarity between warning and information systems. A short notification is sufficient. A longer lasting display does not lead to a longer effect and is even perceived as disturbing.

10 Which warns better, a soft or hard warning transition?

Summary While the basic functioning and effectiveness of the Fuzzy Warning has already been investigated in several studies, there is still little research on the optimal design of this display. In particular, the use of animations has not been specifically investigated. Therefore, this study compared an abrupt and a continuous warning transition using a two-stage hazard warning. In addition, the animation direction of the early warning from the driver to the hazard and vice versa was varied in order to test whether the driver's gaze can be directed or the response improved. A continuous warning transition led to better reactions, although it did not itself provide information about the type of reaction required. Furthermore, the animation from hazard to driver led to slower glances in the direction of hazard.

10.1 Introduction

The previous chapters dealt with the prerequisites that must be met for the use of a Fuzzy Warning and showed differences to other systems. However, the effectiveness of such a display depends very much on the way it is implemented. This study therefore went one step further and examined a design aspect of the display.

An assistance system can only determine at a very late stage whether an object is really a hazard source that requires a reaction or not. Warning times of more than two seconds before a crash can therefore rarely be reached without triggering a high number of false alarms. These in turn have the potential to be less accepted by the driver.

Multilevel warnings offer the advantage that an early warning effect can be achieved with low intrusiveness by combining a simple pre-warning with a conspicuous main warning. The pre-warning alerts drivers to potential hazards at an early stage, while the main warning is only activated in an emergency. In principle, this allows the warning to be issued much earlier and helps the driver to avoid a hazard before the situation becomes critical. In this way, traffic crashes in which drivers overlook another road user could be avoided. In fact, in 2011, errors in turning, reversing, entering and starting were the most common cause of accidents with personal injury caused by driver error, accounting for 18.6 % (Statistisches Bundesamt, 2012b). These are actions that happen especially at intersections in the city, and often pedestrians or cross traffic are overlooked.

The effectiveness of two-stage warnings has already been demonstrated. For example, Maier et al. (2011) found that a pre-warning via the LED bar gave drivers more time to react to various hazards. Also in this paper, in Chapter 8 a tendency for a positive effect of a directed pre-warning on the reduction of the impact speed of a suddenly crossing pedestrian was found.

However, since this concept is still quite new, there is little knowledge about the optimal design of a two-stage warning. How should the transition between the two warning levels be designed? Do drivers react more quickly to an abrupt warning transition that has a high salience, or if they are guided smoothly from one warning level to the next? These questions were investigated in this study. It was expected that an abrupt warning transition is more conspicuous and would therefore lead to faster reactions. In addition, an attempt was made to direct the test drivers' attention by animating the display. In Chapter 8, neither a static

directed pre-warning nor a static undirected main warning was understood as particularly directional. Nevertheless, the test drivers judged the directional warning to be more directional than the non-directional one. This indicates that the design plays a role in the effect. A moving light was intended to reinforce the impression of a directional warning. If there is an effect, it should be best shown by two opposing animations. Therefore, in this study the animations of a hazard to the driver and from the driver to the hazard were examined. It was expected that one animation leads the view to the hazard, but the other leads it away from the hazard. To evoke a reaction as well as to vary the viewing direction, an inner-city intersection scenario was chosen. The test subjects repeatedly passed through an intersection and had to react to vehicles that could approach from the left or right.

Since in the previous studies only weak indications of eye movement were found, it was to be expected that possible effects would also be small in this study. In order to be able to show weak effects as well, the experiment was optimized to minimize the measurement error. The study was conducted in a repeat measurement design and each condition was tested four times per subject. In order to ensure the safety of the test drivers and to be able to fully control environmental factors of the test, the test was carried out in a driving simulator.

Hypothesis The aim of this study was to find out if a two-stage hazard warning presented on a LED bar, a continuous or abrupt warning transition leads to a faster response. It was expected that an abrupt warning transition would be reacted to more quickly, since it should be more conspicuous. In addition, it was to be examined whether one of the examined animations could direct the gaze to a hazard more effectively than the others.

10.2 Method

10.2.1 Experimental design

In this study, a 2x2x2 factorial repeated measurement design with the factors »animation direction«, »hazard direction« and »warning transition« was used (Table 10.1). To keep the predictability of the critical event low, the hazard direction and the occurrence of the hazard were varied. The reaction time to intersecting vehicles, the impact speed, the number of faulty reactions during brake and accelerator pedal activity and the gaze behavior were recorded as dependent variables.

		Warning transition			
		continuous		abrupt	
	Direction of hazard	right	left	right	left
Animation direction	from driver to hazard (<->)	1	2	3	4
	from hazard to driver (-><-)	5	6	7	8

Table 10.1: Schematic diagram. All subjects were tested in each of the eight conditions.

10.2.2 Sample

The study involved 30 subjects (60 % female). Most of them were students of the TU-Braunschweig at the age of 18 to 58 years with a median of 21 years. The median for the duration of the possession of a driver's license was four years. The average driving experience was 33 000 km. All test drivers had normal vision or vision corrected to normal level. The

test drivers were paid either 1.5 VP hours, which they needed for their studies, or an expense allowance of 15,- Euro.

10.2.3 Material

Driving Simulator and Gaze Detection The same driving simulator and the same eye tracking system as in the study in Chapter 6.2.3 was used in this experiment. The gear shift was set to automatic and therefore did not need to be operated while driving.

To capture the direction of gaze, the subjects' field of vision was divided into five areas as shown in Chapter 8 (Figure 8.1). Since the views of the crossing vehicle could not be captured directly, the views in the corresponding hazard direction were evaluated as gaze attributions. A later examination of the data confirmed that gazes in the areas »Right« and »Left« could actually be assigned to the approaching vehicle in the period considered for the evaluation. For the evaluation, the view allocations in the areas »Hazard« (side from which the intersecting vehicle was approaching) and »Not Hazard« (the other side) were calculated on the basis of the approach direction and the absolute views according to »Right« and »Left« and used in the further evaluation.

Figure 10.1: The test drivers passed through an intersection several times. The drivers approached the crossing from the left with 60 km/h and crossed it.

Hazard scenario The hazard scenario chosen was an intersection situation that the drivers had to pass through repeatedly (Figure 10.1). Although the drivers had right of way each time, another vehicle could illegally cut their way at the intersection. The route was designed in such a way that a crash occurred here in any case if the drivers did not react to the cutting vehicle by braking. To keep the timing of the individual events the maximum speed of the test drivers was limited to 60 km/h. They were instructed to fully depress the accelerator pedal while driving and to brake only if they were sure that the other vehicle would cut them. The intersection was also designed in such a way that the other vehicle was only visible at a TTC of 3.5 s, and from a TTC of 2 s on, it became apparent whether it would stop in time or cut in (Figure 10.1).

To reduce the predictability of the hazardous situation, five possible events were varied in random order. The vehicle cut in $\frac{2}{5}$ of the cases and stopped just as often in time. In $\frac{1}{5}$ of the cases there was no vehicle. In addition, when a vehicle intersected, it could approach either

from the left or the right. The approach route was identical each time. All intersections had the same structure.

Warning The warning was displayed via a LED bar, which was already described in Chapter 6.2.3. It was positioned in front of the drivers at the level of the lower edge of the imaginary windshield. The bar had a length of 120 cm and was slightly curved to simulate the shape of a windshield root. However, in this study, not the entire width of the strip was used for the warning. A prototypical warning system was designed, which warned the drivers of possible collisions in two warning levels. This consisted of a pre-warning in the form of a 15 cm wide red light bar indicating the direction of a possible source of hazard and a main warning in the form of a 60 cm wide red light bar flashing at 4 Hz (Figure 10.2). The pre-warning was shown at a TTC of 4 s, the main warning at a TTC of 2 s. The timing was chosen so that the pre-warning was visible half a second before the cutting vehicle and the main warning so that the drivers could just avoid an crash if they reacted immediately to the main warning. There were no false triggers of the system and the test drivers were informed that it would work 100 % reliably.

Figure 10.2: LED bar with active pre-warning of hazard from the left (top) and with active main warning (bottom). Both warnings were animated.

The Warning Conditions Four versions of the warning system were designed to investigate the factors warning transition and animation direction. There was one system for all possible combinations of the factor levels. Both »Animation direction« and »Warning transition« varied within the warning.

In an animation from the driver to the hazard (<->) the small red light bar started centered in front of the driver and moved in a flowing movement within 0.2 s over 30 cm in the hazard direction and stopped there. In an animation from the hazard to the driver (-><-) the lightbar started 30 cm left or right to the driver and moved in a flowing movement within 0.2 s over 30 cm and stopped in front of the driver.

There were different possibilities to set the times for the transition between pre-warning and main warning. While the abrupt warning transition is only defined by a single point in time, the continuous warning transition is described by two points in time: Animation start and end. How should the relative timing of both warnings be designed? The timing of the main warning was determined by practical considerations. It should occur when it could be said with a high degree of certainty that a crash would occur. A later warning time was not reasonable, because a later reaction would not have been able to prevent the crash. An earlier main warning was also not appropriate, as it would have been unrealistic to predict a crash with certainty so early. A warning designed in this way would often produce false alarms. It was therefore decided to set the main warning to $TTC = 2$ s.

For the animation of the warning transition there were also two possibilities: Option 1 was to set the start of the animation of the continuous transition to the same value as the start

of the main warning. However, this would shorten the duration of the main warning and reduce the maximum intensity of the warning. In view of the fact that the 2 s before the crash represented the last possibility of intervention to prevent a crash, this option was not considered acceptable. Option 2 was to equate the end of the animation of the continuous warning transition with the beginning of the main warning. A false alarm of the warning transition is not as serious, because it is not as noticeable as the main warning. Therefore it was decided to let the continuous warning transition start 0.4 s before the main warning at a TTC of 2.4 s (Figure 10.3).

Figure 10.3: Time sequence of the used warnings with regard to the size of the display. Although the continuous warning transition (C) occurs earlier than the abrupt one (D), it does not contain any information about whether the crossing vehicle is cutting or not (A,C). The exact display of the flashing frequency of the main warning has been omitted in favour of readability.

Because of this decision, the change started 0.4 s earlier with a continuous warning transition than with an abrupt warning transition. To neutralize this advantage of the one condition, the continuous warning transition was triggered independently of the presence of the hazard and the animation occurred regardless of whether the drivers had to react or not. Since there were passages in which the crossing vehicle stopped in time and those in which it cut the drivers, the test drivers could not conclude from the warning transition whether they had to react or not. Only the main warning provided this information. There were four possible sequences for the warning transition:

- Vehicle stops, warning transition »continuous«: The light bar initially expands, but then shrinks again until it disappears (Figure 10.3, A)
- Vehicle stops, warning transition »abrupt«: The light bar does not expand and disappears again after a short time (Figure 10.3, B).
- Vehicle cuts, warning transition »continuous«: The light bar expands and changes to the flashing main warning (Figure 10.3, C).
- Vehicle cuts, warning transition »abrupt«: The light bar does not expand and changes directly to the flashing main warning (Figure 10.3, D).

10.2.4 Procedure

All test drivers agreed to the anonymous processing of the data collected in the trial and their possession of driving licenses was checked. They were then shown the driving simulator and explained how to use it. The test drivers adjusted the driver's seat in such a way that they could see the virtual road well and the LED bar was not covered by the steering wheel. Afterwards, demographic data was collected by means of a questionnaire via touch screen. The touch screen was mounted on the passenger seat next to the drivers. To avoid influences of the test coordinator in the execution, the driving task was given to the test drivers in writing. The test subjects were informed that they could stop the test at any time if they showed signs of discomfort or nausea. In order to accustom the test drivers to the driving situation, training on a test track followed. This corresponded to the structure of the later test track, but the test drivers drove here without any hazard warning. During the training, the test drivers had the task of assessing whether a vehicle would cut them or not. The training lasted until five situations in a row were correctly assessed and the reaction time for five critical events in a row did not improve further. Preliminary tests showed that hardly any learning effects occurred with this criterion. After the training, the test drivers were fitted with the eye tracker and calibrated. The first system was then demonstrated in a stationary position and the test drive followed. In order to avoid interferences, the test drivers were left alone in the test room for data collection and the door was closed. The room was darkened except for the light sources of the simulation environment. A test drive lasted about 5 min.

After the first condition was completed, the next system was demonstrated in the booth and the test driver was left alone again for data collection. In total, the test subjects completed five conditions, four with the system and one without. To control position effects, the sequences of the conditions were determined according to the Latin Square method and randomly assigned to the test subjects. Within a condition, the test drivers drove through five types of events in which the behavior of the vehicle (without, stops, cuts) and the direction of hazard (left, right) were varied. Each event type was tested four times. The test drivers thus performed a total of 20 events per condition. The total test lasted about 1.5 hours.

10.3 Results

10.3.1 Data preparation

Of the 30 subjects tested, two were excluded from the evaluation of gaze data. The gaze data of one of the test drivers was lost due to a technical error. Another test driver looked straight ahead the whole time during the test drives. Due to the lack of variance in the eye movements, an evaluation was not reasonable here. In order to reduce the measurement error, all reaction times per subject and condition were recorded four times and the mean values were used for the evaluation. All effects are reported as significant from $p < .05$ on. Since the variance between the test subjects can be ignored in repeat measurement designs (Loftus & Masson, 1994), error bars for repeat measurement designs are displayed corrected in all plots. In order to compare the reactions to critical events between warning conditions, only those events where a warning occurred are considered. This excludes the events where the crossing vehicle stopped, where there was no vehicle and passages without warning system. In all evaluations where it was appropriate, the assumption of normal distribution of data was checked with the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test. In the following, this will be reported only when there were indications that the assumption was violated.

10.3.2 Do drivers react faster to a soft or hard warning transition?

The major question of the experiment was whether a »continuous« or »abrupt« warning transition between the two warning levels allowed a faster response to the hazard. Besides main effects, it was also of interest whether there were interactions with the hazard direction or the animation direction. Therefore, the mean reaction times and impact speeds on the intersecting vehicle were evaluated with a three-factorial variance analysis for repeated measurements. The factors considered were »warning transition«, »animation direction« and »hazard direction« (Table 10.1). The reaction time was calculated from the difference between the time at which the intention of the approaching vehicle could be detected ($TTC = 2$ s) and the time at which the brake was applied or the hazard was over ($TTC = 0$ s). There was a significant main effect in the reaction time for the warning transition $F(1,29)=17.68$. A »continuous« transition was responded to significantly faster than a »abrupt« transition $p < .001$, $r = .62$ (Figure 10.4). There were otherwise neither significant main nor interaction effects in the reaction time.

Figure 10.4: Average reaction time to cutting vehicle in seconds, divided by warning transition. With continuous warning transition the reaction time was faster.

This unexpected result raises the question of whether the test drivers simply already reacted to the animation during the »continuous« warning transition, regardless of the fact that the animation did not inform about the behavior of the crossing vehicle. Whether this was the case could be determined from the faulty braking (driver brakes although intersecting vehicle does not cut). If the drivers simply reacted blindly to the growing, contrary to their instructions, the test drivers with »continuous« warning transition should show more false braking than those with »abrupted« warning transition. This is not the case for braking reactions (Figure 10.5). However, if we look at how often the test subjects stepped off the accelerator even though the vehicle stopped in time and they ultimately did not have to react, there was a tendency for drivers under the »continuous« warning transition to step off the accelerator too early (Figure 10.6).

The better response of the test drivers during »continuous« warning transition was also shown in the impact velocity $F(1,29)=6.94$. A »continuous« warning transition was accompanied by a significantly lower impact velocity $p = .013$, $r = .44$ (Figure 10.7). Also for the impact speed there were no other significant interaction or main effects.

10.3.3 Where did the drivers look during the warning?

For the evaluation of the gaze data, only the intervals of intersection events in which a crossing vehicle was involved were considered. This was done to ensure that only data in which the warning was active was included in the analysis. The considered time period started with the

Figure 10.5: Incorrect braking on an approaching vehicle that stopped in time. Divided into »warning transition«, »animation« and »hazard direction«. Animation from driver to hazard: <->, Animation from hazard to driver: -><-. In all warning groups the number was about the same.

Figure 10.6: Events in which the accelerator was released although the approaching vehicle stopped in time. Divided into »warning transition«, »animation« and »hazard direction«. Animation from driver to hazard: <->, Animation from hazard to driver: -><-. With continuous warning, the throttle was released a little more often, although it was not necessary. Without the support of a warning system this happened most often.

Figure 10.7: Average impact speeds divided according to »warning transition«. Avoided collisions were included in the evaluation as »0«. With continuous warning transition, the impact speed was lower on average.

Figure 10.8: Average duration until first glance at the »hazard direction« divided according to »animation direction«. The view direction in animation from hazard to driver was slightly slower than in animation from driver to hazard or in the control condition.

moment the warning became active (TTC = 4 s) and ended with the moment the possible crash site was passed (TTC = 0).

In order to be able to follow the eye movements of the test drivers, eye movement plots were created for all conditions. On these plots the gaze distribution over all test drivers is averaged over time. The more test drivers have looked at a location at a time, the redder the section is shown. On the x-axis the time is given as a second interval to the possible crash. The times of the »pre-warning«, »main warning« and »crash« relevant for this experiment are additionally marked on the X-axes.

A first look at the eye movements shows that in systems with »abrupt« warning transition and in the animation »from driver to hazard« (<->) more test drivers looked towards the hazard than in the other condition. This can be seen by a more intensive reddish coloration on the area »hazard« approximately at TTC = 3 s (Figure 10.9). A correspondingly more intense blue coloration at the same time in the »road« area indicates that the more frequent glances of hazard were averted from the road (Figure 10.9).

In order to check whether one of the animation directions was able to direct the eye to the hazard, the time elapsed between activation of the warning and the first glance in the hazard direction was examined. In order to determine both main and interaction effects of »warning transition«, »animation« and »hazard direction«, a three-factorial analysis of variance was calculated for repeated measurement designs. There was a significant main effect of the »animation direction« $F(1,27)=11.74$. Drivers looked slower in the hazard direction in an animation »from hazard to driver« than in an animation »from driver to hazard« $p = .002$, $r = .55$. (Figure 10.8). Furthermore, there was a significant main effect for the »driving direction« $F(1,27)=7.99$. When the vehicle cut from the right, drivers looked into the »driving direction« faster than when it cut from the left $p = .009$, $r = .48$. There were no other significant interaction or main effects on gaze reaction time.

10.4 Discussion

This study examined the effect of different design variants of a two-stage warning on braking response and gaze behavior. To this end, the »direction of animation« of a pre-warning and

Figure 10.9: Overview of eye movements for all warning conditions for the warning period when the vehicle is cutting. The point in time marked as »crash« indicates when the intersection was passed at the level of the vehicle. If the brakes were not applied in time, the crash happened here. The relative gaze distribution of all test drivers over five areas is plotted. The areas road, LED bar (LED) and speedometer were permanently assigned. Eyes directed towards the hazard (Hazard) or in the direction opposite to the hazard (Not Hazard) were determined by looking to the right or left and the respective approach direction of the intersecting vehicle.

the »warning transition« between both warning levels were varied.

A continuous warning transition speeds up the reaction Contrary to expectations, the test drivers reacted faster to a »continuous« warning transition than to an »abrupt« one. Since the increase was already visible with a »continuous« »warning transition« before the hard change with »abrupt« »warning transition«, this is not fundamentally surprising. However, this »warning transition«, which was already visible earlier, contained no information about the upcoming reaction. This means that the test drivers were not allowed to simply react to the increase already, but had to wait until the main warning became visible in order to avoid a false reaction. In fact, most of the test drivers succeeded in doing this, but it turned out that they left the gas earlier with »continuous« »warning transition«. It is noticeable that the flashing of the pre-warning alone did not lead to this effect. This indicates that regardless of the information content of the warning, the increase in the light bar activated the test subjects and they prepared themselves for the braking reaction. This level of activation could not be caused by the presentation of the pre-warning alone. This effect could be used in practice to prepare drivers for a reaction at an early stage. A smooth transition between discreet indication and conspicuous warning is thus a promising approach to achieve a compromise between early activation of the driver and low obtrusiveness. In this way, it should be possible to accelerate the reaction compared to a one-step warning system or a two-step warning system with an abrupt warning transition without compromising the acceptance of the system too much. However, this study did not investigate whether a growing animation is actually perceived as less intrusive than a flashing display of the final size. This would still need to be shown and future studies could test this correlation.

Disadvantage of an animation from the hazard to the driver In this study, the drivers' gaze behavior could actually be influenced. But not in the expected way. While no advantage could be achieved by an animation, a negative effect of the animation »from hazard to driver« was shown. It impaired the gaze jumps in the direction of the hazard. Apparently, this animation confused the drivers and kept their view on the road. This negative effect should be avoided when designing animated fuzzy directional signs.

Conclusion In this study, it was shown that a soft warning transition in a two-stage hazard warning is a promising approach to prepare drivers for an early response. However, an animation »from the hazard to the driver« should be avoided.

11 Final Discussion

The aim of this thesis was to evaluate whether a Fuzzy Warning is suitable as a display for FAS. This was done in seven studies in which different aspects relevant to suitability were examined. Prior to this work, there were only a few studies on the effect of a Fuzzy Warning in a motor vehicle. Although some authors have already researched the effect of concrete fuzzy assistance functions in various application cases (Mahlke et al., 2007; Fricke, 2009; Maier et al., 2011), the findings were obtained using very different concepts in very specific scenarios. Overarching relationships and especially the influence of individual design aspects are difficult to determine due to the diversity in the methods and systems used. In addition, fundamental prerequisites, such as proof of sufficiently good visibility of peripheral light signals at the point of use and understanding of this type of warning, have not been examined to date. All in all, a holistic view of the warning concept was lacking, which represents the human processing processes involved, summarizes the previous findings, examines the prerequisites for use and systematically researches the effect of individual design aspects.

The present work starts here by first examining the concept on a very basic level and then, step by step, approaching concrete application scenarios. In this way, the present work has made it possible to create a comprehensive profile of the effect of a Fuzzy Warning.

Will the Fuzzy Warning be seen and understood peripherally? In the first part of the thesis it could be shown that the basic requirements for the use of a Fuzzy Warning in an automobile are fulfilled. On the one hand, peripheral light signals in the area of the front windshield root are clearly visible to people of different heights (Chapter 4) and on the other hand, various functions of the display are intuitively understood by drivers, although no semantic clues such as symbols or characters are used (Chapter 5). Furthermore, it was shown that an exemplary Fuzzy Warning was actually looked at less than a classic warning system (Chapter 6) and resulted in comparable to better response times (Chapter 7).

The measurement of the peripheral field of view in the traffic context is not new in itself. Other works have already approached the topic and determined the visibility of peripheral light signals in real or simulated car driving (Cohen, 1987; Trösterer et al., 2010).

However, previous studies have not been able to provide information on peripheral perception for the area at the base of the windshield. This area is particularly well suited for peripheral warnings, since no information from the environment is obscured, but the area is still very close to the usual focus of vision. In this work not only the result that peripheral perception decreases with increasing eccentricity could be replicated, but the results from Chapter 4 also provide concrete information about peripheral perception in this area and also perception distributions for the views to the side mirrors that are common in the traffic context. In the driver's core area (up to 110 cm away from the side mirrors), more than 95 % of the peripheral signals are usually consciously perceived when looking straight ahead. Even beyond that in the outermost area (119-129 cm) at least 80 % were still noticed. Only when looking away from the front direction, for example to the left side mirror, the detection probability of the light signals decreased to 60 %.

The results from this work thus extend the previous findings and transfer them to the ideal location of a Fuzzy Warning. The values only apply to the tested light signals. It can be assumed that the detection rates can be significantly improved by brighter or wider signals. At the time

of this writing, no research work seems to have dealt with the intuitive comprehensibility of symbol-free warnings in motor vehicles. Previous studies that investigated Fuzzy Warning concepts practically presupposed an understanding of the systems or explained the function of the display before the experiment (Laquai et al., 2010, 2011; Mahlke et al., 2007; Fricke, 2009; Maier et al., 2010, 2011). However, especially if a behavioral adjustment is to be achieved that goes beyond reflex braking, it is necessary for drivers to understand what message the display is intended to convey to them. The results of this work show for the first time that different messages can be successfully conveyed to drivers by means of a symbol-free display in the form of a LED bar without having to explain the function to them beforehand. In addition, it was shown that drivers even unsolicitedly adapted their driving behavior due to the fuzzy display and moved more safely on the road with the display by choosing a more appropriate speed. Fuzzy Warnings can therefore be used as information and warning displays in the vehicle. A symbol-free display did not prevent the message presented from being understood in the present investigation setting.

The concept of Fuzzy Warnings promises to have several advantages over classic displays. One hypothesis was that the symbol-free display would distract drivers less because it could be perceived from the corner of the eye and no additional information could be obtained by looking directly at it. Already Mahlke et al. (2007) recognized the importance of this question and measured both the duration of the gaze assignment and the subjectively perceived effort of one symbol-free and five additional night vision systems. They found that the symbol-free system was not only looked at significantly less overall, but that the subjectively perceived effort with the symbol-free system did not differ from the control condition without the system, in contrast to four other systems. However, in the study by Mahlke et al. (2007) night vision systems were used as a reference, displaying video images of the visual scene in real time. A moving video image is much more complex than a simple symbolic representation as it is common in vehicles. Therefore, the question arose whether the results could be transferred to these simpler systems. To close this gap, this question was investigated in the present work (Chapter 6).

In fact, the unimodal fuzzy LED warning was also looked at less than a simple bimodal symbolic warning in the combined display. Thus, the effect of reduced visual distraction of drivers found by Mahlke et al. (2007) is not only valid for complex animated video images, but also for a simple symbolic warning as it is used today. This suggests that symbol-free warnings are less straining than other displays, both cognitively and visually. A higher level of stress can limit vehicle control and the ability to react to critical events (Engström, Johansson, & Östlund, 2005; Strayer, Drews, & Johnston, 2003). In this way, a Fuzzy Warning can help to increase driving safety.

Another benefit that was expected due to the Fuzzy Warning is an improvement in driver reaction time. The most comprehensive investigation of response times to uni- and bimodal Fuzzy Warning compared to other systems has been conducted by Maier et al. (2010). They were able to show an advantage of the LED bar compared to a system faded into the windshield. In comparison with a classic symbolic display behind the steering wheel, the LED-bar achieved equally good reaction times. In general, a bimodal fuzzy warning was responded to more quickly than a unimodal one. In view of the fact that the Fuzzy Warning leads to a lower strain on the driver, an equally good reaction time to a classic system can already be considered an advantage. In the study presented in Chapter 7 this effect could also be replicated in the case of a small unimodal Fuzzy Warning, which was only 36 % of the width of the windshield root. This finding is relevant for the practical use of the display. For example, the cost of a new assistance system is an important factor for market penetration, because normally customers have to pay for it themselves. A bar that is only displayed in a small area in front of the driver is much cheaper than a bar that covers the entire width of the windshield root. However, the

cheapest solution is to use an already existing system in the vehicle. This option was also examined in Chapter 7. It could be shown that the effect of an already existing display can be enhanced by using a Fuzzy Warning instead of a symbolic one. Basically, it would even make sense to use already existing displays for the presentation of Fuzzy Warnings. However, it is not yet known how the Fuzzy Warning works in interaction with other displays that are presented at the same location. Further research is therefore necessary before this option can actually be considered.

How do drivers react to Fuzzy Warnings? Eye-tracking by light signals is already a well-researched area (see Chapter 2.2.3). However, most of the results were obtained in laboratory settings using simple stimulus-response measurements. They are therefore not necessarily transferable to the driving context. In order to make a statement about eye tracking in the traffic context, it was therefore necessary to replicate the effects known from basic research. A first step in this direction was already taken by Mahlke et al. (2007). Here, eye movements on different night vision systems including a Fuzzy Warning were investigated in a real driving situation. However, the focus of this study was not on the targeted eye movement towards objects on the road, but on the eye distraction caused by the tested systems. The relation between the systems and the correct identification of pedestrians at the roadside at night was recorded. All cases in which drivers identified pedestrians but did not look at the system beforehand or did not indicate having used the system for identification were excluded from the evaluation. This excludes precisely those cases that lead to a direct gaze towards the target object and also those cases in which the test drivers may have benefited from the display without being aware of it. The study presented in Chapter 8 circumvented these limitations by directly examining the gaze behavior towards the street. Contrary to expectation, only a weak gaze control could be achieved. In Chapter 10 even a negative effect was shown by one of the tested animations. This indicates that a Fuzzy Warning in the form in which it was investigated is hardly suitable for directing the driver's attention to potential hazards. The results are therefore very similar to those of Mahlke et al. (2007). Even though the LED bar was responsible for most of the identification compared to the other night vision systems, only 10 % of pedestrians were recognized with this system. Compared to basic research, both results cannot replicate the high success rates from the laboratory.

In the laboratory, involuntary gaze orientation can be caused by sudden appearance or an abrupt increase in brightness (Irwin et al., 2000). One reason for the weaker effects in the applied traffic context could be the lower salience of the cue stimuli. The driving situation is much more complex than the laboratory situation and while in the laboratory the main task is to process the task, the drivers on the road have to pay primary attention to the traffic. Furthermore, in most of the scenarios investigated so far, the target stimuli are presented on the same fixation level as the cue stimuli. With respect to the situation in the vehicle and a Fuzzy Warning, however, the cue stimulus (warning) is relatively located in front of the fixation level (road). As a consequence, drivers tend to focus on other aspects of the situation in the traffic situation rather than the display. The effect could probably be enhanced by a more conspicuous design of the directional warning. This would be a starting point for future investigations to achieve a visual guidance in the vehicle. A possibility to make the display more conspicuous was investigated in Chapter 10. Here an animation to or from the hazard direction was used to direct the driver's gaze. In fact, a steering of the gaze could be achieved, but surprisingly with a negative effect. While an animation from the driver towards the hazard had no significant influence on the eye movement, an animation from the hazard to the driver rather distracted the driver and slowed down the view to the hazard. An influence on the driver therefore does take place, but it is more difficult to create a positive effect than to avoid a negative one. The results from Chapter 10 show that the display can also distract the drivers

if it is designed incorrectly. If the effect of the warning is maximized, it is likely that a reliable visual orientation can be achieved, but in doing so the driver will also be distracted by any other events that are happening. This would be unfavorable if the system is not absolutely reliable or if several events that require a response occur simultaneously. It should therefore be avoided to achieve a purely involuntary gaze orientation. A compromise would be a display that clearly indicates a hazard without patronizing the driver. How can this be achieved?

While reflexive reactions are automatic and highly reliable, non-reflexive reactions require practice to be performed quickly and efficiently. To optimize the response to a directional signal, drivers must learn to use the system in traffic. If drivers learn that a fuzzy directional signal points them to important objects, they are likely to use it for orientation on their own. This aspect could not yet be investigated in the experiments conducted so far due to the short duration of the experiments. Long-term studies with reliable systems are necessary to show whether longer exposure can lead to better support for drivers.

How can the effect of Fuzzy Warnings be optimized? In the third part of the thesis, two studies were conducted to investigate how the design of a Fuzzy Warning can be optimized. Here it was shown that when combining several functions in one display, negative effects can occur if displays that require different reactions are designed very similarly (Chapter 9). Furthermore, the example of a multi-stage warning showed a reaction advantage of a continuous warning transition compared to an abrupt one (Chapter 10).

Due to the limited space in the vehicle compartment, displays are sometimes used for different functions. This is also conceivable for Fuzzy Warning. When combining more than one function in one display, however, it must be noted that transfer effects may occur if the displays are similarly designed (Möller & Frings, 2010). Especially when combining hints and warnings, this can lead to undesired side effects, since warnings require immediate reaction to the display but not to the hints. However, the results of Möller and Frings (2010) were obtained in the laboratory and it was not yet clear whether they could actually be transferred to road traffic. Previous investigations on Fuzzy Warning have dealt exclusively with individual warning systems and prior to this work there was no knowledge about the effects of sharing the display for different purposes. In this work the effect found by Möller and Frings (2010) was transferred to the applied field and examined using the example of a fog information (Chapter 9). The results indicate that overreactions can indeed occur when warnings and information are combined in one display and have a very similar design. The results of Möller and Frings (2010) obtained from simple stimulus-response experiments could thus be replicated in a driving simulator test closer to the application using the example of a Fuzzy Warning. This suggests that the effect of the transmission of effects must be taken into account when combining information and warning systems. A displayed message that informs the driver about an event at an early stage should differ sufficiently from a warning that requires an immediate reaction. However, further research is necessary to determine where exactly the limit lies and in which application scenarios this effect must be considered. The results also show that a sufficiently different design can be achieved even within the Fuzzy Warning by adjusting size, shape and color.

While this study examined the effect of combining warning and information messages that are relatively far apart in time, there is also the possibility of combining them in very short sequences. If both stages occur directly one after the other, one can speak of a single two-stage warning instead of two systems. This has the advantage that information about a potential hazard can be given at an early stage without immediately disturbing the driver with an obtrusive warning. The benefit of a two-stage warning has already been demonstrated by Maier et al. (2011). However, no knowledge was available yet about how a transition between the two warning levels should be designed. This was investigated in Chapter 10. It could be shown that a continuous warning transition led to faster reactions than an abrupt one. The drivers

reacted to the transition with an action preparation, although they knew that the transition did not provide information about a necessary intervention. The results initially apply to a very specific experimental situation. However, the examined design corresponds to a realistic implementation (section 10.2.3). This argues in favor of using continuous warning transitions when two-stage Fuzzy Warnings are used.

Conclusion Based on these findings, the following picture emerges: The Fuzzy Warning in form of a LED bar at the root of the windshield is quite suitable for displaying various assistance functions. The results obtained indicate that the symbol-free display is less likely to distract the driver from the road while still having the same effect. Especially due to the larger warning area or proximity to the visual focus, a purely visual warning can achieve the same good response as a bimodal visual-acoustic classic warning or even a gain in response if the Fuzzy Warning is also presented bimodally and thus visually-acoustically. It is interesting here that the positive effect in the present experiment could even be achieved with a classical display, which is already available in many vehicles. This indicates that in principle not even a new display would have to be installed in vehicles to take advantage of the benefits of a Fuzzy Warning. Thus, already today a Fuzzy Warning concept could be implemented with little effort. Since no clear indication of a visual guidance effect has been found so far, the concepts investigated up to now do not appear to be suitable for the targeted visual orientation of drivers.

Outlook The new warning concept of the Fuzzy Warning thus has the potential to relieve drivers and improve their reactions in comparison with classic displays. This opens up a whole new area for warning systems. Even though a symbolic representation of displays is widely used, the results of this work show that displays can be designed differently without losing functionality. Fuzzy Warnings open up new possibilities for designers to integrate displays in vehicles in an unobtrusive and appealing way. Although the effectiveness in individual application scenarios still needs to be demonstrated, the first results suggest that different displays could be replaced by fuzzy systems or new displays could be displayed in this way. In the future, Fuzzy Warnings could be installed in the vehicle instead of or in addition to classical displays, thus reducing the complexity of displays and warnings in the vehicle again.

Due to the increase in available information and assistance in the vehicle, the density of presented content is increasing. While 20 years ago, mainly analog displays with fixed functions were installed in the dashboard, today there are more and more small screens that can display changing contents and show different functions via one display. Even though the instructions and warnings can provide the driver with important information on navigation, potential hazards and traffic control, this does not mean that the driver can absorb them all. The challenge is to design the human-machine interface and to present the information in a way that it can be used effectively.

A Fuzzy Warning offers a way to get closer to this goal. The results of this work show that the use of a Fuzzy Warning does not automatically make a system 'better'. The way of implementation plays an important role here as well. But if designed correctly, a Fuzzy Warning offers important advantages over symbolic displays. Faster reactions, less distraction and higher acceptance can be achieved. In this thesis and also in previous studies on Fuzzy Warnings, only individual systems were examined. An exciting question is to what extent displays in the vehicle can be replaced by a fuzzy display. In this thesis, a generic indication of driving too fast led drivers to adjust their speed. Do drivers really need to know exactly what their exact speed in km/h is at any given time? Is it not enough to know whether they are driving at an appropriate speed for the given situation? A dynamic indicator that determines the maximum permitted speed based on the current situation and position would only have to be activated in the event of a violation. This reduces the information density that is conveyed

to the drivers by filtering the information to an absolutely necessary level. By shifting a part of the situation assessment to the vehicle, the drivers can be relieved. There is no patronage as in the case of complete driving automation, but support in a part of the driving task. In this way, drivers can concentrate more on driving itself.

This thought may seem strange at first, since the choice of speed in km/h and the comparison with permitted speeds has so far been an integral part of the driving task. But on closer inspection, the transfer of part of the driving task to a system is not so unusual. The introduction of the electric starter was already one such step. Drivers no longer had to start their engines themselves, but only needed to operate the ignition. Another example is the use of navigation systems. Here too, the driver or passenger no longer has to carry maps and determine the route. Instead, only the destination is entered at the start of the journey and then the system's instructions are followed. From this point of view, it is questionable whether the constant reading of the current speed at the speedometer and the permitted maximum speed of signs at the roadside must continue to be part of the driving task. The necessity of other displays can also be questioned in this way. The extreme case would certainly be a single fuzzy display which, depending on the situation, would only show the currently relevant information and would be inactive when the driver is moving safely in traffic. The underlying concept is that of a generic warning, which is a research topic in itself. A warning that provides very general information does not necessarily have to be implemented by means of a Fuzzy Warning. However, the special characteristics of a Fuzzy Warning lead to a closer look at the concept of a generic warning. This opens up a wide field for further research.

The further transfer of subtasks of driving to the vehicle, such as a dynamic speed warning, requires comprehensive and highly up-to-date information from vehicle sensors and infrastructure. This is the only way to enable the vehicle to assess the situation in the respective sub-area as well as a driver can. Today's technology makes this increasingly realistic. In the past, it was not possible to build a speedometer that would independently assess the current situation and calculate the appropriate speed based on weather, road section, traffic and existing regulation. However, we are now in a time in which even completely autonomous vehicles are no longer science fiction due to major advances in information processing and sensor technology. Therefore, there is no longer any technical reason against the use of fuzzy displays in vehicles. The only question that needs to be asked is to what extent the paradigm of very generic displays in the vehicle is advantageous for road traffic.

Many years of research in the field of road safety have led to a reduction in the number of accident fatalities in Germany over the last 40 years to a quarter of the level at that time, despite increasing traffic density. If this trend is to continue, even the non-obvious ways to reduce accidents must be found and used. This work has shown that Fuzzy Warnings are a promising new approach to achieve just that.

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